

SCHOOL OF BUSINESS AND CREATIVE INDUSTRIES

**CHARISMATIC FEMALE LEADERSHIP: AN ADOPTABLE
LEADERSHIP MODEL FOR SUSTAINABLE SMES IN
NIGERIA**

University of The West of Scotland, London Campus

School of Business and Creative Industries

**Charismatic Female Leadership: An Adoptable Leadership
Model For Sustainable SMEs In Nigeria.**

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ABSTRACT

Gender discrimination, weaker sex stigmatisation, and a lack of career advancement and training opportunities have all been and continue to be recurring decimals in Nigerian enterprises. Although the National Bureau of Statistics (NBC) reports that women made up 50% of the Nigerian population in 2017, only about 21% of registered entrepreneurial businesses in Nigeria are run by women. Having said that, Nigeria's small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) continue to face the difficult fate of unsustainability. This has been attributed to poor leadership or, at the very least, the choice and use of an ineffective leadership style. Currently, studies have investigated various leadership styles, such as Transactional, Transformational, Coercive, Charismatic, and Full range leadership styles, but none has highlighted or suggested which one is thought to be the most effective and would support the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. This study aims to examine how women leadership impact on SMEs and to suggest an adoptable leadership model for SME sustainability in Nigeria. This is achieved by investigating the impact of various leadership models on the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria.

To achieve this, a mixed research method of combining both quantitative and qualitative approach with a view to achieving a holistic, well-balanced, and objective research project was adopted. Quantitative data for this study comprised of data got from a tailored research questionnaire. Nonprobability convenience sampling method was adopted, 231 responses were received from the research questionnaire. To analyse the data gathered from quantitative survey, the SPSS was used. The qualitative study used semi-structured interviews to fill gaps in the quantitative study data questionnaire by providing participants' more detailed personal experiences and opinions. Through convenience sampling, 17 people were chosen from the

general population to participate in face-to-face semi-structured interviews with open-ended questions and the data was analysed using the NVIVO software. Data was presented in the form of charts and frequency distribution tables, along with the corresponding percentages. To test the causality relationship in accordance with the study's hypotheses, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used. The goal was to examine the inter-variable correlation and describe the strength and direction of the relationship between variables.

Overall, the findings of all studies suggested that embracing female leadership could improve the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria, and charismatic leadership was found to be more effective in Nigeria than other leadership styles.

DECLARATION

While registered as a candidate for the above degree, I have not been registered for any other research award. This research, result and conclusions embodied in this thesis are the work of the above-named candidate (Temidayo Eunice Fayemi) and have not been submitted for any other academic awards. Material from other work has been acknowledged and quotations and paraphrases suitably indicated.

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DEDICATION

This research is dedicated to God Almighty for the grace and strength to start this thesis and to complete it. Also, I dedicate this to my little nephew (Abimifoluwa Asher) who I never got to hold. You will always have a special place in my heart.

TABLE OF CONTENT

ABSTRACT	II
DECLARATION	IV
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	V
DEDICATION	VI
TABLE OF CONTENT	VII
LIST OF TABLES	X
LIST OF FIGURES	XI
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	XII
CHAPTER ONE	1
1.0 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY	1
1.2 RESEARCH AIM.....	7
1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS	7
1.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES	8
1.5 RESEARCH SCOPE	8
1.6 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM	9
1.7 RESEARCH RATIONALE/GAP	11
1.8 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY DESCRIPTION	13
1.9 RESEARCH OUTLINE	15
1.10 CONCLUSION	17
CHAPTER TWO	18
2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW	18
2.1 INTRODUCTION	18
2.2 THE GENERAL CONCEPT OF LEADERSHIP	20
2.3 MODELS OF LEADERSHIP	24
2.3.1 <i>Authentic Leadership Model</i>	26
2.3.2 <i>Situational Leadership Model</i>	29
2.3.3 <i>Charismatic Leadership Model</i>	31
2.3.4 <i>Full Range Leadership Model</i>	33
2.4 THE CONCEPT OF SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES.....	38
2.4.1 <i>Small And Medium Scale Enterprises Versus Entrepreneurship</i>	41
2.4.2 <i>Small and Medium Scale Enterprises In Africa</i>	43
2.4.3 <i>Small And Medium Scale Enterprises In Nigeria</i>	46
2.5 SMEs ENVIRONMENT IN NIGERIA	49
2.5.1 <i>PEST Analysis Of SMEs In Nigeria</i>	49
2.5.2 <i>Relevance Of Small And Medium Enterprises To The Nigerian Economy</i>	54
2.5.3 <i>Leadership In SMEs</i>	57
2.5.4 <i>Gender And Entrepreneur Leadership In Nigeria</i>	60
2.5.5 <i>Challenges Facing Women Leadership In Nigeria SMEs</i>	62
2.5.6 <i>Factors That Contribute Towards Women Leadership In Nigeria SMEs</i>	64
2.6 THE CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABILITY AND KEY VARIABLES OF SUSTAINABLE SME	67
2.6.1 <i>Sustainability And Its Indicators</i>	67

2.6.2	<i>Constraints To Sustainable SMEs In Nigeria</i>	71
2.6.3	<i>Contribution of Women Leadership Towards Sustainable SMEs</i>	75
2.6.4	<i>Leadership Model For Sustainable SMEs</i>	77
2.6.5	<i>Charismatic Women Leadership for Sustainable SMEs</i>	79
2.7	CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	80
2.7.1	<i>Literature Gaps</i>	83
2.8	RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS	85
2.9	CONCLUSION	85
CHAPTER THREE.....		87
3.0	RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	87
3.1	INTRODUCTION	87
3.2	METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK.....	88
3.3	RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY.....	91
3.3.1	<i>Positivism</i>	94
3.3.2	<i>Interpretivism</i>	96
3.3.3	<i>Pragmatism</i>	98
3.3.4	<i>Realism</i>	100
3.3.5	<i>Chosen Research Paradigm Rationale</i>	102
3.4	RESEARCH APPROACH	103
3.4.1	<i>Inductive Approach</i>	104
3.4.2	<i>Deductive Approach</i>	105
3.5	RESEARCH DESIGN	106
3.5.1	<i>Research Method: Quantitative</i>	107
3.5.2	<i>Research Method: Qualitative</i>	108
3.5.3	<i>Research Method: Mixed</i>	110
3.6	REQUIREMENTS OF DATA	111
3.6.1	<i>Sampling Method</i>	113
3.6.2	<i>Data Collection: Primary And Secondary</i>	116
3.7	DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES	118
3.7.1	<i>Quantitative Data Analysis Technique</i>	118
3.7.2	<i>Qualitative Data Analysis Technique</i>	119
3.8	ETHICAL CONSIDERATION.....	120
3.9	CHALLENGES/LIMITATIONS IN DATA COLLECTION PROCESS	122
3.10	CONCLUSION	123
CHAPTER 4.....		124
4.0	RESULTS AND FINDINGS.....	124
4.1	INTRODUCTION	124
4.2	QUANTITATIVE DATA PRESENTATION	124
4.2.1	<i>Respondent Demographics</i>	125
4.2.2	<i>Respondent's Experience</i>	126
4.2.3	<i>The Impediments To SMEs Sustainability In Nigeria</i>	128
4.2.4	<i>The Effect of Women Leadership on SMEs Sustainability in Nigeria</i>	135
4.2.5	<i>Charismatic Leadership; An Effective Leadership Model For Sustainable SMEs In Nigeria</i>	141
4.3	QUALITATIVE DATA PRESENTATION	147
4.3.1	<i>Introduction</i>	147
4.3.2	<i>Demographics of Respondents</i>	149
4.3.3	<i>Factors That Contributes To SMEs Sustainability</i>	150
4.3.4	<i>Leadership Models As Preferred By Respondents</i>	151
4.3.5	<i>Leadership Values</i>	153
4.3.6	<i>Leadership Styles That Encourages SMEs Sustainability</i>	154
4.3.7	<i>Leadership Model That Best Suit Women Leaders</i>	155
CHAPTER 5.....		157
5.0	DISCUSSION	157

5.1	THE INFLUENCE OF AGE GROUP ON NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY GRADUATES' ENTREPRENEURIAL AMBITIONS.	157
5.2	THE RATIO OF FEMALE TO MALE ENTREPRENEURS IN NIGERIA.....	158
5.3	TECHNICAL KNOW-HOW A FUEL FOR BUSINESS SUSTAINABILITY.	159
5.4	IMPRACTICABLE OR NO SUSTAINABLE FORECASTS	160
5.5	THE IMPACT OF ENTERPRISE EXPERIENCE AND EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION ON NIGERIA SMES 161	
5.6	JOB MIGRATION AND EMPLOYABILITY	162
5.7	IMPEDIMENTS TO SME SUSTAINABILITY.....	163
5.8	LEADERSHIP AS A FACTOR TO IMPROVING SUSTAINABILITY	165
5.9	LEADERSHIP MODELS FOR SUSTAINABLE SMES IN NIGERIA	166
5.10	FACTORS THAT CONTRIBUTES TOWARDS WOMEN LEADERSHIP IN NIGERIA SMES	167
5.11	IMPACT OF WOMEN LEADERSHIP ON SME SUSTAINABILITY IN NIGERIA.....	169
5.12	CHARISMATIC LEADERSHIP; AN EFFECTIVE LEADERSHIP MODEL FOR SUSTAINABLE SMES IN NIGERIA 171	
5.13	ADOPTABLE LEADERSHIP MODEL FOR WOMEN, THAT CAN DRIVE A SUSTAINABLE SME IN NIGERIA 173	
CHAPTER 6	176
6.0	GENERAL CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK.....	176
6.1	INTRODUCTION	176
6.2	SUMMARY: CONCEPTUAL MODEL	177
6.3	SUMMARY: LITERATURE GAP	177
6.4	SUMMARY: METHODOLOGY	178
6.5	SUMMARY: FINDINGS.....	178
6.5.1	<i>Leadership models for sustainable SMEs.</i>	<i>179</i>
6.5.2	<i>Factors that contributes to women leadership in SMEs.....</i>	<i>179</i>
6.5.3	<i>Contributions of Women Leadership to sustainable SME in Nigeria</i>	<i>180</i>
6.5.4	<i>Women's leadership has positive relationship with SME sustainability</i>	<i>180</i>
6.5.5	<i>Charismatic Leadership: An Effective Leadership Model for Long-Term SME Sustainability in Nigeria. 180</i>	
6.6	CONCLUSIONS	180
6.7	RECOMMENDATION OR FUTURE WORK.....	181
6.8	LIMITATION OF RESEARCH.....	182
7.0	REFERENCES.....	184
8.0	APPENDIX	209
8.1	PARTICIPANTS' INFORMATION SHEET FOR THE INTERVIEW	209
8.2	SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE	210
8.3	SEMI-STRUCTURE INTERVIEW	213

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Age groups distribution in relation to gender	126
Table 2: Enterprise Experience and Educational Qualification Crosstabulation.....	127
Table 3: Mean and Standard deviation of financial hurdle.....	128
Table 4: Mean and Standard deviation of lack of infrastructural facilities.....	129
Table 5: : Mean and Standard deviation of poor management	129
Table 6: Mean and Standard deviation of gender discrimination	130
Table 7: Mean and Standard deviation of leadership problem	131
Table 8: Model fitting test for the variables that influence SME sustainability	131
Table 9: The percentage effect of the variables on SMEs sustainability	132
Table 10: Regression analysis to test for significance	135
Table 11: Mean and Standard deviation of the effect of women leadership on SMEs.....	136
Table 12: Model fitting test for effect of women leaders on SME sustainability.....	137
Table 13: The percentage effect of women leadership on SMEs sustainability	137
Table 14: Regression analysis for test of significance.....	140
Table 15: Model fitting test.....	142
Table 16: The percentage effect of the variables on SMEs sustainability	142
Table 17: Effect of leadership styles on SMEs sustainability.....	145

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework	81
Figure 2: Saunders' Research Onion (Saunders et al., 2009).....	93
Figure 3: Sample Size Calculator Used	115
Figure 4: The difference in percentage of women and men involved in the quantitative survey.....	125
Figure 5: Word cloud of what the participants discussed mostly.	148
Figure 6: Conceptual Framework	149
Figure 7: The respondents' proportion comparison in terms of marital status, gender, education level, age group and enterprise experience.	149
Figure 8: : Opinions of our respondents on what factors they believe could improve sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria	150
Figure 9: Male and female respondents' preferred leadership styles used in their businesses	152
Figure 10: Participant's thought on the leadership values as displayed by both male and female leaders	153
Figure 11: Leadership style that encourage SMEs sustainability	154
Figure 12: Respondents' perceptions of the best leadership style for female entrepreneurs.	155

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACGSF	Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund
BOI	Bank of Industry
CBN	Central Bank of Nigeria
CEDAW	Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women
EDC	Entrepreneurship Development Centres
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GEM	Global Entrepreneurship Monitor
GNI	Gross National Income
IMF	International Monetary Fund
NAFDAC	National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control
NBCI	Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry
NBS	National Bureau of Statistics
NEPC	Nigeria Export Promotion Council
NERFUND	National Economic Reconstruction Fund
NEXIM	Nigerian Export-Import Bank
NGOs	Non- Governmental Organizations
NIDB	Nigerian Industrial Development Bank
NYSC	National Youth Service Corps
SAP	Structural Adjustment Programme
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PPP	Purchasing Power Parity
PZ	Patterson and Zochonis
SAP	Structural Adjustment Programme
SMEDAN	Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria

SMIEIS	Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme
UAC	United African Company
YouWIN	Youth Enterprise with Innovation

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The growth and operations of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) is a key driver and indicator for meaningful and sustainable development. This is because the SME subsector is fundamental to the socio-economic transformation of any nation (Aremu and Adeyemi, 2011). According to Alese (2017) most of the nations of the world that have prioritized SME have attained substantial increase in various sectors of their economy. These include; development of indigenous entrepreneurship, increase in income per capita, rapid growth in national output, improvement in export earnings, reduction in poverty level and its correlates of rural-urban migration and crime rate to achieve sustainable livelihood.

Globally, a SME is defined as any recognized business or venture with annual turnover, in America dollar terms, of between ten and one thousand times the mean per capita Gross National Income (GNI), at purchasing power parity (PPP) of the operating country (Gibson and Van dar vaart, 2018). Likewise, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) are described as non-subsiary, independent firms which employ less than a given number of employees (Highland, 2019). This number varies across countries and the most frequent upper limit scale designating an SME is 250 employees, as in the European Union as well as in the United Kingdom. However, some countries set the limit at 200 employees, while the United States of America considers SMEs to include firms with fewer than 500 employees (Highland, 2019).

Within the Nigerian context, The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in its 1995 Credit Guidelines cited in Montilewe, Ogbari and Aka (2015), defines a SME as an enterprise with a labour force between 11 and 300, fixed capital/asset of N5million to N500 million (\$26,932 and \$2,693,240) and turnover of below 100 million (\$538,648) per annum.

Nonetheless, these descriptions of SME mainly captured quantitative indices which are prone to periodic economic fluctuations. To make up for limitations of quantitative definitions Obaseki (2015) defines SMEs as a very heterogeneous group of businesses ranging from single unincorporated entrepreneurs to medium-sized listed companies, mostly owner-managed in a personalized way with little or no adequate professional support. Furthermore, SMEs are flexible with simple organisational structure, labour intensive, capital saving and employment catalyst capable of helping to create most of the one billion new jobs the world will need by the end of the century. Additionally, with the aid of SMEs, regions with local economic activity can acquire more income which in turn could potentially enhance wealth and further employments opportunities (Reuben, 2019; Eniola and Ektebang, 2014).

Alese (2017) avers that the SME subsector is the largest business sector in the world economy which a developing country should not ignore. Furthermore, SMEs are considered to be a vital driving force for the economic growth and the creation of employment in developed as well as developing countries, contributing to the growth of employment at a rate that is higher than that of large-scale or bigger organisations (Abeh, 2017; Highland, 2019). SMEs have demonstrated extraordinary potentials for sustainable development as it is mainly the route by which employees made redundant by larger organisations have been admitted back into work fold (Eniola and Ektebang, 2014). They are also perceived as necessary for the attainment of National Economic objectives of poverty alleviation, wealth creation, work generation, increase in Gross Domestic Product (GDP), equitable distribution of resources, reduction of income disparities, curtailing rural-urban migration, stimulation of technological

innovation, entrepreneurial skills development, rural development acceleration, diversification, harnessing of native raw materials and expansion of industrial production (Moses *et al.*, 2015; Taiwo *et al.*, 2016; Abeh, 2017).

Historically, the orientation of SMEs has been an integral aspect of Nigeria's antiquity, stretching back to the pre-colonial (self-reliant) entrepreneurial prowess of our forebears vis-à-vis their wood carving, farming, poultry, iron production, cottage businesses, etc. Ningi and Mairigi (2015) succinctly affirm that SMEs have existed in Nigeria for centuries now as most of them grew from indigenous cottage industries. Unfortunately, the advent of Colonialism in Nigeria saw the previously indigenous entrepreneurial climate become dominated by European Multinational Corporations, who exploited the Nigerian economy to the detriment of the indigenous small-scale industries (Ayozie, Oborah, Umukoro and Ayozie, 2016). The drawback of this exploitation was further underscored by Udensi, (2015) that:

“Those initial multi-national corporations fashioned differential economic consequences amongst their originating country and their colonies by a process of exploiting colonial resources and manpower and investing the resulting profits and net increase in their own country, culminating in the advancement of the colonizer and the impoverishment of the colonized”.

Fortunately, Nigeria's attainment of independence in 1960 marked a new era in the evolution of the SME subsector, particularly with the introduction of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986, which gave more recognition to the SME subsector as a remedy for ameliorating unemployment, poverty and criminality in Nigeria as well as for the attainment of a self-reliant economy (Abeh, 2017). The enhancement of SMEs operations to promote sustainability thus became a major concern for policy makers and stakeholders of Nigerian's economy. Baroni (2018) affirms that enhancing SMEs sustainability necessitated why government focus shifted from large scale industrial projects (which are more capital

intensive and less labour intensive) to SMEs which invariably have better prospects for evolving domestic economy. Edam (2019) corroborates that for this purpose, the Federal Government of Nigeria since independence in 1960 has initiated series of developmental programmes and policies to enhance SMEs survival and growth. Likewise it sought collaborative effort with International Establishments, Civil Organizations, Bilateral and Multilateral Interventions and Non- Governmental Groups to steer SMEs support; while regulating SMEs operations via the CBN.

Regardless of the recognition and positive attention given to small and medium scale ventures and entrepreneurship in Nigeria, the performance of the enterprises are still below expectation and less than satisfactory. For example, reports of the 2001 Nigerian Economic Summit Group cited in Okafor, Onifade and Ogbechi (2018), revealed that SMEs performance at the post-independence era degraded with the devaluation of Naira and rise in inflation (an after-effect of the Structural Adjustment Programme SAP), such that 70% of small and medium businesses in Nigeria failed in the first five year of being in operation. Even though the 1999 consolidation of democracy in Nigeria focused on expansion of capacities to harness entrepreneurial potentials, SMEs in Nigeria either remain small, moribund or shut down within few years of operation due to certain constraints inhibiting their growth (Evbuomwan *et al.*, 2014).

Different opinions abound as to why SMEs are not able to breakeven and remain competitive. Some argue that it is poor infrastructures and lack of access to credit facilities while others contend otherwise arguing that poor management, inability to access global market, lack of entrepreneurial skills and other leadership inadequacies are largely responsible for the low survival rate of SMEs. Suffice to argue that the fundamentals of the entire argument on SMEs sustainability boils down to leadership factor (Evbuomwan *et al.*, 2014).

Leadership is described as a universal phenomenon which breathes life into every human activity or endeavour (Habeeb and Ibrahim, 2017). Mews (2019) defines leadership as that manner of directional influence, which a person exerts on a group of people under him/her, in such a manner that it stimulates the behaviour of such individuals, or groups towards the attainment of a common goal, which for every business is sustainability and growth.

Leadership is a very vital part of any form of business with its success and level of performance depending on the effectiveness of leadership. Vincent (2019) found that internal human resource capabilities of SMEs are characteristically different from what is obtainable in large firms, and a critical element of organizational human resource capability is leadership, with evidence indicating that the strategic behaviour of SME owner-managers is a defining characteristic of the leadership process within the SME firms. Reuben (2019) explained that because SMEs are mostly owner-managed by one person, where the chief executive is typically the creator, proprietor, managing director and day-to-day manager of the enterprise, who in addition to leadership duties assumes virtually all the liability risk; any little mistake by the owner/manager has a great tendency of crashing the enterprise.

Therefore, the performance of an SME is essentially related to the leadership of the enterprise which is the all-important, driving force. Mitra and Hamed (2017) corroborates that the SME subsector is a very open/translucent market prone to very competitive entrepreneurs who realize that the economic environment is a survival of the fittest situation. Hence, Leadership is needed to move the business forward among a changing, competitive landscape by imagining, innovating, motivating, organizing, managing and leading employees to a higher level of performance.

Also, Reuben (2019) avows that SMEs susceptibility to low survival necessitates that, more than all businesses, SMEs need a strong leadership backing, without which they often grow much more slowly and often lose direction and as a result, fall behind competitors and most

likely go into premature extinction. Drucker, (1985) cited in Etuk *et al.*, (2014) posits that entrepreneur-leadership is centred on creating a new thing with added value, involving a great deal of innovation and skills. This assertion invariably implies that not all established SMEs can be said to be entrepreneurial because for an SME or a business to be entrepreneurial, the enterprise operator should possess required entrepreneurial skills of innovativeness, creativity, clarity of thought, rational decision-making communication, competence, ambition, aptitude and dexterity.

The emphasis is therefore on the nexus between leadership and sustainable SMEs based on their ability to breakeven, stay afloat and beat competition. Sustainable SMEs herein refers to a state of continuous competitive existence of an enterprise, centred on creation of meaningful value for both society and the individuals. Ion and Criveanu (2016) avow that the meaningfulness of the value created for sustainability is manifested via the level of such variables as: effectiveness, efficiency, quality, timeliness and finance, as well as workplace environment. Accordingly, effectiveness deals with the extent to which the enterprise is achieving desired results at any point in its operations.

Efficiency reflects productivity which is described as how successfully enterprise inputs have been converted into outputs; quality is concerned with creating standard goods/services of public requirements and of customer satisfaction; timeliness refers to aptness in production and delivering of goods/services; finance bothers on the profitability of outcomes and the stewardship/prudence in the management of funds; Workplace environment is about the organizational climate and organizational culture in terms of the state of infrastructure, employees remuneration, work hours, rest period, safety, health, security, values, beliefs, orientation, training and development (Ion and Criveanu, 2016).

Sustainable SMEs therefore entails a process whereby an individual influence a group of individuals to achieve desired enterprise performance level; and to enhance enterprise

performance, leadership plays a crucial role to make the best possible products and services through the best utilization of available resources (Eniola and Ektebang, 2014). SME leaders have to prudently take responsibility for company finances; make good calculated decisions that allow the business to operate profitably and compete successfully; inspire the workforce by encouraging them to feel valued and motivated to work hard and believe in the company (Bakshi, 2018).

Within each of these sustainability variables, SME leadership further engenders the responsibilities of clarity of thought and decision-making consistent with the company vision. There also need to be continuous communication across the business and on-going engagement amongst all teams. Moreover, the enterprise operations has to be more inclusive by engaging professional support and involving the resourcefulness of the leader to stimulate the entire organisation in helping to overcome any challenges; and in turn reward them, provide favourable workplace environment, as well as investing in the workforce through training and development opportunities to uphold them as a valuable productive resource. It is therefore argued that the extent to which these variables are manifest facilitates the healthy growth and competitiveness of the enterprise.

1.2 RESEARCH AIM

This research aims to examine how women leadership impact on SMEs and to suggest an adoptable leadership model for SME sustainability in Nigeria.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Arising from the problem statement, the following research questions were addressed by the study;

- i. What factors contributes towards women leadership in Nigeria SMEs?

- ii. Is there any significant relationship between women leadership and sustainable SMEs in Nigeria?
- iii. Which leadership model is adoptable for women leadership that can drive a sustainable SMEs in Nigeria?

1.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objectives developed to achieve the aim of the research are as follows:

- i. To review leadership models for sustainable SMEs in Nigeria
- ii. To examine factors that contributes towards women leadership in Nigeria SMEs
- iii. Investigate the contributions of women leadership towards sustainable SMEs in Nigeria
- iv. To evaluate the relationship between women leadership and sustainable SMEs in Nigeria
- v. To propose an adoptable leadership model for women leadership that can drive a sustainable SME in Nigeria.

1.5 RESEARCH SCOPE

SMEs are very heterogeneous group of businesses ranging from single unincorporated entrepreneurs to medium-sized listed companies, mostly owner-managed in a personalized way with little or no adequate professional support (Aremu and Adeyemi, 2011). Categorically in Nigeria, SMEs are enterprises with a labour force between 11 and 300, fixed capital/asset of N5million to N500 million (\$26,932 and \$2,693,240) and turnover of below 100 million (\$538,648) per annum (Montilewe *et al.*, 2015). There is an estimated 41.5 million small and medium-sized businesses spread across the 36 states. Effectively, the scope of this study was constricted to SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. This choice was made because

Lagos State is the commercial capital of Nigeria and is mainly where most businesses in the country spring-up from. (Eniola and Ektebang, 2014). Also, Lagos is the most multicultural city in Nigeria whereby majority of the cultures in Nigeria is well represented (Onipede, 2023). As the largest city in Nigeria, Lagos attracts people from various ethnicities, cultures and backgrounds. It serves as a melting pot where different cultures intersect and coexist. Furthermore, Lagos is a home to a significant expatriate community with people from countries around the world including those residing in the city. The multiculturalism is evident in various aspects of life in Lagos and the city's vibrant atmosphere and diverse population make it suitable for data collection for this study (Onipede, 2023).

Constricting the scope of the study to SMEs in Lagos State Nigeria, gave the study a measurable and realistic range in investigating the significance of leadership styles to organisational effectiveness in the Nigerian public sector, vis-à-vis its effect on employee productivity. Though the challenges undermining sustainable SME sector in Nigeria is inexhaustible, the study however examined those loopholes as it bothers on gender and entrepreneur leadership and its impact on the performance of SMEs; while recommending plausible combination of leadership models that will ensure the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria.

1.6 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Nigeria is a very good example of a resource rich country that continues to struggle economically even with enormous resource wealth. Endowed with massive productive and arable land, wide range of mineral resources, with a population of 200, 963.599 million and an estimated 41.5 million SMEs spread across the 36 states (National Bureau of Statistics, 2019); the country has struggled to sufficiently develop competitive resources sector that can promote production and other types of industrialization (Adesoji, 2019). The performance

and growth of SMEs in different sectors has been believed to be the engine drive that can influence the economy of the country.

However, the absence of solid and vibrant SME sector has been the major setback in the country's pursuit of industrial development for decades now (Smart and Caspersen, 2018). According to Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Enterprises (NASME) in line with the 2019 National Bureau of Statistics report on SMEs and Nigeria's re-industrialization goals, 71.2% of new businesses established in Nigeria have crashed within the first three years of their start-up.

The crux of the varied challenges inhibiting sustainable SMEs in Nigeria is said to be a leadership problem, and it appears the issue takes a toll on the role of women leadership among SMEs in Nigeria (i.e. gender and entrepreneur leadership). Generally, leadership and management remain highly gendered in Nigeria as gender discrimination, weaker sex stigmatization, lack of career advancement and training opportunities have been and remains a recurring decimal in Nigeria enterprises (Edintoyinbo, 2020). Data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) indicate that as of 2017, women constituted 50 percent of Nigeria population, but just about 21 percent of the registered entrepreneurial businesses in Nigeria are run by women.

It appears that despite their entrepreneurial/leadership skills and significant contribution to the nation's economy, recognition of the leadership potentials of Nigerian women remains untapped and unacknowledged in the SME sector (Adesoji, 2019). In addition to operating in an unfavourable business environment, characterized by various challenges ranging from infrastructural deficiencies, low access and high cost of finance, weak institutions, bribery and corruption; it seems women entrepreneurs are not afforded the same opportunities as their male counterparts, due in part to deep rooted discriminatory socio-cultural norm which perceive them as wives and mothers.

The 2019 Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) research depicts that growth expectations and aspirations of early-stage entrepreneurship represent key dimension of sustainable SMEs. The survey indicates that Nigerian women are very creative and innovative and that they are more eager to establish new businesses as well as show high success rate in their endeavours. This may be because they have more clarity of thought, communicate better, are more focused, resilient, responsive and resourceful.

Thus, it is argued that Nigeria women's leadership potentials provides the antidote for the underperforming SME sector when provided insights into the tools, techniques and frameworks for functional areas of small and medium business enterprises. Due to the lack of women leadership, this study examined the role of women leadership among SMEs in Nigeria, with the view towards developing a model for sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

1.7 RESEARCH RATIONALE/GAP

According to Olowookere et al., (2021), it has been established that the importance of small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in socio-economic transformation cannot be overstated (CBN, 2005). They have been acknowledged as crucial drivers of economic growth, agents of industrial development, and promoters of poverty eradication in various economies (Olowookere et al., 2021). However, of all the effort and support of institutions and governments, SMEs have not made the anticipated impact on the economy of Nigeria. The poor performance and high mortality rate of this subsector in Nigeria has become a recurring decimal and a serious cause for concern (Kalu, 2022). The matter has long been under intense academic scrutiny in Management and Social Sciences palace; hence in recent studies, the factors inhibiting SMEs performance have rapidly become issues of contestation. This highlights the perception that there is a vital issue that challenges SMEs which have not yet been addressed or tackled wholesomely (Kalu, 2022)

Quite a lot of studies have argued on SMEs environmental problems and funding issues, while few researches mentioned the management issues confronting SMEs (Fjose *et al.*, 2010; Mwangi and Sejjiaaka, 2016; Bakshi, 2018; Olowookere et al., 2021). However, one of the major weaknesses of extant studies is that none of them have been able to properly scrutinize and address in concrete terms the leadership factor in the mix of SMEs growth and sustainability. Series of study has been carried out on leadership styles with consideration to larger business; but not a lot has been evaluated on leadership with consideration to SMEs, that is, entrepreneurial leadership style. Even when the concept of leadership is addressed, the masculine gender comes into mind, with little or no attention accorded the leadership potential of the female gender in entrepreneurship. Hence, the aspect of female leadership and how they differ or unique to male leadership, is quite new to the literature.

This is identified as a gap in knowledge that needs to be addressed to determine an adoptable leadership model for sustainable SMEs in Nigeria. Therefore, to carve a niche for itself and close the identified empirical lacuna, this study not only evaluates the challenges confronting SMEs in Nigeria with reference to leadership style, but also examines the effectiveness of women's leadership role on the survival and competitive growth of SMEs in Nigeria. The researcher, being a female, who would like to start up her business soon decided to evaluate how being a female entrepreneur can further increase the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria.

Theoretically, the study could potentially serve as an embodiment of knowledge to students, scholars, economic analysts, entrepreneurs and the general public, as it will further extend the frontiers of knowledge by contributing to the plethora of extant literature related to the subject matter; thereby creating a fresh platform for further studies to emerge. Empirically, the findings and recommendations of this study will be useful for the researcher and will be of immense relevance to Nigerian economic policy formulators, development economists, and the entirety of private and public organizations across all the tiers; as it will further serve as a

nugget of solution for ameliorating constraints undermining the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. Existing SME owners/operators and prospective entrepreneurs will find this study invaluable as it will further expose them to the practical processes, tools, techniques and frameworks for a fully functional and profitable enterprise.

1.8 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY DESCRIPTION

The methodology section presented the path through which the researcher conducted the research. A problem statement was generated in concomitance with research questions formulated to address the research problem; which aligned with the aim of the research and in order to achieve the aim of the research, research objectives were formulated. A pragmatic approach was considered more suited to this work and chosen as the philosophical stance applied. Pragmatism is a deconstructive paradigm that advocates the use of mixed methods in research as it sidesteps the contentious issues of truth and reality and focuses instead on ‘what works’ as the truth regarding the research questions under investigation (Morgan, 2014).

Therefore, pragmatism offers a middle philosophically position where research questions are answered in a more practical and action-oriented manner (Cameron, 2011). The importance of the pragmatic approach to this research emanates from the use of research questions and the need to obtain actionable result applicable to women-led leadership sustainability model for SMEs in Nigeria. The deductive reasoning approach is also best suited to the study and was preferred to the inductive method, since deductive reasoning aids the discovery of the nexus between research variables objectively (Worster, 2014). Moreover, it was aimed at identifying a causal connection between leadership value and SMEs effectiveness, efficiency (productivity), quality, timeliness, finance (profitability) and workplace environment (training and development) to objectively proffer an adoptable model that will ensure the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. The deductive approach therefore gives room for the

achievement of the right result by utilising critical evidence from analysed data (Heit and Rotello, 2010).

On the field, this study adopted a test-re-test reliability technique based on a 'Pilot survey'. The research instrument was administered on a pilot sample drawn from the population, on two different time periods. A pilot study was used to assess the research instrument (questionnaire) in accordance with the discussion of Leon *et al.*, (2011), to ascertain if the instrument will obtain the right answers for the research, or to show in advance aspects of the research instrument that could fail. The rationale was to determine the consistency of the instrument in measuring results in different situations. The pilot study was successful and provided a pathway for the main study with minor changes to the questionnaire to facilitate the achievement of the research objectives.

The research design adopted is the mixed method as suggested by Teddlie and Tashakkori (2012) to be used for research with variables that require a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches to analyse. This investigation work will legitimise the decision to utilise the quantitative strategy using its methodologies viz: exploratory and causal relative techniques. The exploratory approach aims to develop a model that will extend a nugget of solution for ameliorating constraints undermining the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria, while the causal approach will look at the character of women leadership and its impact on sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

The primary data were collected through questionnaire, focus group discussion and contents as recommended by McKim (2017) through a purposive sampling method. The quantifiable data from this study were examined using exploratory and causal relationship statistics with the aid of the SPSS (statistical package for social science); while the qualitative data from the interview were examined through content analysis (McKim, 2017).

1.9 RESEARCH OUTLINE

Chapter One introduces the research and the background of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises while capturing its meaning and importance to both the individual and to the economy at large. It highlights the challenges inhibiting SMEs sustainable growth vis-à-vis the perceived leadership gap, with particular emphasis on gender and entrepreneurship leadership in Nigeria. The purpose, aim, and objectives of the research work were highlighted while outlining specific questions that were to be answered by the research. The implication of the study and contribution to existing knowledge were also highlighted as the chapter was concluded, with a brief description of the research methodology summarised while the terms used were also defined for contextual understanding.

Chapter two reviews key concepts and gave an overview of issues bothering on sustainable SMEs in Nigeria while exploring the nexus between SMEs efficiency, effectiveness, quality, timeliness, profitability and prudence in management of finance, organizational climate/organizational culture and the women leadership variables of clarity of thought, professionalism, resilience, commitment, communication, responsiveness and resourcefulness for sustainable SMEs. Certainly, a review of this magnitude cannot be said to be exhaustive. Nonetheless, the study carried out a considerable review of available literature on the subject matter and/or variables under study. It has to be emphasized that the review was guided by the research problem, research questions and objectives of the study made in the preliminary part of the work.

A brief analogy of the SMEs in Nigeria and the strategies for sustainable SMEs were underscored. An analogy of how the sector evolved and notable internal and external factors impeding the performance and sustainability of the sector were among the critical discussions of the chapter. The review and criticism of existing literature covered the concept of

leadership and the models associated with it, its significance to SMEs performance, the relationship between the variables, and its impact on SMEs sustainability. The summary of literatures inspired the development of the conceptual framework that will be shown and discussed in the next chapter.

Chapter three reveals the methodology employed in solving the research problem. The methods adopted in conducting the research and the justifications were also explained in detail. The chapter also explained the population of the study and the sample while justifying the criteria for the selection.

Chapter four is used to present in a logical manner, the data gathered from the survey which were analysed for better appropriation. SPSS was used to present descriptive statistics of the data, providing demographic variables of respondents in frequency distribution tables with their corresponding percentages which provided room for comparison and further analysis. Regression analysis and correlations were computed from the SPSS table to define the degree of relationship between the variables being discussed. A statistical reliability test using the Cronbach Alpha analysis was also conducted to test the consistency of the research instrument. A NVIVO software was also applied to the transcribed key informant interview sessions for easy data presentation and analysis.

In chapter five, analysis of data is performed from the results highlighted in the presentation section, while the reviewed leadership models were also used as a guide for conclusions.

Chapter six presents a summary drawn from the whole discussion and findings and this also formed the bases upon which conclusions were made. Conclusions are checked to ensure the research has effectively answered the research questions stated in the preliminary part of the work. Appropriate recommendations were also drawn from the results obtained which will help the Nigerian SMEs leadership approach and the growth of the economy at large.

The contribution of this inquiry to knowledge is drawn from the empirical lacuna filled through the answers provided to the research questions to solve the research problem. Meanwhile, the researcher was able to identify areas of improvement to the result obtained.

1.10 CONCLUSION

This first chapter was structured into relevant themes and sub themes capturing the background of the study, the research problem, research aim, research questions and objectives. Likewise, the rationale for carrying out the study was justified with a brief description of the research methodology as well as an outline of the research. The scope and limitations of the study were also explained for objectivity.

In the first instance, the study captured an abridged introduction of the nature and essence of SMEs while catching its global meaning and definition within the Nigerian context with a brief idea of the historical trajectory of SMEs in Nigeria. Meanwhile, the research background also captured the meaning given to such key variables as: SMEs sustainability, Leadership and entrepreneur leadership. Likewise, the background succinctly addressed the challenges inhibiting SMEs sustainability in Nigeria while highlighting the gender and entrepreneur leadership problem.

The problem of the study was concisely given that “despite their entrepreneurial skills, leadership potentials and significant contribution to the nation’s economy, recognition of women entrepreneur leadership in Nigerian still remains unacknowledged in the SME sector”. It must emphasized that this chapter also delved into explication of various forms of sustainable leadership variables to align theoretical leadership models with the practical impact of women leadership on the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The concern of leadership in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) cannot be passed over (Baroni, 2018). This is because all businesses need a strong leadership backing, particularly for small and medium businesses whose start-up and sustainability is a risk, with a slimmer chance of success compared to failure (Baroni, 2018). Leadership influences the daily operations of SMEs as well as their competitiveness and subsequent longevity (Lincoln, 2016). SMEs require hands-on leadership management, with leaders who are involved in the day-to-day activities, but are also able to manage the enterprise dynamically by establishing the long-term enterprise vision and the required directional strategy to desired achievements (Agwu & Emeti, 2014).

Therefore, it is crucial for SME leaders to be able to inspire, motivate and provide a clear direction to a sustainable business enterprise. Without effective leadership, an SME either remain small, moribund or go into premature extinction. Consequently, leadership has been an aspect of critical interest in management and social sciences studies for decades now. However, Leadership in SMEs has remained an under-researched area in the management literature, most significantly in Nigeria, a country whose continues struggle to grab any form of meaningful socio-economic development has remained a mere rhetoric (Lincoln, 2016).

In Africa, the under voiced debate in management science discipline has been the contestation of gender and entrepreneur leadership; specifically in Nigeria SMEs where leadership and management remain highly gendered as gender discrimination, weaker sex

stigmatization, lack of career advancement and training opportunities have been and still remains a recurring decimal (Afuegbu, 2019). The effort of women in sustaining the socio-economic well-being of their families has been tacit, unvoiced and even made latent by the society, ending in the trivialism of woman socio-economic contribution to the economy and underutilization of their incredible leadership potentials in socio-economic activities in the Nigeria SME environment (Taiwo *et al.*, 2016). The argument is therefore that the SME leadership gap implicitly and explicitly takes a toll on the role of women leadership on sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

It is not unknown that different leadership models such as: the authentic leadership model, charismatic leadership model, situational leadership model, full-range leadership, and many more were developed to provide insights into archetypal implements, techniques and frameworks for functional organisations and businesses operating within complex globalization dynamics (Ali and Salisu, 2019). In evaluating these models towards proffering an ideal leadership representation, this study argues that the antidote for the underperforming SME sector in Nigeria lies in women leadership prowess and/or potentials (Ali and Salisu, 2019).

Thus, this chapter sets out to comprehensively review existing studies on the subject matter under interrogation. The review is thematically divided and focused on the research relevant concepts and/or ideas, normative contribution and submissions of Scholars on: the Concept of Leadership and Leadership Models, the Concept of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and its Environment in Nigeria, Leadership in SMEs, SMEs versus Entrepreneurship, the Concept of Sustainability and key variables of Sustainable SMEs, Gender and Entrepreneur Leadership in Nigeria, Factors that contributes towards Women Leadership in Nigeria SMEs, Challenges facing Women Leadership in Nigeria SMEs, Constraints to Sustainable SMEs in Nigeria and Leadership Model for Sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

2.2 THE GENERAL CONCEPT OF LEADERSHIP

Leadership is as old as the origin of man and the existence of nature itself and even though the first acknowledged use of the term 'leadership' is traced to the 19th century in 1821 when the suffix 'ship' was added to the word 'leader' to describe the position of the leader, the concept of leadership as used in the contemporary epoch, made its way into the general literature across the last century (Klingborg, Moore and Hammond, 2014). Onward, the choice of a definition of the leadership concept became of critical importance to leadership development in classical societies. However, the model-based conceptualization of leadership has been a recent academic activity which evolved overtime to become one of the most debated concepts across all fields, with many different definitions as there are many persons who have attempted to define the concept (Fairholm, 2015).

Edward (2018) avers that because of the conceptual ambiguity of leadership, the concept may never be defined in a way that all researchers agree on. Hence, the concept of leadership depicts so many meanings such as: influence, direction, guidance, transformation, facilitation, orchestration, servitude, to mention but a few; and each of these different meanings has developed into distinctive behavioural types/models of leadership viz: participatory, directive, transformative, transactional, facilitative, authentic, stewardship, servant leader and many more (Richard, 2020). Klingborg, *et al.*, (2014) however notes that regardless of the different meanings, leadership can be defined by a series of abilities and behaviours, and whilst they cannot exactly be taught, they can be learnt, or rather, discovered, fostered and allowed to grow in certain circumstances.

Accordingly, Chester, I. Bernard (Davies, 2020) defined leadership as the quality of behaviour of the individuals whereby they guide people or their activities in organised efforts; and in a similar vein, Sterling, J. Livingston succinctly defined leadership as the

ability to awaken the desire to follow a common objective (Davies, 2020). Suffice to say that leadership is a behavioural phenomenon made manifest by abilities of the person leading as well as those following. Hence, leadership is the human behavioural factor whose ability binds a group together and tilts their combined efforts towards improved performance directed towards the attainment of goals (Ravet-Brown *et al.*, 2023).

From the foregoing, it can be argued that the concept of leadership not only depicts the idea of leadership as the ability of persuading the conduct of individuals or groups and swaying their actions, but also resonates the voluntariness and willingness of those being led, heartily aiming their attention towards actualizing stated goals. In other words, leadership in essence portrays an unceasing ability of influencing behaviour, exercised as a mutual relationship between a leader and his/her followers, such that the leader tries to influence the behaviour of the individuals or group of individuals around him to achieve common interests (Ravet-Brown *et al.*, 2023).

Thus, leadership is conceptualized as a continuous interpersonal influence, exercised in situations, directed through proper communication and channeled towards the attainment of a specific goal or set of goals (Daniel and Josse, 2017). The following goes to show that leadership is a relationship in which one person influences others to work together willingly on related tasks to attain what they mutually desire. Thus, it must extract cooperation and willingness of the individuals and groups to attain what is held as shared interest.

Moreover, interpersonal influence is triggered by effective communication between the leader and the followers. On this note, Bernard, J. Keys and Thomas, R. Miller defined leadership as the process of influencing and supporting others to work enthusiastically towards achieving stated objectives when set objectives are properly communicated.

Likewise, Keith Davis opined that leadership is the process of conversed encouragement and help towards others to work enthusiastically in achieving their objectives (Fairholm, 2015).

Daniel Katz and Robert, L. Kahn conceptualized leadership as an influential increment over and above mechanical compliance with the routine directives of collective efforts towards realizing set organisational goals (Davies, 2020). The implication is therefore that leadership is persuasive over time, rather than a coercive or programmed submission. It was on the bases of the 'influence-relationship' premise that W.C.H. Prentice in his 1961 article, argued against the notion of leadership as the exercise of power and force or the possession of extraordinary attributes over and beyond the ordinary.

Prentice defined leadership as "the accomplishment of a goal through the direction of human assistants". Hence those been led, willingly comply to conduct themselves in a certain way or carry out certain task for a certain purpose; and a successful leader is one who can understand people's motivations and enlist employee participation in a way that integrates individual needs and interests to the group's purpose (Edward, 2018). The concept of leadership therefore reflects the ability of an individual to bring to bear the collaborative tendencies of those being led. On this premise, Fairholm (2015) defined leadership as the process of influencing others to understand and agree about what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to accomplish what has been shared and understood.

Thus, this individual who successfully marshals his human collaborators to achieve particular ends is a leader; and is termed worthy or effective leader when he/she can exert the collaborative-influence day after day, and year after year, in a wide variety of circumstances (Richard, 2020). As clearly emphasized by Daniel and Josse (2015), leadership is centred on rousing the zeal and confidence of individuals or group members to pursue set targets based

on predesigned parameters, to the extent that it becomes a shared goal and vision, with all efforts directed towards the purpose of achieving success.

This implies that leadership is not just an impromptu task because leading others towards accomplishment of shared vision and set goals necessitates the exercise of proper guidance, facilitation, direction, comportment, adaptation, interaction and understanding; while putting into consideration the feelings, keen interest, desires, values and ways of life of others. Perhaps the foregoing assertion was the reason why Chester, I. Bernard emphasized on the quality of behaviour, both of the leader that guides the individuals being led and the quality of the behaviour of the followers and their activities in organised efforts (Davies, 2020).

Adding more substance to the foregoing, Richard (2020) avows that the quality of the character and behaviour of a man influences the works of others. Hence, the art of leadership depicts those people who know how to achieve goals and are undaunted in inspiring others along the way. This is why leadership is not evaluated merely by an individual's own leadership ability, but by the quality of leadership in terms of values, servitude, resourcefulness and dexterity they bring out in others, which invariably substantiates the necessity for continuous leadership development. Klingborg *et al.*, (2014) corroborates that to inspire others into higher levels of teamwork and goal attainment, the ability and quality are acquired through continuous improvement. So good leaders are continually functioning and learning to improve their leadership abilities, without resting on their achievements.

Shedding more light on the concept, Hammond (2019) defined leadership as a shared function whereby the leader shares his knowledge, experience, ideas and views with his followers and work hand-in-hand with them to achieve the objectives of the organisation. Leadership therefore ignites a reciprocal relationship between the one leading and those following; with the reciprocity regarded as the nexus or the connecting point of leadership effectiveness and/or success. Hammond further explains that a leader can influence his followers and, in

turn, the followers can influence the leader. Thus the willingness of both the leader and the followers is responsible for the influence and the end result.

W. C. H. Prentice drew more emphasis on the importance of reciprocity and shared values in leadership as he argued that there must be community of interests between the leader and his followers. The point of Prentices' argument is that leadership cannot thrive with disjointed interests where a leader has his own objectives and the followers have theirs; thereby moving in different directions in the absence of community of interests. Leadership therefore entails the reconciliation of different objectives (or compromise of the individual interests) for overall organisational objectives. To this end, leadership entails regulating all the elements of responsibility to be congruent with the guidelines of the organisation and the interest of the followers as well. This invariably requires the development of organisational vision and mission, as well as outlining organisational goals clearly.

Accordingly, leadership is defined as a 'cooperative followership' and according to Aibieyi (2014) leadership is meaningless devoid of followers, who are those being influenced; because without followers or subordinates, the leadership ability of the individual leading will be irrelevant. He further explicates that it is those being led that gives meaning to leadership, since the core task of a leader as an influencer, is to influence the conduct of the followers. As a result, the manner and extent the followers or subordinates are influenced creates the compulsion to put in more efforts than they would have given towards any given course.

2.3 MODELS OF LEADERSHIP

Leadership is a combination of strategy and character in an influence-behavioural relationship between a leader and the followers. A leader is someone who takes the central roles in interaction and who influences the behaviour of other members of a group (Dolly and

Okpakwasili, 2018). Thus, it is widely held that leadership models help us to understand why leaders act or behave the way they do and give us a framework and a process that aids us in evaluating their leadership in congruence with goals, organization and staff (Simpson, 2012; Laguerre, 2010). In other words, leadership model can be referred to as a choice of measures to influence followers or workers and stimulate performance-oriented actions (Dyczkowska and Dyczkowski, 2018).

Scholarly attention on leadership has existed throughout history; however El-sheriff (2013) avows that the topic of leadership models as a subject of scientific study did not begin until the 1930's and 1940's. Laguerre (2010) clearly notes that the comprehension and indulgent of leadership behaviour since the 1950's was shaped by the pioneering research programs at Ohio State University and the University of Michigan; the time at which leadership theoreticians were seeking for effective leadership behaviour, and measured how often leaders exerted the behaviours. Initially, scholarly postulations centred on behaviours focused on task accomplishment and as succinctly put by Imhonopi and Ugochukwu (2018), leadership understanding at that time was static in its form and style.

At those early ages, leadership was regarded as an elitist activity associated with power behaviour and related to hierarchy. Thus, the leadership models/practices were essentially a top-down, authoritarian and individualistic process; such that leadership was seen as an inbred and hereditary potential possessed by a privileged minority. Overtime, classical (mechanical-tasks oriented) models began to give way to (more humane-social relationship) new leadership development models and intervention methods in an age of uncertainty, complexity, globalization, and accelerating change (Imhonopi and Ugochukwu, 2018).

Consequently, the task accomplishment focused behaviours became less preferred and less sought after, compared to those focused on developing relationships with followers. Quinton (2019) asserts that these new intervention models require organizations to have effective

leadership strategy to groom organizational leaders with the right character and provide them with the right trappings to handle uncertainty, complexity, globalization and change. Thus, from the 1960's and 1970's leadership theorists began to focus on how leaders make decisions, particularly on influences such as inclusiveness, participation of and delegation to followers (Avolio *et al.*, 2012).

The influence relationship and cooperative followership between the leader and the follower were therefore explored, (Avolio *et al.*, 2012), including the level of adaptation or whether the leader changed their behaviour for different followers. Thus, the emphasis was on character and strategy of a more humane and social behaviour which stems from the leaders understanding of his fellow workers and the relationship of their individual goals to the group goal that must be accomplished. In conspectus, two broad categories of leadership behaviour existed from the earliest epoch to the contemporary times, which are: behaviour models focused on task accomplishment and those focused on developing relationships with followers. As a result, different leadership models emerged and continue to evolve just as the business world is changing rapidly with the advancement in information technology (Adanri and Thakkar, 2016).

2.3.1 Authentic Leadership Model

Historically, the concept of authenticity stretches back to the mid-1950s when humanistic psychologists classically conceptualized authenticity as an echo of analogy between a person's self-concept and realization of self-actualization (Peters, 2019). However, some scholars have traced the origin of authenticity to the ancient Greek philosopher Socrates, who taught on the importance of knowing oneself and staying true to that self (Abraham and Duraisamy, 2016). Overtime, modern conceptualizations of authenticity evolved and were influenced by the self-determination theory which emphasizes that authenticity is related to

high levels of self-determination; thereby forming the basis of contemporary authentic leadership model.

The model psychologically construes authenticity as the observable behaviour or action of one's true self in one's everyday enterprise. In other words, authenticity depicts the quality of being real or true, which requires self-awareness and the ability to act in accordance with one's true self. However, it is important to note that being authentic is not a condition; rather it implies that people are more or less authentic or inauthentic at all; one or the other. Consequently, authenticity is deemed as encompassing two main components with the first depicting a leader's ability to act on the right societal values and influencing followers, and the second depicting the followers ability to act according to the leader, following the leaders traits. The implication is therefore that an authentic leader can influence their followers towards acting or behaving in the right way (Nkwabi, 2019).

Johnson (2019) argues that in contemporary knowledge, authentic leadership model is a complex ideal that applies authentic and humanistic principles to leadership approach with the belief that being true to one's own self will yield more positive results. Peters (2019) affirms that achieving organisational goals is a shared result which the authentic leader buttresses by being a selfless leader who motivates their followers by being aware of their actions and inactions. In fact, achieving set goals is not something authentic leaders boast about as an individual, because he/she is self-aware and have the ability to recognise and acknowledge his own strengths and weaknesses. Peters (2019) further notes that authentic leaders are usually not afraid to show their vulnerability and feelings, since they listen to their own intuition and voice out their opinions based on their personal observations.

Explaining the quintessence of the application of authentic leadership model for leadership effectiveness, Makhmor (2018) avows that authentic leadership model is a prerequisite for

organizations building for the future, because authentic leaders' focus is typically on the long term, helping to steer the organisation in the right direction. Such leaders place organizational interest foremost above all other things. Additionally, authentic leaders are strict and are no pushovers as they take their responsibilities seriously and expect team members and subordinates to do the same. But they also empathize with followers/employees by trying to relate with their shortcomings and creating an interpersonal connection with them (Abraham and Duraisamy, 2016).

Therefore, in addition to the requirements of being self-aware and knowing one's strengths and weaknesses, authentic leadership model presupposes a transparent leadership approach whereby the leader encourages open communication and is willing to discuss successes as well as failures. Nkwabi (2017) further explains that consistency, integrity, trust, transparency, openness and leadership development are the watchwords for authentic leadership model; where the leader is a constant factor within the organisation, and people around him/her trust and know what they can expect from their authentic leader. Vincent (2019) sums up that Authentic leadership model is a pattern of leadership behaviour that focuses on encouraging self-awareness, with clarity around one's moral perspectives, balanced and fair decision making, and high levels of transparency mutually portrayed by both the leaders and their followers

Nonetheless, authentic leadership model is criticized based on the impossibility of the "true self" taking into cognizance the fact that those leaders and followers are human beings with complex behavioural pattern. Thus, the argument is that in leadership, authenticity is misleading; because it is extremely difficult, if not impossible for a person to be authentic when some leaders/followers are good at hiding their true character, making it tough for others to know whether they are acting or being truthful. Antagonists further criticized the irony in the definition of authenticity which emphasis "being genuine or one's true self".

Critics therefore point out that if followers are meant to imitate/act like their leader and succeed such traits that their leader possesses, then those followers are already inauthentic, because they ought to be portraying their own values and acting their true self (Ford and Harding, 2014; Nkwabi, 2019).

2.3.2 Situational Leadership Model

The situational leadership model was derived from the contingency-situational leadership theories, which emerged as a reaction to the trait-based leadership. The model is based on the principle that behaviour is determined and influenced by the situation one finds him or herself (Simpson, 2012). Ghazzawi, Shougari and Osta (2017) explain that with the emergence of the trait-based leadership, social scientists such as Karl Marx, Hebert Spencer and other scholars, pioneered the notion that a leader is made by the result of time intervention. Suffice to say that time/occurrence is the fundamental factor towards being a leader. These scholars particularly Paul Hersey and Ben Blanchard argued that there is no ideal sketch for a leader and no leader has the same characteristics as others, rather each act or lead in a certain way at a certain time or occurrence.

Paul Hersey and Ben Blanchard proposed a situational-taxonomy consisting of four leadership tactic (ranging from directing to coaching, to supporting and to delegating) and a framework for matching each style to specific situations. With concise emphasis, Thompson and Glasso (2010) explained that situational leadership model is based on the amount of direction (task behaviour) and the amount of support (relationship behaviour) a leader certainly has to exert given the situation and the level of keenness of the follower or group. On this note, task behaviour refers to the one-way communication ability of a leader in engaging the followers; that is, the extent to which the leader explains what each follower is to do as well as when, where and how tasks are to be accomplished. While relationship

behaviour depicts the extent to which a leader engages in two-way communication by providing socio-emotional support.

Appropriately, the leader must be able to determine which leadership style to enforce for each given situation (Ryan, 2018). The implication is that these tactics are varied in accordance with what is at stake (time and task occurrence), such that a leader that is concerned about the capabilities of his/her followers in the accomplishment of an important task or specific responsibility will often direct (i.e. the directional or indicating leadership style). But where the confidence level is unconvincing, the leader coaches and eventually progresses towards playing the supportive leadership role so as to ensure the task is accomplished according to the expected standard and desired outcome. At the peak of the confidence level, that is a leader that has confidence in their followers or subordinates, such leader applies the delegating leadership tactic to accomplish organizational tasks (Thomppson and Gaso, 2010).

Situational leadership model is therefore the stance that different situations should be handled in different manner since each situation has its own unique distinctiveness or characteristics. The crux of the situational leadership model is that there is no one best way or most effective way or pattern of leadership, rather that there are different leadership patterns and/or approach which are appropriate for different tasks and different individuals (Ghazzawi *et al.*, 2017). The efficacious ones are those who are able to tune their approach to adapt accordingly with the strengths and weaknesses of their followers or subordinates they work with. Therefore, the situational emphasis is on the followers' or subordinates level of development and the leaders' leadership acclimatization. A follower or subordinates' development level is said to be a combination of their competence and commitment; and according to Shriver (2017), situational leadership model combines both directive and supportive measures of influencing subordinates and each of these measures are to be applied correctly in a given situation.

The model demands that the leadership vary their behaviour and leadership style according to their subordinate's commitment. Thus, a situational leader has to influence their followers or subordinates by valuing their commitment and change the degree of supportiveness and directive to their employee according to exigencies and subordinates level of motivation. Shriver (2017) avers that this leadership model requires a resourceful and transformative leader who is swift to handle problems innovatively and efficiently in order to meet exigencies. It is unanimously held that the strength of situational leadership lies with the effective combination of task behaviour, worker commitment and relationship behaviour; three components of which permits openness between leaders/followers and ensures inclusive decision-making in goal attainment through an objective and competent follower or subordinate participation.

Ghazzawi *et al.*, (2017) affirm that situational leaders make effort to discover the unique characteristics of their followers so as to ascertain which leadership tactic to utilize to get the best results. Hence, the action that a leader will take depends on a range of situational factors and the leader must be versatile with different leadership approaches. In other words, it is vital that the leader is able to fit into different types of hats (resolutions) and complement each with the befitting attire (strategy) to match a given occasion or situation. Varying the tactics ensures that there is a wide variety of possible sound solutions to an organizational task or problem. Thus, situational leaders know when to appropriately give guidance and full task support for their subordinates, as well as when to allow the subordinates handle things themselves in order to accomplish the desired goals successfully.

2.3.3 Charismatic Leadership Model

The meaningfulness of charismatic leadership model is traced to the writings of Aristotle which laid the key foundation of charismatic leadership (Vincent, 2019). However, it was

Marx Weber that first made use of the term “charisma” to describe specific gifts of the body and spirit not accessible to everybody. Weber invented the term in the social and management sciences parlance to describe a charismatic leader or manager “as one who could bring about social change”. Weber argued that with their supernatural, superhuman, and specifically exceptional powers or qualities, charismatic leaders could attain outstanding accomplishments (Scavavem, *et al.*, 2017). Charismatic leadership model therefore depicts deeper level of personality-induced influence that has the ability to stimulate subordinates or employees towards set organizational goals via the leader’s personality.

Adding more substance to the foregoing, John (2018) asserts that the personality-induced behavioural influence is more intense because it is inevitable that people will follow a leader that they personally admire and hold to a high esteem. Besides, charismatic leaders are known to possess great charm and grace that can stimulate followers or employees within an organization. The charismatic leaders have the knack to focus on the emotions and values of the individuals they are influencing and these leaders find a way to make tasks and goals meaningful to their employees. Hentrup and Menges (2017) notes that charismatic leadership model serves the leadership purpose of stirring the zeal and willing commitment of followers in an organizational setting because it links the employee’s self-concepts to the identity of the organization.

Hence, by exerting the charismatic model of leadership, leaders are able to motivate their employee’s or their followers to make personal sacrifices in order to achieve the organizational goals. According to Scavavem *et al.*, (2017) the core manifestation of the charismatic charm/influence is the emotional interaction that occurs between followers and their leader. Charismatic leaders motivate followers to pursue and realize their ideals and values, while the followers reciprocate by showing affection and admiration for the leader, in whom their sentiments and ideals are expressed. Charismatic model of leadership therefore

reveal courageous leaders who challenge the status quo, set high expectations for themselves and their followers, and show confidence in their own abilities and that of their followers that the impossible can be achieved.

2.3.4 Full Range Leadership Model

The Full Range Leadership Model is an invention of the Neo-charismatic theories, birthed to give an all-round assessment of how effective leadership postulations can be conjectured into empirical ideals, to help transform even the most failing organization or business and place it on a higher growth trajectory (Gheorghe and Florin, 2017). The full-range leadership comprises of three elements viz: transformational leadership, transactional leadership and laissez-faire leadership. These leadership models are seen to encapsulate most of the contemporary leadership behaviours; and its recognition as a managerial development strategy have shown good prospects (but not without weaknesses) for leadership effectiveness across businesses and corporate organizations (Vincent, 2019).

Thus, the full range leadership model includes the three typologies of leadership behaviour, considered one of the most extensively researched paradigms in the leadership and management areas of specialty. Gheorghe and Florin (2017) clearly notes that the model has significantly proven its soundness for prognosticating leadership outcomes both in terms of leadership effectiveness and followers' satisfaction, motivation and overall goal attainment. Accordingly, the full range leadership theory encompasses nine factors: idealized influence behaviours, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration for transformational leadership; contingent reward, active management-by-exception and passive management-by-exception for transactional leadership; and then the laissez-faire leadership.

2.3.4.1 Transformational Leadership

The concept of transformational leadership was introduced by James Burn in 1978 in his depiction of what makes or mars political leaders (Simpson, 2012). Burn described transformational leadership as a process and instrument by which leaders and followers help each other to advance to a higher level of morale and motivation (Dyczkowska and Dyckowski, 2018). Obviously, transformational leadership is a truism of a 'reciprocity' process and a social stimulus response whereby leaders and followers influence one another to meet set goals and objectives. Hammond (2016) describes it as an influence relationship that sways both ways between leaders and followers who desire changes that reflect agreed purposes. Suffice to say that transformational leadership is like a two-edged sword that simultaneously impacts on the human conducts (leaders-followers, superiors-subordinates) cooperating to accomplish a common purpose (Ravet-Brown et al., 2023).

Adding more substance to the foregoing, Simpson (2012) asserts that transformational leaders are focused on the common good, which is the greater good, rather than in their individual power base. Hence, transformational leadership is capable of inducing substantial change in both the individual followers/employees and the organization at large by realigning what is mutually expected and aspired, as well as what is perceived and valued; all of which is largely dependent on the leaders' personality, character, vision, challenges and set examples. Transformational leaders engage with followers and inspire them to focus on higher-level human needs for personal achievements and self-actualization (John, 2014). The motivation prowess of transformational leaders is said to be top-notch; Gheorghe and Florin (2017) corroborate that the leadership process transforms followers to achieve more than they could have or initially intended and often even more than they ever imagined possible.

Their astonishing motivation capabilities are founded on the premise that transformational leaders set more challenging targets and typically achieve higher performances. Thus, an

enterprise or business continuous competitive existence is enhanced as transformational leaders inspire their subordinates/workers to a stronger commitment level; such that they subdue narrow-minded personal interests to pursue broad-minded general interests. Hentrup and Menges (2017) avow that because the transformational leadership model was birthed from the neo-charismatic constructs, there is sense of belongingness, feelings of trust, respect, admiration and loyalty. Consequently, employees and subordinates with a transformational kind of leader will often feel a deep sense of enthusiastic desire to work harder than he/she would ordinarily be expected. Vincent (2019) corroborates that transformational leaders get their followers more involved in the scheme of things and inspire them to focus on higher-level human needs for job satisfaction and self-actualization.

Accordingly, the meaningfulness of transformational leadership is attributed to four major elements viz: individualized considerations, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and idealized influence. Individualized consideration is the degree to which a leader recognizes that each follower has specific needs, desires and concerns; thereby addressing these unique needs from personalized perspectives with the objective of enhancing their performance. Intellectual stimulation reflects the ability of a leader to recognize the potentials of the followers, involve them in decisions, encouraging them to be creative and more cognitive in identifying innovative solutions. Inspirational motivation deals with how the leader facilitates confidence and sense of belonging through team work; this the leader achieves by articulating a vision with a clear sense of direction to get the best from followers. Idealized influence is the ability of the leader to act as a role model by demonstrating a strong sense of conviction, values and principles; thus, the charisma of the leader and how well he/she uses it inspires mutual respect and trust (Vincent, 2019; Hentrup and Menges, 2017; Gheorghe and Florin, 2017).

2.3.4.2 Transactional Leadership

Transactional leadership model is a blueprint for employee productivity as it focuses on getting followers to accomplish assigned tasks and to achieve set goals. The model is basically an exchange relationship process between leaders and followers; depicting an employment relationship where business owners and workers each aspires to satisfy self-interests (Vincent, 2019). The transactional approach is derived from the doctrines of the social exchange theory, where the motivation of followers/employees is through materialistic or psychological exchanges; the leader notices the follower's need and aim at fulfilling the need in exchange for meeting specific objectives or performing defined duties (Mews, 2019). Hence, Followers/employees obey their leaders/employees, carry out their tasks, fulfill their responsibilities and in return they get paid as their reward (i.e. the transaction).

Simpson (2012) described the transactional leadership model as a more traditional 'give and take' relationship where the followers/employees have little or no say in their rewards which is determined by the leadership. Moreover, penalties are enforced if tasks are not appropriately carried out. There are three main elements of transactional leadership model, which are: contingent reward, active management by exception and passive management by exception. Contingent reward is the transactional reward paid to employees for meeting or surpassing set target; therefore, the prize including incentives which employees gain on the accomplishment of a target is the contingent reward. Active management by exception depicts the close monitoring of employees, such that leaders are actively involved in regulating followers, even to the extent of using active corrective measures to ensure stipulated standards are met. On the other hand, passive management by exception ensures that leaders only help followers when problem arises (Vincent, 2019; Gheorghe and Florin, 2017; Chadhry and Javed, 2012).

2.3.4.3 Laissez-Faire Leadership

Typically, Laissez-faire leadership refers to leaders who avoid making decisions and who are focused on problems that need to be corrected. According to Adebayo and Bharat (2016), laissez-faire leaders are devoid of a sense of commitment and responsibility with followers, as these leaders would rather delegate tasks/responsibilities. However, laissez-faire implies more than delegated leadership because those in the position of leadership do not carry out leadership responsibilities and practically do not engage or involve in any meaningful management or control whatsoever.

Originally, laissez-faire is a French term brought into economics and political sciences vocabulary to describe a policy of minimum governmental interference in the economic activities of both the individual and the society. Ekmekci and Tosunoglu (2016) further explain that the term was subsequently applied in leadership literature, to depict a “hands-off” approach to leadership where those who ought to be at the helm of affairs and influencing others would rather let things-ride. Laissez-faire leadership is therefore likened to absence of leadership as well as the avoidance of intervention by leaders.

Chadhry and Javed (2012) argue that this category of leaders often display an attitude of indifference toward employees and their tasks and tend to behave as if they are relinquished from their responsibilities and duties they ought to perform. More like a nonchalant leadership with “I don’t care attitude” and as succinctly defined by Blake and Mouton (1985) cited in Vincent (2019), laissez-faire leadership is an impoverished management with leaders/managers making minimal effort to get required work done and showing minimal concern for subordinates (Vincent, 2019).

2.4 THE CONCEPT OF SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

The concept of Small and Medium Enterprise (SMEs) is not susceptible to any complex or simple definition rather it varies across economies of the world and defining agencies depending on: the role of SMEs in the economy, policies and programs designed by particular agencies/institutions empowered to develop SMEs, the stage of industrial development or the level of technology within the economy of a particular country. Ibrahim and Ibrahim (2015) affirm that this is why, a small business in the developed economies of countries like Britain, Japan, Germany and United States of America, may be a medium or large-scaled business in a developing economy like Nigeria, Tanzania, India.

In other words, an enterprise regarded as a small and medium business in a particular setting, may be regarded differently elsewhere. Micha, Kassah and Andah (2017) emphasize that even within a country the definition varies; but there are common indicators employed in the various definitions across the globe, such as: number of employees, asset base, turnover, running capital, ownership structure, business size, management structure, etc.

Globally, SME is defined as any recognized business or venture with annual turnover, in America dollar terms, of between ten and one thousand times the mean per capita gross national income, at purchasing power parity of the operating country (Gibson and Van dar vaart, 2018). Other developed nations also define Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) as companies/firms which employ less than a given number of employees.

This number varies across countries and the most frequent upper limit scale designating an SME is 250 employees, as in the European Union and particularly the United Kingdom. However, some countries set the limit at 200 employees, while the United States of America considers SMEs to include firms with fewer than 500 employees (Highland, 2019). According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the

International Monetary Fund (IMF), small businesses are classified based on employees of 10 to 49 persons while medium-sized enterprises is that of 40 to 249 persons (Gibson and Van dar vaart, 2018).

Conceptualizing SMEs within the Nigerian context, The Central Bank of Nigeria in its 1995 Credit Guidelines cited in Montilewe *et al.*, (2015) refer to an SME as an enterprise with fixed capital or asset of about N5million to N500 million (\$26,932 to \$2,693,240), turnover below 100 million (\$538,648) per annum and labor force of 11 to 300. The Federal Ministry of Industries defines a medium-scale enterprise as any endeavor with operating assets below N200 million, and employing below 300 persons; while it defines a small-scale enterprise as one that has total assets below N50 million, not less than 100 employees (Agwu and Ameti, 2014).

Various definitions captured above are mainly based on quantitative indices, but using quantitative approach alone to conceptualize SMEs is limiting and has been confirmed unsatisfactory due to its susceptibility to periodic alterations of inflation and other economic fluctuations, and these indices can sometimes be deceptive (Fjose *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, to make up for the limitations of quantitative definitions, it becomes necessary to consider qualitative variables that captures the humanistic elements of the SMEs, based on pre-determined attributes of the their owners/operators with regards to Nigeria the focus country of this study.

Berisha and Pula (2015) identified two bases to conceptualize SMEs, which are “Personal principle” and “Unity of leadership and capital”. The former indicates that the enterprise owner/manager is the overall decision maker; he/she regards the enterprise as a lifetime duty and maintains direct contact with workers, customers and suppliers. Meanwhile the unity of leadership and capital principle implies that the company, manager, Proprietor usually is the

same person, who in addition to leadership duties assumes virtually all the liability risk. Elucidating the ownership structure of SMEs, Mohammed and Nzelibe, (2014) aver that SMEs are generally associated with ventures mostly 'Owner-Manager' such that the chief executive is typically the creator, proprietor, managing director and the director of the enterprise.

The chief executive is usually of acquaintance with workers; and almost singlehandedly runs the day-to-day operation of the enterprise devoid of sufficient professional support. Adding substance to the foregoing, Negrut and Mihartescu (2016) further explain that SME ownership reflects its operations, such that the owner, who is most often the manager, runs the business based on his or her inclinations and experiences. These owners are known to majorly focus on short-term needs and medium-term survival, concentrating on production and sales at the expense of long-term profitability and increased market share (Negrut and Mihartescu, 2016). In a similar vein, Agwu and Ameti (2014) referred to SMEs as enterprises often family or individually owned and managed, with decisions basically personalized.

They further argue that these SMEs are run with small capital base, but undermined by inability to attract funds for expansion. Hence they are dependent on personal sources of funding. Moreover, the owner-manager finds it difficult to separate his private funds from the company's funds, more or less culminating in lack of professionalism and underperformance of the subsector. Agwu and Ameti further argue that most SMEs operate labour-intensive technology, making it difficult to modify product line and infuse innovativeness. Hence, majority of them tie their objectives more closely to the product line than to other matters such as the use of capital.

Conceptualizing SMEs based on their features, Obaseki (2015) opined that SMEs are a very heterogeneous group of businesses ranging from single unincorporated entrepreneurs to

medium-sized listed companies on exchange usually operating in such economic sectors as: Education, Art Entertainment and Recreation, Manufacturing, Wholesale & Retail Trade, Construction, Accommodation and Food Services, Agriculture, Forestry, Fishing & Hunting, Water Supply; Sewerage, Waste Management and Remediation, Administrative and Support Services Activities, Mining and Quarrying, Other Services Activities. Some of the SMEs are dynamic, innovative, and growth-oriented while others are satisfied to remain small and perhaps family owned; while some of the SMEs usually operate in the formal sector of the economy and employ mainly wage-earning workers.

2.4.1 Small And Medium Scale Enterprises Versus Entrepreneurship

Both terms, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) and Entrepreneurship are often used interchangeably and alternatively by Scholars in the social and management sciences parlance (Fjose *et al.*, 2010). But in actuality, they differ considerably but correspondingly. Both are deemed interconnected, interdependent and set towards accomplishing same goals of socio-economic transformation of a nation. Entrepreneurship according to Etuk, Etuk and Baghebo (2014) is used to describe creativity, innovativeness, risk taking and organizational processes and functions of individuals who initiate, nurture and run a business venture. Hence it involves identifying opportunities, creating or improving a new or existing idea, technologies, products or services, as well as bearing the accompanied risk and receiving resultant rewards. In other words, entrepreneurship is about foreseeing environmental opportunities that are waiting to be tapped and taking advantage of the foreseen opportunities by fashioning something new or something old in a different way.

Arguing on the dissimilarities and interdependency between SMEs and entrepreneurship, Esuh and Adebayo (2012) submits that the term SMEs implies firms or businesses which are small and medium in sizes, born out of entrepreneurial activities of individuals or group of

individuals. Therefore while SMEs refer to firms, industries or businesses, entrepreneurship is a process leading to the creation as well as sustenance of SMEs. Derosi (2014) explain that SMEs are mostly young companies with a propensity to explore innovative ideas. Thus their innovative entrepreneurial tendency combined with their interpersonal relationship skills in dealing with customers as well as employees, enhances their flexibility to adapt with change in accordance with the market's demands, giving them a competitive advantage.

Adding more substance to dissimilarities between SMEs and Entrepreneurship, Drucker, (1985) cited in Etuk *et al.*, (2014) asserts that entrepreneurship is centred on creating a new thing with added value, which involves a great deal of innovation and skills. Implying that not all established SMEs can be said to be entrepreneurial. They further argue that for an SME or a business to be entrepreneurial, the enterprise operator must possess required entrepreneurial skills (innovativeness, creativity, competence, ambition, aptitude, dexterity, etc.) and such business must substantially inculcate unique management ideas and techniques.

To this end, the business products are relatively developed and standardized, and the operating processes/tools are constructed based on analysis of set task. Suffice to argue that though SME and Entrepreneurship differ, they are both interdependent and interrelated; with SMEs largely dependent on Entrepreneurship as a means towards enhancing performance and maintaining continuous competitive existence. Thus, the implication is that entrepreneurship in all ramifications is a vital factor in business creation, expansion, diversification, modernization and overall social change. Entrepreneurs are said to be proactive to change; they are change agents and catalyst for transforming resources into tangible products/services with greater utility and value. All over the world, and throughout history, people have created SME businesses through their entrepreneurial prowess.

Entrepreneurship immensely impact on SME performance and as Oduntan (2014) clearly notes, “The brain behind every successful Small and Medium Scale Enterprise (SME) is Entrepreneurship”. In other words, entrepreneurial proficiency should be the forte of SMEs always. Therefore, an entrepreneur may start as a small enterprise, but the business may not remain in that category for long. Eventually, it thrives and develops into large scale venture or a multinational corporation. On the other hand, SME Operators are not necessarily entrepreneurs without the necessary entrepreneurial skills, management techniques, skills and controls (Imhonopi *et al.*, 2016).

Globalization has made business survival and growth even more complex than it has ever been; thus, emerging SMEs in Nigeria are often confronted with external and internal uncertainties such as the market and economic environment dynamics, made worse by the underdeveloped infrastructures, processes and dearth in experience (Ezika, 2019). Likewise, existing SMEs has to navigate through translucent and highly competitive nature of the sector, while faced with associated risks with new investment, expansion and diversification. Rationality in all these therefore places much reliance on entrepreneurship, which encompasses the leadership capability of an owner-managed enterprise like an SME (Ningi and Mairiga, 2015).

2.4.2 Small and Medium Scale Enterprises In Africa

At the heart of Africa’s growing economy lie the contributions of SMEs (Highland, 2019). SMEs are perceived as the backbone of any country as they are interlinked with almost every facet of the society and economy. They are found in all sectors of industrial development, from mining, manufacturing, craftsmanship to agriculture and services sector where they account for two-thirds of employment levels. Okewu (2015) avers that the SME sector is the

nexus between cottage industries to complex and highly developed large scale industries, which has provided the platform for Africa's takeoff to sustainable development.

SMEs are therefore fundamental to the relative success story of the African continent, with the potential to establish a new middle class and boost the demand for local goods and services. SMEs role in driving innovation, creating employment opportunities and therefore contributing to domestic wealth creation routes is critical for sustained economic development. Fjose et al., (2010) affirm that SMEs play the pivotal role of facilitating Africa development from the grassroots through provision of inputs and services for industries and as well as furnishing direct goods and services for the masses. Thus, the SME sector invariably serves as the oil necessary for lubricating the engine of socio-economic transformation of the African continent (Aremu and Adeyemi, 2011).

The London Stock Exchange (2018) report revealed that SMEs comprise the backbone of Africa's economy, accounting for approximately 90% of all companies and providing nearly 80% of the region's employment. In Kenya, SMEs contribute 40% of the GDP, over 50% of new jobs and account for 80% of the workforce; and as clearly emphasized by Murithi (2017), SMEs generated employment for 3.2 million Kenyans in the last decade. Similarly, SMEs account for 70% of Nigerian industrial jobs and 95% of the manufacturing sector; likewise in Ghana, SMEs account for 70% of all businesses and employed 70% of the total workforce. The sector also sums up 97% of businesses and 18% of workforce in Zambia (World Bank Report, 2016).

Opinions are therefore unanimous that SMEs has largely aided the industrialization goals of the continent, with more than 50% of employment in low and lower middle-income countries attributed to businesses with less than 100 employees (Murithi, 2017). In Nigeria, the emphasis is more glaring considering that SMEs comprise 96% of the country's businesses in comparison with 53% in the US and 65% in Europe in last few decades. Bakshi (2018)

affirms that the recent epoch has seen significant growth in the African continent compared to the rest of the world. This is because, while the rest of the world economies were struggling with other more complex route to economic growth, African growth averaged more than 5% far above America, Europe and South America in the last ten years.

Notwithstanding the nonsymmetrical growth experienced across such African countries as Angola, Rwanda and Malawi, Zimbabwe and even Nigeria (that continues to struggle when her over 200 million population rate is considered in relation to her level of economic growth), the overall positive growth has made Africa the centre of economic attraction for foreign investors offering direct investment opportunities especially from USA, China, Japan, India, and more; a process expected to further boost long term economic growth. Nevertheless, SMEs operating in Africa are not devoid of personal constraints and many more challenges inhibiting their growth and survival (Murithi, 2017).

Bakshi (2018) avows that beside their positive role to development, SMEs face many obstacles that restrict their long term survival. SMEs in Africa are susceptible to high mortality rate, a milieu attributed to financial hurdles. Okewu (2015) observed that in Africa, a huge chunk of initial financing for SMEs is derived from personal savings of the operators themselves and from informal financial sources, while additional debt funding comes mainly from the formal institutions. This has led to premature extinction of most of the SMEs within the first five years of their operation, with only a handful managing to breakeven. Murithi (2017) asserts that this is not surprising as the SMEs activities revolve around the poor who can barely meet the loan conditionality of recognized financial institutions.

Categorically in Uganda, only one-third of new business start-ups stay afloat beyond one year of operation; while in South Africa, the failure rate is between 50% and 95% depending on the subsector. To the foregoing, Bakshi (2018) further revealed that 75% of SMEs in South

Africa fail to metamorphose into established businesses; thus ranking South Africa as the country with the highest SME failure rate in the world. Chad has also been named as a country with failure of 65% and one of the most difficult countries for business transactions and SMEs operation.

Nigeria is not left out of the unfavorable regulatory frameworks and other unfriendly business conditions (Ezika, 2019). Although the African continent in general has shown significant improvement in business environment in the last ten years (which attracted various business interests from different parts of world), it is still ranked by World Bank as the most difficult region to transact businesses, particularly for the SME sector which is ranked at the bottom of regions like Eastern Europe, Central Asia, East Asia and Pacific, Middle East and North Africa, Latin America and South Asia (Fjose et al., 2010; Bakshi, 2018).

2.4.3 Small And Medium Scale Enterprises In Nigeria

Nigeria economic history is well stocked with insights into the humble beginnings of present-day successful businesses and grand corporations; enough to emphasise that historically, SMEs orientation has been an integral aspect of ancestral Nigeria even before the advent of colonial rule. Ningi & Mairiga (2015) asserts that evidence abounds in our respective communities of what successes our progenitors made of their respective farming, woodwork, pottery, iron smelting, cottage industries and other entrepreneurial endeavors. Motilewa, Ogbari and Aka (2015) affirms that at first, they went into subsistence farming to placate their instantaneous needs.

But as society evolved and got inhabited by more people and given the diverse human talents, natural and geographic endowments, in contrast to the farmers inability to meet other people's needs; they then expanded into other SME craftsmanship and trades so as to fulfill these other needs. However, the secret behind the success of their self-reliant strategy was not

premised on any given political ideology, rather on the self-will and inherent entrepreneurial initiative of our fore-fathers to undertake indigenous entrepreneurial ventures, which overtime evolved to become what we know today as Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) and the emerging Large Corporations (Ningi & Mairiga, (2015). In order words, most of the existing large scale industries and multinational corporations were once cottage enterprises, growing as their industry grew and through their sheer ability either reproduce existing products more cheaply or improved their ability.

It is however important to point out that the imperialistic usurpation of Nigerian economy by the erstwhile colonial masters, gave a consequential twist to the development of small and medium scale industries and entrepreneurial ventures in Colonial Nigeria; because the existing small cottage industries were dominated by European multinational corporations (such as: John Holt plc., United African Company UAC., Lever Brothers, Patterson and Zochonis PZ., etc.) and grossly exploited for cheap raw materials (Udenta, 2015). Hence little or no attention was directed towards the development of Small and Medium Scale industries in pre-independence Nigeria, rather the colonial-induced economic policies of government were geared towards serving the interest of the colonialist.

Fortunately, Nigeria's independence in 1960 marked a turning point in the growth and development of SMEs. Ayozie *et al.*, (2013) aver that the major activities towards SMEs development rather began between 1987 and 1989 with the establishment of several institutions to provide financial assistance to small and medium enterprises. The institutions/schemes include: The Nigeria Industrial Development Bank, the Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry, Nigerian Agricultural and Cooperative Bank, the National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) etc. However, by the mid-1990s, the funds being made available by these institutions had dried up and most of the SMEs had collapsed

as a result of the debt burden (i.e. inflated foreign exchange) and the concavity in the value of the Naira.

The resultant effect was that the contributions made by the SME sector to the economy were below par. Lack of sufficient funding and lack of managerial skills were described as the major reason for the high mortality rate of SMEs in Nigeria. Reports of the 2001 Nigerian Economic Summit Group cited in Okafor, Onifade and Ogbechi (2018), revealed with the devaluation of Naira and rise in inflation (an after-effect of the Structural Adjustment Programme) SMEs growth and sustainability were inhibited. Hence about 70% of small and medium businesses in Nigeria failed in the first five year of being in operation. The milieu necessitated the formulation of new policies and attitudes towards the growth and development of SMEs in Nigeria.

In 2001, the Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS) was launched under the guidance of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to encourage the Nigerian Bank's Committee in 2000 to set aside 10% of its annual profit before tax for equity investment in small and medium scale enterprises to accelerate their growth. The Bank of Industry (BOI) was also reconstituted in 2001 with the core mandate to provide financial assistance and entrepreneur mentorship for the establishment of SMEs; likewise for the expansion, diversification and modernization of existing enterprises as well as for the rehabilitation of ailing industries in Nigeria (Taiwo *et al.*, 2016; Oputu, 2015).

Subsequently in 2003, the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) was also set up to stimulate, monitor, and coordinate the development of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in an efficient and sustainable manner. In addition to the Federal Government YouWIN (Youth Enterprise with Innovation) scheme in 2013, the Federal and State Governments partnered to setup entrepreneurship development centres to

provide institutional support for the development of SMEs (Abeh, 2017; Ningi and Mairiga, 2015). Yet, it is discouraging to see that even with all the formulated policies, national development plans and aid programmes, SMEs in Nigeria are still performing below expectation and still susceptible to premature extinction; perhaps more so because women are not fully represented in the scheme of events.

2.5 SMEs ENVIRONMENT IN NIGERIA

2.5.1 PEST Analysis Of SMEs In Nigeria

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are business-oriented enterprises in Nigeria transacting in a translucent open system, with interdependent interactions with its environment (Pogson, 2014). The SME environment is described as a set of factors, policies and institutions that shape the opportunities and motivation of business owners to invest productively, manage risks, grow and expand (Igwe *et al.*, 2019). The implication is that the environment influences SME operations, but which has to be favorable to the business to ensure sustainable SMEs in Nigeria. Consequently, SME owners/operators must plan, take decisions and execute them within the limits imposed by the environment. Avail to say that the environment is a strong determinant of the success or failure of an SME in Nigeria. The SME environment in Nigeria is typically classified into the political, socio-cultural, economic and technological environment.

2.5.1.1 Political Environment

The political environment covers the forms of institutions (from military to democracy) and governing issues in which the business enterprises operate or are subjected to (Igwe *et al.*, 2019). The Nigeria political environment has been a turbulent one for SME ventures in the country, subsumed in the unfortunate circumstances of political instability from 1966 till the recent democratic dispensation. Politics they say is the superstructure that exerts humongous

impact on the other structures, particularly the economy (Okpata, 2019). Politically, the Nigerian economy since the military interregnum has been faced with challenges of reintegration into the global economy as a result of misplaced priorities, policy discontinuity, corrupt and self-centred leaders.

For decades now, successive regimes in Nigeria have proffered and attempted different plans, policies and programs; structuring and restructuring institutions, the entire socio-economic and political system to attain more efficient and more desirable economic growth and development of both society and the individual. But prior to the introduction of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises were virtually neglected in all the development plans of the country (Adah and Abasilim, 2016). Following SAP, Nigeria governments initiated series of programmes and policies for SMEs development as well as sought collaborative effort with International Organizations, Bilateral and Multilateral Agencies and Non- Governmental Organizations (NGOs) to steer SMEs support.

Major landmarks include: Specialized financial institution and development aid programs such as: the Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI), Nigerian Industrial Development Bank (NIDB), Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF), National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND), Bank of Industry (BOI), Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises Apex Unit Loan Scheme, Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS), Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), as well as the World Bank SME I and SME II fiscal incentive initiatives for business grants and granting tax holiday SMEs for the first six years of its operation (Abeh, 2017).

Also the Central Bank of Nigeria setup credit guidelines/rules requiring commercial bank to set aside certain percentage of their funds as loan to small businesses. There were also export incentives from the Nigerian Export-Import Bank (NEXIM) to encourage export loan facilities to small businesses as well as export duty exemptions administered by the Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC). The Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YouWIN) and Entrepreneurship Development Centres (EDC) by State governments provided various training initiatives, repair and maintenance of machines, and extension services for SMEs (Ningi and Mairiga, 2015; Young, 2017).

Despite the laudable schemes and initiatives put in place, the effect is yet to be felt by operator/owners of SMEs (Igwe et al, 2018; Evbuomwan et al, 2014). Thus, the argument is that the problem is not lack of ideas and policies by the political actors, but the problem of unstable political environment commonly associated with political instability and its correlates of policies/programmes discontinuity which has continued to make mockery of successive government efforts.

2.5.1.2 Economic Environment

The economic environment comprises of factors that directly and indirectly impacts on the nature and direction of production, distribution and consumption of goods and services. It also encompasses the price level, productivity level; interest rate, employment rate, real income level, savings level, etc. Igwe, *et al.*, (2018) aver that government over the years has pursued economic policies that would provide favourable economic conditions for small and medium business including trade liberalization and some incentives towards making the economic environment friendly for entrepreneurs. Nevertheless, the economic environment of SMEs in Nigeria depicts a circus race of trying to achieve the extraordinary but paradoxically eluding the simple.

The Federal Government fiscal and monetary policies in Nigeria as it relates to business issues have been more or less unpredictable, contradictory, inconsistent and from time to time conflicting. The federal government has formulated good policies in the past but implementation, control and consistency have always been the problem (Ezika, 2019). This has created a lot of hurdles not just for SMEs but the entirety of domestic investors who as against their foreign counterparts have the alternative of making Nigeria a dumping ground for their output (Abeh, 2017).

2.5.1.3 Socio-Cultural Environment

SMEs socio-cultural environment consists of factors related to human behaviour and human relationships in business. Nwachukwu and Ubana (2019) explain that the business environment usually consist of individuals from different background and various dispositions who come with their varying mind-set and belief to interact with each other to achieve certain set goals. However, these differences otherwise referred to as diversity is attendant with far-reaching challenges that could be either disadvantageous or favourable to the SME, contingent on the manner with which they are handled.

Thus, the social-cultural environmental factor comprises of demographic characteristics such as population density and distribution; family structure like attitude of the family; social concerns and social attitudes; and most significantly the cultural orientation and traditional believes regarding business and wealth creation. The owner-manager family structure mentality of SMEs is prevalent in Nigeria. The reality of this social milieu is the control of all activities personally, while taking decisions in matters affecting the entire enterprise with little or no time for modification, or to train and up ones forte and mastery of contemporaneous knowledge for effective business management. Also worth mentioning is that the owner-manager family structure is usually a failure in business longevity, because the demise of the owner of the enterprise may mark the end of the business (Ezika, 2019).

In Nigeria, the people's way of life or traditional approach to SME is that business or trading is the escape route for those who are unable to go to school; thus SME is seen as an alternative to western education in the pursuit of greener pastures. Alabi *et al.*, (2015) explains that the fact that there is no educational restriction on starting/owning SMEs in Nigeria makes the whole situation even worse and business owners may have no understanding of what they are getting into. There is also the cultural belief of SMEs owners/operators search for immediate wealth by supernatural and/or superstitious means rather than systematic business management process (Micah *et al.*, 2017). It is quite not uncommon for some African people to seek different unorthodox means to acquire wealth. This has been observed through activities of traditional money doublers, black magic perpetrators, and witch doctors. It is important to stress however that the acquisition of wealth through these means remain vaguely understood and remains a mystery.

2.5.1.4 Technological Environment

Globalisation and its technological innovations have certainly raised the level of competitiveness for Nigerian businesses; and while many SMEs have indeed succumbed to a deteriorated level of competitiveness, others have found ways to actually enhance their positions in global markets (Young, 2017). The technological environment of SMEs in Nigeria is related to the knowledge applied in the production process, innovations, machines and materials used for producing goods and services. Technology therefore deals with continuous changes or improvement in expertise and technical know-how; changes of which influences the operations of SMEs (Hanadi and Aruna, 2015).

This is especially true of modern communication technology, because online databases enable vast quantities of information to be shared easily and quickly between businesses and their customers. Adepoju, Olomu and Akinwale (2018) avow that technology definitely impacts the production and distribution of goods and services, as its innovations improves the

speed and efficiency with which goods and services are accessed or delivered to the consumers and also help minimise cost. But most Nigerian SMEs are still playing catch-up, while majority of them rely heavily on conventional technology and traditional labour rather than the use of modern technology.

The cause is said not to be limited to lack of funding rather ignorance or lack of knowledge, as those SME operators that do have access to funds but due to imprudence and/or sheer managerial ignorance of technological trends tend to purchase obsolete, valueless and inefficient equipment with the resultant effect of low productivity and poor product quality. Adepaju *et al.*, (2018) clearly note that SMEs often have difficulties in gaining access to appropriate technologies and information on available techniques. They further argue that in most circumstances SMEs make use of foreign technology with a scarce percentage of shared ownership or leasing. In addition to this unfavourable milieu, SMEs have to acquire foreign licenses, because local patents are difficult to obtain.

2.5.2 Relevance Of Small And Medium Enterprises To The Nigerian Economy

The importance of SMEs to the Nigerian economy is not contestable as findings of various studies (Etuk *et al.*, 2014; Abeh 2017; Ezika, 2019) avow that SMEs play pivotal role in the country's economic development and in building Nigeria as a nation. To the foregoing, Eniola (2014) avers that a thriving SME sector is seen as one of the most effective instruments of poverty alleviation in Nigeria. Poverty according to Abeh (2017) is a state of need and helplessness; of not having access to necessities of life that support actual dwelling. Etuk *et al.*, (2014) noted that this state of helplessness has been a major threat to Nigerian's attainment of sustainable human and environmental development.

Presently, the successful performance of the SME subsector is deemed a recipe for wealth creation which invariably alleviates poverty in the society. On this premise, Ezika (2019)

corroborates that SMEs play a vital role in reducing poverty and inequality among the citizenry, predominantly due to the affordable and relatively low capital requirement for its establishment; which gives hope to the common man. Effectively, SMEs convert the dormant and idle resources like land, labour and capital into goods and services and engage both skilled and unskilled workforce to create viable means of livelihood.

A healthy and robust SME sector is also a key instrument in fighting insecurity and ensuring crime reduction economically, because SMEs contribute to the gainful employment of the teeming unemployed youths. To the foregoing, Ebitu, *et al.*, (2016) assert that SMEs constitute about 97% of all businesses in Nigeria and generate about 98% of the 1.8 million jobs created each year. Adding more substance to the foregoing assertion, Oduntan, (2014) explained that because SMEs symptomatically are more labour intensive than large scale enterprises, they have the capacity to generate more employment thereby solving the problem of unemployment in the country to a very large extent. Hence, more jobs per unit of investment capital and per unit energy consumed are created worldwide by SMEs than large scale enterprises.

Likewise, the promotion of cottage and rural industries is amongst the major contributions of SMEs towards enhancing the Nigerian economy. According to Abeh (2017), SMEs are the foundation of any economy because their presence in rural areas do not only help in the development of such places but also support the socio-economic transformation of such areas. Historical evidence indicates that most of today's giant corporations began as very small firms. Thus as succinctly put by Eniola (2014), SMEs are regarded as the bedrock of industrialization, because they constitute vital ingredients for stimulating and transforming rural entrepreneurship and indigenous technology.

Hence natural resources that would have been lying waste are put into effective use through SMEs active participation in the production of goods and services as well as in buying and selling. Most importantly, small-scale industries provide ample opportunities for the development of local skills and technology acquisition through adaptation (Abeh, 2017). A good example of such indigenous technological transformation is the popular 'Made in Aba Goods', whose innovative SME operations have over the year's engendered industrial esteem virtually acknowledged by all Nigerians.

SMEs also stand a better chance of reducing rural-urban migration. This is because quite a large number of SMEs are springing forth in the rural areas hence the rural populace are gaining useful employment as a result of the activities of the small and medium businesses. This considerably reduces the rate of rural-urban erosion in Nigeria and as succinctly put by Eniola (2014) "68% of Nigeria SMEs Owners operate in rural areas, narrowing the gap between urban and rural development as well as social inequities and rural migration". It can therefore be innocuously argued that one of the far-reaching relevance of the SME subsector is its potential of guaranteeing development that is inclusive and participatory at the grassroots.

Abeh (2017) avers that SMEs generate income both for the citizens and the nation by means of their various economic activities through which the businesses generate profits. Just as the people gain income through SMEs paid employment, government likewise generates more revenue as these SMEs pay taxes to government. Adding more substance to the foregoing, Eniola (2014) avows that SMEs contribute to income generation as well as income redistribution, since the development of SMEs help spread income to more people. SMEs promote savings and investment in as much as they also spread income in the polity. Hence, SMEs facilitate even distribution of wealth to bridge the gap between the rich and the poor.

The development of small and medium scale production encourages export promotion and enhances Large Scale Enterprises. This according to Oduntan (2014) is because most of the exporting Industries are interdependent on SMEs for business. SMEs supply the much needed raw materials/primary commodities to export oriented Large Scale Industries. To this end, equilibrium in the demand and supply of specific raw material results to economics of scale. This consequently results in reduced prices beneficial to large scale production and advantageous for the consumers. In a similar vein, Ebitu, *et al.*, (2016) emphasize that SMEs generate mutual industrial linkages between local producers of raw materials and large industrial ventures since most SME output serves as intermediate or semi-processed goods of large scale firms.

2.5.3 Leadership In SMEs

Leadership is critical in changing the business environment of our contemporary Nigerian society, where small and medium sized enterprises operate under harsh conditionality (Igwe *et al.*, 2018). SMEs therefore have to navigate and surmount the change challenges of globalization by creating competitive advantage for themselves. Bojadziev and Mileva (2019) clearly note that SMEs cannot build competitive advantages over larger companies on the basis of resources alone. They argue that their competitive advantage lies in flexibility and adaptation to changing needs of customers and market condition; and these change processes which makes or mar the business, require the effectiveness of leadership.

Suffice to say that the most critical element of sustainable SMEs is leadership and according to Miltra and Taherdoost (2015) the strategic behaviour of SME owner/managers is a defining characteristic of the leadership process. They further assert that because the internal human resource capabilities of SMEs are characteristically different from what is obtainable in large firms, the influence of leaders on their followers is more pronounced in the SME

sector. Therefore, the performance and sustainability of SMEs is essentially related to the leadership of the enterprise which is the all-important driving force. However, opinions are unanimous that the leadership requirements of SMEs are rather more problematical. Mitra and Hamed (2017) explain that this is because SMEs are not merely new start-ups, neither are they large mature organisation, but a somewhat combination of both.

Thus, leadership in SME start-up call for hands-on management with leaders seen more as managers involved in the day-to-day activities. Leadership in the already established and expanding SME ventures require leaders who establish the long-term company vision and the required strategy to achieve it. In a nutshell, SME operations and longevity require leaders who are able to manage the company dynamically whilst setting a clear company direction. Franco and Matos (2015) corroborate that without effective leadership, businesses often grow much more slowly and often lose direction and as a result, fall behind competitors.

Therefore, leadership in SME need to successfully see to fruition three key roles so as to provide the enterprise with effective leadership. These are, taking up responsibility for company finances since no business can thrive without a sound financial outlook; making good calculated decisions that allow the enterprise to operate effectively and compete successfully, (it also behoves on SME leadership to inspire workers), and encouraging them to feel valued and motivated to work hard and believe in the enterprise (Miltra and Taherdoost, 2015). Regardless of the established knowledge that effective leadership is the key element that drives the success of SMEs, the structure and style of leadership in Nigerian SMEs is seen as the nerve centre that impacts on the long-term sustainability of an enterprise.

Perhaps this is what motivated Adeoye (2019) to categorical emphasis on those factors influencing effective leadership as a key element stimulating SME growth and sustainability, which are the SME leadership structure, characteristics and features; leader's aspirations, motivations and intentions; and the leader's behaviour towards planning and overall business

management. The first aspect relates to how SMEs in Nigeria are assembled, the physiognomies of the SME operators/personnel, their experience, education, skills, expertise, etc. The second elucidates SME leaders' motivation for fulfilling tasks and achieving set goals, attitude to innovation and inclination towards risk, as well as determining how the leader's aspirations and intentions are reflected in his actions and attitudes. Then, the third aspect hinges on the leader's behaviour concerning his capacity for the firm's administrative planning and strategic management.

In Nigeria, leadership in SMEs is characterized by un-professionalized 'Owner-Manager' leadership structure (Abeh, 2017). Taiwo, *et al.*, (2016) avow that in most Nigeria SME ventures, managers tend to be the business owners as well as chief executive, managing director and the overall controller of the enterprise. The owner-manager practically does everything alone; he/she is actively in charge of the decision-making process and day to day operation of the firm with little or no adequate specialist support. In fact, the basic orientation of SMEs in Nigeria is "Family Business" because it is being controlled by one person or a few related people and because of their close nature of operations (Abeh, 2017).

The success of Nigerian SMEs is usually in jeopardy as 'Owner-Manager' most likely would do everything themselves, even when they lack the required entrepreneurial skills and expertise proficiency to survive and push the business beyond the subsistence level. Micah, *et al.*, (2017) argues that these have given an explanation for the lack of pioneering, inventive, innovative, dynamic, vibrant and entrepreneurial resourcefulness necessary to take risks and effectively confront and tackle issues as they emerge. Though the predicament is mostly that SMEs operators are financially incapable to employ and retain the required skilled professionals, but of note is the phobia-induced reluctance to employ, they are afraid that they may not know the nitty-gritty of the business any longer or that they may lose control of certain key decisions. Young (2017) was more nuanced in his opinion that the

individualistic tendency of SME ‘Owner-Managers’ is borne out of their desire to maintain and protect their business, paying lip-service to the fact that as the enterprise grows, there may be need for more people to take up decision-making roles and responsibilities in strategic and operational areas of the business.

2.5.4 Gender And Entrepreneur Leadership In Nigeria

Since the advent of civilization and organized labour, gender issues in entrepreneurship have been of great concern for some national governments with organized groups globally clamoring for an end to gender inequality (Hyson, 2017). To address gender discrimination, the United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) was passed in 1979 (Bako and Syed, 2018). However, gender egalitarianism in leadership has continued to elude some countries of the world, particularly in Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African region, where the socio-cultural, religious and political structures wholly operate on patriarchal systems, with women not regarded as the right human species to lead. Yet obvious is the misogynist African mentality that contends ‘why a woman should lead full-blooded men’ even when they are more competent (Goslin and Kluka, 2014).

No wonder the numerous cross-cultural studies on leadership have generally been limited to female leaders in Western societies and economies, until most recently when radical social and management scientists have begun to pave way for gender-entrepreneur-leadership studies across Africa. Gender Egalitarianism according to Andrew and Jefferson (2019) refers to the extent to which a society minimizes the differences between gender roles in promotion of gender equality in leadership. Dishearteningly, the Sub-Saharan African countries are ranked poor in gender egalitarianism because their leadership system is built upon masculine attributes. Perhaps the reoccurring decimal of gender inequality in entrepreneur leadership is

better illustrated by the 2019 United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) report, which revealed that the female gender in sub-Saharan Africa merely hold 29% of managerial positions (Adegoke, Adegoke, and Oyedele 2016).

Regardless of the fact that women make up more than half of the global population, they only constituted 39% of the total workforce in 2018. Marginalization of women is persistent in Nigeria in almost all spheres of the economy, with women constantly facing massive inequalities in the labour market. In working life, women meet with higher rates of unemployment, fewer possibilities for a career, and lower wages. Even highly educated women or those trying to attain higher education face marginalization in Nigeria (UNDP, 2019).

The issue of gender and entrepreneur leadership in Nigeria and its implications on the growth of the SME sector and the attainment of Nigeria's re-industrialization goals is gradually becoming a matter of major concern to intellectual bodies. Statistically, women constitute more than 50% of the Nigerian population and out of the record; only about 21% of the registered entrepreneurial small and medium businesses in Nigeria are run by women and only about 35% of them are generally involved in entrepreneurship which takes the form of micro, small, medium and large enterprises (Imhonopi *et al.*, 2016).

It rather disconcerting that in spite of women's huge physical population in Nigeria, and their educational, economic and social accomplishments, they are not well represented in SMEs leadership. It is even more appalling that the female gender is not even substantially represented in the decision-making chamber that decides on issues pertaining to SME businesses and entrepreneurial development in Nigeria (Bako and Syed, 2018; Miniti, 2016; Imhonopi *et al.*, 2016).

2.5.5 Challenges Facing Women Leadership In Nigeria SMEs

Contemporary opinions are unanimous to the perception that women entrepreneurs in Nigeria are confronted with similar challenges but more distinctive constraints compared to their counterparts in other developing countries (Taiwo *et al.*, 2016). Women in Nigeria represent far lesser figures in SMEs leadership due to all forms of discrimination meted against them which continuous to constitute adverse challenges to the growth and sustainability of the SMEs subsector. Discussing the challenges of women entrepreneurship in Nigeria, Imhonopi, *et al.*, (2016) disclose that women in Nigeria are less likely to become an entrepreneurial leader and get involved in business ownership because of their gender and the structural disadvantage of women in accessing funding and other meaningful resources.

Igwe *et al.*, (2018) aver that Nigerian women are stereotypical discriminated against and this affect most women ability to gain access to finance. Besides, statistical data point out that women suffer the effects of financial and economic downturns more than their male counterpart; hence more often than not, most women complain that they are not able to meet the conditionality that grants them access to corporate funding and there is also the challenge of penetrating informal financial network (like borrowing from friends and relatives, the financial black market or unregistered money lenders). Thus, access to finance poses as a major constraint to female entrepreneurs in Nigeria.

Without an iota of doubt, the inability to access funding is an inhibiting factor facing women leadership in Nigeria SMEs which not only limits their ability to secure sufficient capital for SME start-up; it further results in inadequate working capital for entrepreneur women leaders already in business. Subsequently, it culminates in lack of funds for assets financing and rehabilitation needs, down to financial incapacitation for diversification or new investments, and they become fiscally handicap to offer prepossessing remuneration to attract and retain

skilled professional employees, as well as financial malignancy to meet adequate training and development needs required for effective leadership (Ezika, 2019).

Micah *et al.*, (2017) further argues that women leadership in SMEs face poor access to information and technology as most of them do not have access to computers and internet facilities, thereby inhibiting their SME leadership prowess/potentials. No doubt, the challenges of poor access to finance, information and modern technology are impactful on women leadership in Nigeria SMEs. However, it can be innocuously argued that these challenges are not as inherent as the stereotypical perception of people regarding women involvement or leadership roles in business; a perception commonly referred to as the “African mentality”.

Thus, the role of women leadership in Nigeria SMEs is marred by the orientation placed on the female gender that a woman is meant to cook, clean and take care of her home, irrespective of her professional or social status or achievements. Laden with the two jobs of being a home-maker and an entrepreneur leader, Igwe *et al.*, (2018) posits that the traditional African role of taking care of the home has remained ineradicable what characterize the foremost challenges facing women leadership in Nigeria SMEs. Consequently, the women have to combine the overwhelming duties of a being a wife, mother, daughter and an entrepreneurial leader.

The implication is that when it is not managed properly, these conflicting roles can stand in the way of running a successful start-up or even being an effective leader in an already existing firm. Adding more substance to the foregoing, Taiwo *et al.*, (2016) aver that women enterprise owners are likely to experience work–home role conflict regardless of the structure of their family or the number of hours spent at work; and this role conflict has been

associated with the level of business satisfaction and perceived success of sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

Bako and Syed (2018) note that gender restrictions in SME and entrepreneur leadership in Nigeria can be traced to the taciturnity of women's exploits in business activities and leadership. They further argue that Leadership in business and leaders generally are perceived to be ambitious, competitive, decisive, and vision and goal oriented; and these are qualities professed to be the distinctive cultural masculinity of SME leadership roles. Perhaps this was what inspired Edgar Schein's popular cultural model of "think-manager-think-male".

Schein observed that there has been a heralded mismatch between the argentic (silver-lining) attributes of male leadership and the female gender; thus vilifying any woman who dares to take the leadership path to conflict issues and segregation within an organization (Okafor and Akukuwebe, 2016). Particularly in the case of Nigeria, leadership proficiency is contemptuously viewed to be more masculine than feminine in terms of socio-cultural categorisation. Hence, the perception is that men are made-up to live for work and make money to care for the family, while women are not. This in concomitance with a woman's domestic role is said to be an inhibiting factor to women entrepreneur leadership (Imhonopi et al., 2016; Bako and Syed, 2018).

2.5.6 Factors That Contribute Towards Women Leadership In Nigeria SMEs

The explanation for the behaviour of women entrepreneurs and their gender-related distinctiveness is multifaceted and as succinctly put by Imhonopi *et al.*, (2016), this gender-related distinctiveness is their strength and what makes them stand out in entrepreneur leadership, particularly in Nigeria where the curbing of gender inequality is still a Shangri-La. Globally, women suffer more gender stereotypical discrimination, with more emphasis to their common traits of sympathy, responsiveness, care, and loyalty being a major hurdle for

leadership (Taiwo *et al.*, 2016). Ironically, scholarly works are beginning to observe that these traits rather enrich the capability of the female gender to be a better SME leader that guides, coaches and inspires followers/subordinates more than the male gender.

Imhonopi *et al.*, (2016) further argue that these traits make up some of the most impactful factors of women SME leadership in Nigeria. Some scholars attributed these factors to such motivational dynamics as: entrepreneurs search for independence, autonomy, greener pasture or improved income, as well as the opportunity to be one's own boss. These factors are applicable to both the male and female gender; but more distinctive to women. Bako and Syed (2018) argue that women first and foremost women rank the need for independence and need for greater flexibility, as they have to balance work and personal life; and this is reinforced by the observation that money lies in the third interest for female entrepreneurs, whilst male entrepreneurs rank money in the first interest.

The implication is that it results in more passion and strong responsiveness for women, which are effective entrepreneur leadership variables. Thus, women entrepreneurs more often than not, adopt distinct behavioural patterns from men and have different expectations as they seem to have the willpower and pay more attention to details in order to balance the all-round requirements of the business and the demands of family life (Economic Co-operation and Development Report, 2012). Bako and Syed (2018) corroborate that these traits enhance women leadership effectiveness, while the male entrepreneur leaders invariably prove their masculinity by exerting transactional and laissez-faire leadership styles, which are less attributed to the collective traits of women.

Conversely, women are observed to be warm and kind; qualities that befit support and exemplary leadership. Therefore, women aim to strike a balance between being a “good woman” and a “good leader”, inclining them to lean towards the participative and transformational leadership approach. Based on the foregoing premise, there are studies

(Taiwo *et al.*, 2016; Imhonopi *et al.*, 2016; Offerman and Coats, 2018) that assessed women to display traits of a transformational leader compared to their male counterparts, especially in workers' motivation and development. These scholars observed that women make better leaders than men because effective leadership for organizational sustainability may no longer require the command and control leader or top-bottom autocratic leadership approach of the male gender.

Nevertheless, women are resilient and strong-willed and as clearly emphasized by Afuegbu (2019), their professionalism is top-notch in terms of work-life balance, that is, their ability to reconcile their professional and personal lives. Moreover, one of the most inhibiting challenges of underperforming SMEs in Nigeria is the inability of owner-manager to separate their personal life from their professional life (Ezika, 2019). When work and family responsibilities collide, men may lay claim to the cultural narrative of the good provider. But women rarely view themselves as working to feed, clothe or shelter their families, which are the responsibilities of what men should do. So, unlike men who still think of their family responsibilities in terms of fitting into the breadwinner narrative with everything at stake, women habitually see theirs as role modeling for their children (Groysberg and Abraham, 2014).

In other words, women emphasize (much more than men) how important it is for their children to see them as competent professionals, and for society to regard them as a whole being. This assertion avails to argue that women entrepreneur leaders can and do engage meaningfully with work, family, and community; discovering through hard experience (of being a homemaker and an entrepreneur) that effectiveness in business leadership is a matter of carefully combining work and home so as not to lose themselves, their loved ones, or their foothold on success.

Worthy of note is the clarity of thought and rationality of women leaders who are averse to uncalculated risk-taking; factors of which contribute towards the success of women leadership in Nigerian SMEs and entrepreneurial ventures. Contemporary studies such as the

survey by Okafor and Alakende (2019) revealed that having women as owners and managers of SMEs not only diminishes the risk potential for such businesses but also reduces the likelihood of insolvency and premature extinction. The emphasis within the context of this study is that decision-making process for an SME is a highly intellectual and cognitive task considering that SME risk-taking is a volatile venture. The onus therefore behooves on a leader whose rationality and clarity of thoughts is useful in value addition.

2.6 THE CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABILITY AND KEY VARIABLES OF SUSTAINABLE SME

2.6.1 Sustainability And Its Indicators

SMEs are regarded as the catalyst of industrialization and economic development in Nigeria and other countries of the world. Thus, their sustainability is important to the economy of any country focusing on the creation of a favourable environment where businesses can succeed, grow and thrive. Suffice to say that sustainability is tantamount to a sustainable economy, considering their importance to the economy (Mwangi and Sejjaaka, 2016). A traditional definition of the concept of sustainability associated with the owners and managers of SMEs, relates to enterprise performance (Peters, 2019).

Thus, the performance of SMEs is defined as the major sustainability indicator of a country's economy. Sustainable SMEs is therefore defined as a state of continuous competitive existence of an enterprise, centred on creation of meaningful value for both society and the individuals. Ion and Criveanu (2016) avow that the meaningfulness of the value created for sustainability is made manifest by the level of such variables as: effectiveness, efficiency, quality, timeliness and finance, as well as workplace environment.

2.6.1.1 SMEs Efficiency

SMEs efficiency reflects their productivity which is described as how successfully inputs have been converted into outputs. Thus, Ion and Criveanu (2016) defines efficiency as the ratio of relevant outputs to relevant inputs. From the economic and financial aspect of enterprise performance or sustainable SMEs, evaluation is based on how efficient the business or firm is performing because efficiency is a criterion that evaluates the relationship between inputs and outputs. Avram and Rus (2016) corroborate that efficiency measures relationship between efforts and outcomes or the successfulness in transforming resources into maximum output. Suffice to say that efficiency is about resource allocation across alternative uses or an enterprise optimal use of resources to achieve desired output, such that the lesser the inputs used to generate maximum outputs, the greater the level of SME efficiency. Ilona and Evelina (2016) affirm that efficiency is achieving the necessary outputs from little resources, always with a view to maintaining optimum output.

2.6.1.2 SMEs Finance

Enterprise finance deals with the profitability of outcomes and the stewardship or prudence in the management of funds (Ion and Criveanu, 2016). Accordingly, profitability reviews the quality of the conducted activities of an enterprise at every stage, at all levels. This implies that profitability of outcomes synthesizes the productivity of factors of production and the performance of all designed activities. Hence for every SME operator or capital holder, maximizing outputs and profitability are of utmost priority since both variables provides resources for developing the respective economic activities for sustainable SMEs.

Prudence or stewardship in management of funds is also a major variable of sustainable SMEs, which requires those responsible for managing and investing enterprise money to act in good faith and with utmost care. Ejere (2015) affirms that stewardship in management of funds ensures minimum wastage or theft and that meaningful value is always derived for any

money spent. Therefore, prudence in management of funds brings into play the responsibilities of SMEs leaders/managers in budgeting or prioritizing income and expenditure, good accounting system, and proper documentation of business transactions.

To the foregoing, Obasan, Shabayo and Amaghionyeodiwe (2016) emphasize that these responsibilities would require professional expertise of managerial/entrepreneurial competence and innovativeness to adapt to the changing environment. Elger (2015) argues that presently, SMEs are under perpetual pressure, based on complex demand from shareholders, employers, employees, customers, suppliers, government and the society at large; and in order to optimally address each demand/requirement, enterprises have to overcome social and environmental hassles to enhance their sustainability.

2.6.1.3 SMEs Effectiveness (Business Growth)

Effectiveness, which is associated with business growth, is defined as the extent to which an enterprise or organization is achieving desired results at any point in its operations (Ion and Criveanu, 2016). Hence, the enterprise main focus is to achieve their mission, goals and vision of growth through new investments, expansion, diversification, etc. Ion and Criveanu further argue that an enterprise is rather operationally effective being able to recognize, direct and control the interface amid socio-economic influences of development, as well as responding to expectations of the environment. Thus, effectiveness deals with how well an organization as a social entity, bearing in mind the scarcity of resources and other means, realizes its goals without exerting excessive effort from its participants and other stakeholders.

Therefore, SMEs effectiveness signifies the degree of progress towards set objectives by asking such question as ‘Do we have what we wanted? Are we where we want to be?’ The answers are obtained through the measurement of results based on the principle of doing only those things that really should be done. Suffice to say that an effective activity is such activity

whose results most closely match the expected goals. However, the realization of enterprise goals and objectives not only depend on doing only those things that really should be done, but doing them at the right time and in the right quality (Ilona and Evelina, 2016).

2.6.1.4 SMEs Timeliness And Quality

Timeliness is the characteristics of promptness or punctuality in getting things done appropriately (Ion and Criveanu, 2016). This implies that an SME aptness in producing and delivering goods or services of public requirements determines their sustainability; because for SMEs to remain in business and thrive, customer satisfaction fostered through good customer relationship must be paramount (Imhonopi *et al.*, 2016). Likewise, the quality variable is concerned with the creation of superior goods and services of great value that meets public requirements or customer satisfaction. Ion and Criveanu (2016) specifically conceptualize quality as the exceptional standard or grade of goods or services produced, as measured against other goods and services of similar kinds. From this definition, it can be innocuously argued that the exceptionality of an SME in satisfying customers or in meeting public requirements with standard goods/services enhances their competitiveness and survival.

2.6.1.5 SMEs Workplace Environment

The nature or level of workplace environment is regarded as a quintessence of sustainable SMEs. Conceivably, two of the most noteworthy physiognomies of a workplace environment are the organizational climate and organizational culture. Ion and Criveanu (2016) describe these terms as how the organization is able to focus on, and accentuate innovativeness, flexibility; appreciation and concern for employees' welfare, training, advancement, workforce orientation, values and ethics, practices, structure, leadership, etc. In a similar vein, Liou and Cheng, (2015) depicts both terms as a set of physiognomies that make an

organization's work environment unique from others. They further aver that these physiognomies are quite long lasting and tend to sway the performance of an entity. In other words, the convulsiveness of an SME organizational culture and climate, hinges on such factors as: the company policies, customs and values, as well as the state of physical infrastructure, communication, reward system or remuneration, employees' support, work hours, rest period, safety, health, security, values, beliefs, orientation, training and development, supervision, opportunity for advancement, etc.

Consequently, the extent to which these variables are manifest facilitates the healthy growth and competitiveness which ensure sustainable SMEs. Perhaps these variables were what motivated the unanimous opinion that leadership is a key element of sustainable SMEs. Esiebugie *et al.*, (2018) avow that it is leadership with the right approach/model that invariably enhances SMEs finance, effectiveness, efficiency, quality, timeliness and workplace environment. But to attain these heights, SME leadership must possess and manifest the effective leadership components of professionalism, clarity of thought and rational decision-making consistent with the company vision. Moreover, the enterprise operations must be built on good customers relationship and it has to be more inclusive by engaging professional support; with reliable communication to stimulate the entire organisation in helping to overcome any challenges; and in turn be responsive to customers and employees' needs, providing the right working conditions, as well as investing in the workforce through training and development opportunities to uphold them as a valuable productive resource.

2.6.2 Constraints To Sustainable SMEs In Nigeria

Undoubtedly, financial hurdle is regarded as the most formidable factor inhibiting the wherewithal and continuous competitive existence of SMEs in Nigeria. The 2016 survey reports of the National Bureau of Statistics quoted in Ebitu, *et al.*, (2016) revealed that 73.24

percent of the topmost urgent assistance required by business operators in Nigeria is finance. But, merely 4.2 percent of 17.2 million Small and Medium Enterprises succeed in obtaining loans or overdrafts from financial bodies; while new comers or startups discover it is almost impossible to acquire debt funding from Nigerian money houses. To the foregoing, Alabi et al (2015) notes that the problem of financing SMEs is no longer about where the funds will come from (i.e. sources of funds) but its ease of acquisition; as there are subject to certain stringent conditions.

In a similar vein, Owenvibiugie and Igbiniedion (2015) aver that factors inhibiting SMEs sufficient funding includes: inadequate credit information, dearth of collateral, cost of financing and other stringent conditions imposed by financial institutions. Worthy of note is the lack of professionalism and financial indiscipline, which are challenges hinging on the inability of SME owners/operators to separate their business life and funding from their personal life. This is exacerbated by the wide spread pilfering and outright theft prevalent among most SMEs staff which constitutes a major financial challenge as funds that could have grown the business end up in private pockets of staff. Thus, SMEs constraints not only rest on access to or availability of funds, but also on the characteristics of the entrepreneurs in terms of their perceptions, character or attitude in handling money, the full time commitment of the owner-manager and transparency of employees as well as other key strategic factors which could make or mar the performance of these enterprises (Ezika, 2019).

Besides financial huddles, the attainment of sustainable SMEs in Nigeria is also marred by poor management and/or leadership. Obasan, *et al.*, (2015) emphasize that most SMEs in Nigeria are characterized by un-professionalized Owner-Manager system such that the Owner-Managers practically perform all tasks themselves not soliciting the services of consultants or specialists. The shortcomings invariably culminate in total incompetence, wastefulness, depletion and poor utilization of available resources of businesses and firms.

Management most certainly is not a single activity; rather it accomplishing activities aptly and effectively with the cooperation and efforts of others. Management therefore involves planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, reporting and budgeting summed by the acronym POSDCORB; which encompasses the entirety of both manpower and material resources control in an entity, to actualize predetermined goals and objectives (Idede, 2012).

The optimum performance of SMEs is usually at peril as most business persons do not possess the required entrepreneurial skills and entrepreneur spirit to ensure continuous competitive existence and sustainable SMEs. On this premise, Abeh (2017) argue that SMEs ought to create new things and induce originality into their business so as to ensure sustainable SMEs business vitality. However, due to lack of entrepreneur skills SMEs remain moribund. This explains the lack of ground-breaking, creative, innovative, self-motivated and effervescent entrepreneurial willpower needed to meticulously resolve emerging issues. Etuk *et al.*, (2014) corroborate that lack of entrepreneurial spirit inhibits SME operators from driving the business neither beyond the subsistent level nor to fight for the recovery of a dwindling venture.

Alabi, *et al.*, (2015) argues on the challenges of poor education and inadequate experience as major inhibitors of sustainable SMEs in Nigeria. In a similar vein, Micah *et al.*, (2017) explained that there is no educational restriction on starting/owning SMEs in Nigeria because SMEs are the most attainable means of livelihood for the common man irrespective of qualification. Nonetheless, lack of education and short experience of operators of SMEs in Nigeria, has proved to be one of the major challenges to their optimum performance. To the foregoing, Owenvibiugie and Igbinedion (2015) corroborates that actual formal knowledge acquisition is a sure manner to shape and/or improve the human talents, proficiency and aptitude necessary for the optimum performance of ventures in Nigeria. This is attainable

through human capacity building schemes for SMEs to inculcate the know-how in them by exposing them to information and knowledge that enables them do better in their businesses.

Besides funds and skills, SMEs also require tangible infrastructural essentialities; but it is quite obvious that the provision of adequate infrastructure (like good roads, electricity, medical services, industrial estates, and telecommunication) by government has remained utopian in Nigeria. Ebitu, Basil and Ufot (2016) affirmed this assertion by stating that in most cases, the above infrastructures only exist on the pages of newspapers and the airwaves, such that running a business in the country is that of ‘survival of the fittest’. Nearly all SME operating in Nigeria have one or more power generating plants as an alternative source of power supply.

The cost of obtaining, maintaining, sustaining and managing such generating plants are more often than not very expensive and most SMEs are financially incapacitated to fund the alternative means of electricity and ensure conducive operating environment for the sustenance of their businesses. Thus, infrastructural facilities in Nigeria is a case of incessant epileptic energy supply, inadequate water supply, unreliable telecommunication facilities, abysmal state of road networks, among others. Micah, *et al.*, (2017) affirms that this milieu over the years hindered the competitiveness and sustainability of enterprises in Nigeria; with prices of goods/services inflated.

Likewise the unfriendly business climate has continued to make mockery of Nigeria’s pursuit of sustainable SME sector. Besides the infrastructural challenges, fiscal and monetary policies regulating businesses in Nigeria obviously have had unpredictable, contradictory, inconsistent effects on SMEs. To the foregoing, Abeh (2017) avers that various administrations have been proffering good plans/policies but implementation and control has always been the problem, causing hardship for SMEs and home investors. Likewise, unlawful taxes/fees such as: business activity tax, commercial registration tax, trade premise tax,

sanitation levies, signpost fees, fee for labels/stickers, imposed on SMEs mostly by agencies and/or tax-force of state/local governments; have subdued SMEs in Nigeria to high cost of operation, poor productivity, poor sales and less competitiveness.

2.6.3 Contribution of Women Leadership Towards Sustainable SMEs

Professional Nigerian women today are found in virtually every entrepreneurial venture in our society. They are in Education, medicine, pharmaceuticals, engineering, law, transportation, technology and of course the traditional areas such as poultry, entrepreneurial farming, restaurant and hospitality services, fashion and beauty, to mention but a few. This situation is made possible because of their entrepreneur leadership prowess these women possess (Imhonopi *et al.*, 2016). More emphases have been drawn to the traits of strong responsiveness, care, and loyalty, willpower, resourceful and resilience which have contributed towards the evolution of renowned Nigerian female leaders and entrepreneurs who have made their mark in the sands of time (Qureshi *et al.*, 2021)

Female entrepreneur leaders have demonstrated the ability to build and maintain long-term relationships and networks, to communicate effectively, to organize efficiently, to be fiscally conservative, to be aware of the needs of their environment, and to promote sensitivity to cultural differences. In fact, there's no gainsaying the role of women in economic development especially in the small and medium scale enterprises; as women's enterprises are qualitatively different from men's. These are assertions backed by descriptive surveys (Afuegbu, 2019; Okafor and Alakende, 2019; Ezika, 2019; Taiwo *et al.*, 2016; Imhonopi *et al.*, 2016) indicating that women business owners create a clear culture of their own. It is observed that female enterprises pay attention to production of goods and delivery of services responding to traditionally unsatisfied needs. Suffice to say that women's feminist touch on

leadership gives a balance of modern and traditional satisfaction for a healthy and robust SME subsector in Nigeria.

Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala a PhD holder in Economics and an international development expert, successfully transformed the Nigerian SME subsector and the entire Nigeria economic platform when her leadership as the Minister of Finance (July, 2003-June, 2006), thrived in negotiating a debt relief package for Nigeria under the Obasanjo regime. It was with her leadership guidance that the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) was established in 2003 to stimulate, monitor, and coordinate the development of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria by initiating and articulating policies, programmes, instruments and support services for the development of the SME subsectors.

In 2013 the YouWIN scheme (Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria), which is one of the greatest landmarks in SME leadership and sustainable SMEs in Nigeria was attained through Okonjo-Iweala's leadership prowess. As one of its effort to develop entrepreneurship in the country YouWin signaled foreseeable hope for the growth and development of various business enterprises in Nigeria particularly SMEs (Young, 2017). The late Prof. Dora Nkem Akunyili (1954-2014) is still regarded as a good depiction of resourcefulness, responsiveness and strong willpower. She was the former Director of National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) between 2001 and 2008 and her leadership dexterity empowered a lot of entrepreneurial ventures in Nigeria to kick start and sustained SMEs. Her leadership virtues positively impacted on Nigeria's reindustrialization goals, earning her the African Virtuous and Entrepreneurial Women Merit Award in 2005, amongst other numerous leadership honors bestowed on her (Ezika, 2019; Imhonopi *et al.*, 2016).

Consequently, the African-mentality narrative that places the glass ceiling against women leadership seems to be breaking gradually as women continuously strive to make a

difference. A report from the World Bank Group (2018) has concluded that women have the entrepreneurial potential to massively create employment opportunities, generate income, reduce poverty and accelerate economic growth through SMEs leadership. For instance, women-owned SMEs in the US have doubled generating \$3 trillion with 23 million jobs created, with a 5 years projection of an additional 9.72 million jobs (World Bank Group Report, 2018).

This phenomenon is gradually taking shape in Nigeria, with more gender marginalization hurdles to overcome. A survey report by SMEDAN and National Bureau of Statistics (2013) revealed that SMEs owned and led by women generated over 26 million jobs across the nation. Women-owned businesses in wholesale and retail industry were able to generate approximately 63% of 14 million jobs in the industry; concluding that the woman-owned business in Nigeria has a great potential in spreading across other sectors, both formal and informal. It is therefore argued that Nigeria women leadership potentials provides the antidote for sustainable SMEs sector in Nigeria when provided insights into the right tools, techniques and frameworks for full functionality of the small and medium business enterprises.

2.6.4 Leadership Model For Sustainable SMEs

This study proposes the contingency-situational leadership model as a plausible solution for sustainable SMEs in Nigeria. Fred Edward Fiedler who was one of the leading 20th century researchers in industrial and organizational psychology, presented the contingency-situational theory of effective leadership in 1964 (Peters, 2019). The underlying concept of this model was that a single leadership style does not apply to all situations or organizations. Fiedler argues that effectiveness in leadership depends on situational factors (contingencies) and the environment in which the organization operates (Ghazzawi and Shougari, 2017).

Globalization exigencies have made business survival and growth even more complex than it has ever been, such that both emerging and existing SMEs in Nigeria are often confronted with external and internal uncertainties such as the market and economic environment dynamics, made worse by the underdeveloped infrastructural facilities, processes and inconsistency in government policies. Hence, successful leaders are those who are able to adapt their leadership style or approach to meet the demands of their unique situation.

This implies that time and occurrence is the fundamental determining factor towards being an effective leader, because different situations call for different measures at any given point in time. To this end, the action or strategies an SME leader adopts in order to breakeven, beat competition and thrive as a business venture, depends on a range of situational factors and the leader must be versatile with different leadership approaches. Effectively, the leader must be able to determine which leadership style to enforce for each given situation, and vary them in accordance with what is at stake.

Therefore, in as much as the growth and sustainability of SMEs demands for an authentic leader who is not afraid to show their vulnerability and feelings, who empathizes with employees and relate well with them to get the very best from them. However, sustaining SMEs in emergencies or such times like the recent Covid-19 pandemic would also require a resourceful and transformative leader whose creative mind-set is swift to handle problems innovatively and efficiently in order to meet exigencies. Sustainable SMEs would also require inclusive or participatory decision making through a democratic leadership approach that carries employees along.

Likewise to succeed, SME owners/managers have to lead by example by adopting the charismatic leadership approach that motivates employees to make personal sacrifices (when they see their leaders sacrificing their own personal interest) in order to achieve the overall organizational goals. Yes taking care of the social motivational needs of the employees such

as: interpersonal relationship, affiliation, recognition, delegation, and job satisfaction is quintessential for sustainable SMEs. However, employees are also motivated to do better through economic rewards and in some situations by punitive measures. Hence, transactional leadership model becomes a blueprint for employee productivity as it focuses on getting followers to accomplish assigned tasks and to achieve set goals in due time.

Therefore, the crux of the contingency-situational approach as the plausible model for sustainable SMEs in Nigeria is that different situations should be handled in different manner, since each situation has its own unique distinctiveness. There is no one best way or most effective way or pattern of leadership, rather there are different unique leadership ways which are appropriate in different circumstances, for different tasks and different individuals.

2.6.5 Charismatic Women Leadership for Sustainable SMEs

Charismatic women leaderships proposes to play a vital role in fostering SMEs sustainability due to the peculiar characteristics of both women leadership and charismatic leadership.

According to Zhang and Wei (2021), charismatic leaders are adept communicators who can effectively convey the mission, values, and objectives of the SME. They can articulate why sustainability matters and rally support for initiatives that promote social, environmental, and economic well-being (Zhang and Wei 2021). Also, Charismatic leaders are often perceived as trustworthy and genuine, which is essential for building strong relationships with customers, suppliers, investors, and other stakeholders. Trust is particularly important in sustainability initiatives, where transparency and accountability are paramount (Zhang and Wei 2021).

Furthermore, Charismatic women leaders often possess a clear and compelling vision for their businesses. This vision can inspire employees, stakeholders, and the broader community to commit to the organization's long-term sustainability goals (Qureshi *et al.*, 2021)

Subsequently, due to the sensitivity of the female gender, charismatic women leaders are often forward-thinking and focused on long-term success rather than short-term gains. They understand that sustainable practices may require upfront investment and effort but can yield significant benefits in terms of brand reputation, customer loyalty, and financial performance over time (Tran and Nguyen, 2022).

Overall, charismatic women leadership can serve as a driving force for sustainable SMEs by inspiring others, fostering collaboration, building trust and championing initiatives that create value for both the business and the society

2.7 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The emphasis of this study centres on establishing the nexus between the role of women leadership and sustainable SMEs in Nigeria vis-à-vis assessment of different models of leadership, so as to proffer a plausible model that would enhance sustainable SMEs in Nigeria, which is deemed the dependent variable of this study. Sustainable SMEs is manifested via the level of such variables as: effectiveness, efficiency, quality, timeliness and finance, as well as workplace environment which makeup the independent variables of the study. However, for these sustainability variables to culminate in sustainable SMEs, the leadership has to engender the component variables of professionalism, resourcefulness, resilience and clarity of thought for rational decision-making consistent with the company vision. There also need to be continuous communication across the business. Moreover, the enterprise operations have to be more inclusive and the leadership has to be responsive to followers needs to stimulate the entire workforce towards set goals. Below is an illustration of the conceptual framework:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on the ‘Human Capital Theory’ in line with the objectives of the study and the phenomena under investigation. The original idea of the Human Capital Theory can be traced as far back to Adam Smith 18th century work which perceived effective leadership and sustainability of economic growth “as a collaborative effort and the wealth of a nation”. Nonetheless, the use of the theory in the modern neoclassical economic literature is attributed to Jacob Mincer’s article “Investment in Human Capital and Personal Income Distribution” in the Journal of Political Economy published in 1958 and Gary Becker’s book titled “Human Capital” published in 1964; both of which became a standard reference for many years. Till date, the best-known application of the idea of human capital theory in social and management sciences is that of Jacob Mincer and Gary Becker of the Chicago School of Economics (Goldin, 2014).

Human capital theory is closely associated with the study of human resource management as found in the practice of public administration, business management and macroeconomics (Nwokwu, 2016). According to this theory, the principal source of productive capacity vis-à-vis effective management/leadership whether in an economy or organization, rests on the

capacity of the people. Hence, human capital has to do with the stock or collection of traits of all the knowledge, talents, creativity, skills, abilities, experience, intelligence, training, judgment, and wisdom possessed individually and collectively by individuals in a group (Simkovic, 2013). In other words, human capital is the social and personality attributes embodied in the ability and/or dexterity to perform labour so as to produce economic value.

The human capital according to Ojukuku and Sayujigbe (2015) are the total capacity of the people that represents a form of wealth which can be directed to accomplish the goals of the nation or state or a portion thereof. It implies how effectively an organization uses its 'people resources' as measured by creativity and innovation. Therefore, in contemporary world economies, SMEs performance and competitive advantage are derived more from what the operator knows and the human capital that permits the enterprise to use what it knows. Thus, human capital has been identified as one of the most critical agents of sustainable SMEs. Accordingly, this calls to action the role of effective leadership in harnessing human capital to enhance performance and facilitate SMEs sustainability; and according to Richard (2019), the man who successfully marshals his human collaborators to achieve particular ends is an effective leader, and a great leader is someone who can do so consistently in a wide variety of circumstances.

Specifically, the relevance of the theory to this study hinges on the fact that, human resource can be transformed into human capital with effective leadership inputs of professionalism, clarity of thought, responsiveness, care, and loyalty, willpower, resourcefulness, resilience, etc. Suffice to say that sustainable SMEs require strategic human resource management which makeup the role of SME leadership. The transformation of raw human resource into highly productive human capital is usually referred to as human capacity building. The human capital is what aids the functionality of any endeavour particularly Small and Medium

Enterprises (SMEs); thus, the SME operators or personnel are an integral part of the business success since they are the human resource that adds more value to the enterprise.

But for this to happen, the enterprise leadership has to appreciate them and motivate them to demonstrate their capacities and understand how they can contribute to the enterprise's performance and sustainability. When the leader succeeds, it will be because he has understood the two basic lessons that human beings that make-up organizational personnel are complex and are different. The leader must realise that human beings respond not only to the traditional carrot and stick used by the driver of a donkey; but moreso to ambition, patriotism, love of the good and the beautiful, boredom, self-doubt, and many more dimensions and patterns of thought and feeling that make them human.

He must also comprehend that the strength and importance of human interests are not the same for every worker, neither the same degree to which they can be satisfied in his job. There must be professionalism in behaviour and conducts, which the leader must encourage, and its success depends on level of communication. The one who leads effectively must be able to understand the enterprise goals/purposes (responsiveness) and put the enterprise human resources in a position to satisfy them (resourcefulness); he must be able to understand the implications of his own actions and be consistent and clear in his decisions (clarity of thought). Ezika (2019) avows that these unique roles are a human and social one and its achievement stems from his understanding of his fellow workers and the relationship of their individual goals to the group goals.

2.7.1 Literature Gaps

Definitely, entrepreneurship is progressively growing alongside oil industry in Nigeria with much emphasis placed on entrepreneurial development (Olowookere *et al.*, 2021). Meanwhile, the most tangible manifestation of entrepreneurship is a healthy and sustainable

SME sector. But the underperformance and early extinction of SMEs in Nigeria (like in other African countries) has become more prevalent, coming under intense academic scrutiny in business management and leadership studies (Kalu, 2022).

Hence in recent works, the factors inhibiting sustainable SMEs in Nigeria have widely become issues of contestation, with quite a lot of researchers exploring the leadership challenges of SMEs in Nigeria, while most scholars have painstakingly researched on the leadership styles in search of ideal approach to leadership success in business. However, only a handful of scholars have narrowed it down to women leadership (Olowookere *et al.*, 2021).

Gender issue is a subject that has and still generates heated arguments and is most noticeable when it bothers on issues of economic and social marginalization; constituting one of such economically and social weighty issue that cannot be trivialized (Kalu 2022). It is more discontending that not enough scholarly works has done justice to the plight of women leadership in Nigeria SMEs; considering that even with our huge physical population in Nigeria, educational, economic and social accomplishments, we are still an under-represented group. Therefore, in order to carve a niche for itself and close the identified literature gaps, this study scrutinized the role of women leadership among SMEs in Nigeria, while addressing a model for sustainable SMEs (Olowookere *et al.*, 2021).

There is no better time than now for a study of such economic, social and academic relevance. The Nigerian women have for decades engaged in survivalist activities due to little or no encouragement from the government and the organized private sectors, even when we have a lot to offer to improve SME leadership and bring to fruition the much desired national economic objectives of industrialization and sustainable development. Thus, this study not only bridges empirical gap in gender and entrepreneurial leadership, but also serves the useful purpose of proffering a workable leadership model that fits the Nigerian situation as a

solution for ameliorating constraints undermining the attainment of sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

2.8 RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

In congruence with the research questions and the objective of this study, the researcher formulated the following hypotheses to guide the analysis process on the role of women leadership among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria.

H₁: Leadership models significantly influence SMEs continuous competitive existence and sustainable SMEs in Nigerian.

H₂: There is a significant relationship between women leadership and sustainable SMEs in Nigerian.

2.9 CONCLUSION

A study of this magnitude certainly cannot be said to be exhaustive. Nonetheless, the study carried out a considerable review of relevant literature on the subject matter under study. It has to be emphasized that the review was guided by the objectives of the study and the research questions made in the preliminary part of the work, in congruence with the hypothetical assumptions of the study. Accordingly, the review was collapsed into themes and sections; capturing the general concept of leadership, models of leadership (authentic, situational, charismatic and full range leadership models), SME environment in Nigeria, leadership in SME, gender and entrepreneur leadership in Nigeria, factors that contribute towards women leadership in Nigeria SME, challenges facing women leadership in Nigeria SME, the concept of small and medium scale enterprises (SME), small and medium scale enterprises versus entrepreneurship, small and medium scale enterprises in Africa, small and

medium scale enterprises in Nigeria, the concept of sustainability and key variables of sustainable SME, constraints to sustainable SME in Nigeria, contribution of women leadership towards sustainable SME and leadership model for sustainable SME. Finally, the conceptual framework was outlined, including the gaps in literature, theoretical framework and research hypotheses.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter describes how the researcher systematically designed the study to ensure valid and reliable results that address the research aims and objectives. It discusses the methodological epistemologies as well as the processes that support research of this nature. The examination is based on the role of women leadership among SMEs in Nigeria, with a view towards preferring a plausible leadership model for sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

Accordingly, this aspect of the study presents the overarching research strategy that outlines the way the research is carried out. It also identifies specific methods applied in the study and the reasons behind each methodological approach. The methodology therefore involves a detailed outlay of the techniques used for the survey and the theoretical underpinnings or principles behind choosing certain methods in congruence with the research objectives (Igwenagu, 2016).

The chapter basically encompasses the survey design and how the researcher went about deciding what data to collect, who to collect it from, how to collect the data and how to analyse the data to arrive at an empirical standpoint. Hence, for the purpose of understanding the theoretical and empirical underpinnings of the study, the methodology chapter was collapsed into themes and sections. It is however important to note that delineating the survey into themes and sections as seen in this chapter, further puts into coherence the activities of the researcher for proper understanding of the essence of the research, as well as the appropriate procedures and research paradigm adopted.

The themes and sections appropriately capture the methodology framework, the research philosophy with a critical review of the positivism, interpretivism, pragmatism, and realism standpoint. The rationale for choosing the research paradigm was clearly underscored with the researcher further underlying the research approach, research design and research method utilized. In explicit and implicit terms, the research data requirements including the sources of data collection and sampling method, as well as the method of data analyses were clearly featured.

3.2 METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Research is an arrangement of both experience and reasoning and is deemed to be the most appropriate way of discovering ‘what is’ or better still validating or repudiating ‘what is perceived to be’ or ‘what ought to be’ (Igwenagu, 2016). Igwenagu (2016) avers that attaining the foregoing meaning, requires an appropriate methodology framework which ideally serves as a guide to the research and how it is conducted. Therefore, the methodology framework is the Procedural agenda applied in producing research data and analyses towards knowledge creation.

Opinions are rather unanimous that no single research method is inherently better than any other method, with various scholars calling for a combination of research methods in order to improve the quality of research. Overtime, researchers embraced an array of available techniques to make their choices of data gathering and analyses. Nevertheless, it is required that research techniques and design for conducting a research should be guided by the research questions, study aims and objectives (Bilau, *et al.*, 2017).

Taking into cognizance the target of utilising the most appropriate way of empirical discoveries to gather concrete evidences and make valid confirmations, this study embraced the mixed research method which is a combination of both quantitative and qualitative

approach. The term “mixed method” refers to an emergent methodology of research that advances the systematic integration or mixing of quantitative and qualitative data within a single investigation or sustained program of inquiry (Wisdom and Creswell, 2013).

Bamberger (2015) corroborates that there is rarely a single evaluation method or approach that can fully capture all of the complexities of what is actually factual and can be backed with evidence (i.e. research); particularly in the social sciences that deals with the complexities of human behaviour. On this note, Flowers (2009) contends that since social research involves so many choices, the chances that researchers’ values and preferences could influence the research process makes it difficult to ultimately achieve true objectivity.

Consequently, researchers must find ingenious ways to combine different evaluation frameworks, tools and techniques while attaining objectivity (Igwenagu, 2016). The mixed method therefore gives the needed edge and advantage over the routine use of variety of methods. Bilau, *et al.*, (2017) avow that what distinguishes mixed-method application is the intentional or planned use of diverse methods for particular mixed-method purposes using particular mixed-method designs of qualitative and quantitative recipes. Bamberger (2016) affirms that using a combination of qualitative and quantitative data (rather than in substitution of one for the other) improves evaluation by ensuring that the limitations of one type of data are balanced by the strengths of another. Also, it is the best approach to answer the research questions.

Research is enriched when qualitative approach is combined with quantitative approach to identify issues or obtain information on variables not obtained by quantitative surveys (vice versa). And as succinctly put by Jones and Mills (2018) this will ensure that understanding is improved by integrating different ways of knowing; likewise for verifying or rejecting results by using one to argument the other. In other words, the basic premise of this methodology is

that such mixture or integration permits a more complete and synergistic utilization of data, than separately using either quantitative or qualitative data collection or analysis.

Hence, the mixed research method of combining both quantitative and qualitative approach is regarded as the quintessential recipe to a holistic, well-balanced and objective research project (Bamberger, 2016). The foregoing assertion agrees with the submissions of Wisdom and Creswell (2013); Lincoln (2016); Mitra and Hamed (2017); Diabate, Sibiri and Yu (209); Vincent (2019); Edgar (2020); to mention but a few scholars who have combined the quantitative and qualitative approach in their examinations, exercised to facilitate the understanding of the impact of leadership and leadership models on the sustainability/growth of the Small Medium-scale Enterprises sector.

Accordingly, this research borders on leadership with the application of the mixed research method. But to further carve a niche for itself, this study clearly examine the role of women entrepreneurial leadership on the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria, with the view of proffering a model for sustainable SMEs. Moreover, there is a consensus on why women remain underrepresented in the entrepreneurship fields (Andrew and Jefferson, 2020). Hence, gender and entrepreneur leadership are mind boggling subjects in research, particularly when considering the best model for SMEs sustainability.

Suffice to say that a study of this nature requires that the most appropriate technique (mixed method) should be employed, with the outcomes critically assessed from every single imaginable point of view so as to ascertain validity and reliability of outcomes. The importance of the mixed research methodology framework within the context of this study is invaluable in that it guides the researcher in the development of research instruments to measure participants' perceptions with precision and validity.

Effectively, questionnaires have been argued to provide respondents opinion to the phenomenon being investigated, and questionnaires are analysed through statistical application which are commonly seen to be precise. Likewise, focus group discussion and/or interviews are regarded as one of the alternative approaches to analyzing participant's opinion which delivers additional validity to the research results.

Aside from directing a broad report regarding the SME phenomenon which enhances the industrialization and attainment of meaningful economic development for the Nigerian polity; the outcome of this research gives a decent mix of gender leadership and sustenance of a thriving and vibrant SME sector, surveyed from structured questionnaire and semi-structured interview. The interrogation covered issues of leadership in Nigeria SMEs, factors that contributes towards women leadership in Nigeria SMEs, contributions of women leadership towards sustainable SMEs in Nigeria, challenges facing women leadership and SMEs in Nigeria, as well as addressing a model adoptable for women leadership that can drive sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

3.3 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Through a period of time spanning years, so much emphasis has been placed on the underlying philosophy of a research, which is described as a belief or opinion of a researcher about the way in which data about a phenomenon should be gathered, analysed and used (Stanton, 2020). Research philosophy is often times used interchangeably with research paradigm and according to Thanh and Thanh (2015) research paradigm is an amalgam of belief about the nature of knowledge, the methodology of a study and criteria for validity. Simply put, research paradigms are conceptual and practical implements that are used to solve specific research problems; and each paradigm has a different perspective regarding the

axiology, ontology, epistemology, methodology, and rhetoric of research (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019).

In the same vein, research philosophy is defined as the set of beliefs concerning the nature of the reality being investigated to gather valid and concrete evidence (Bryman, 2012). In other words, research philosophy or paradigm is the underlying definition of the nature of knowledge sought for and/or obtained in research. Hence, research philosophy is deemed an integral aspect of research methodology with different research philosophical stance taken by scholars. May (2011) however argues that they are not completely different, but the choice(s) of research philosophy by researchers are defined by the type of knowledge being investigated in various research projects.

Flowers (2009) clearly notes that research philosophies can differ on the goals of research and on the best way that might be used to achieve these goals. The most recognised of them include ontology and epistemology; and then there is positivism, interpretivism and realism, but there is also the pragmatism research philosophy. These philosophical lines of reasoning/attack enable a researcher to make up his/her mind on which research approach to adopt and reasons why such approach should be adopted, in line with the research approach, research questions and objectives (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009).

Perhaps, no better diagrammatic illustration explains the nexus between a research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, research alternatives and timeline like the Saunders' research onion. The Saunders Research onion illustrates the stages involved in the development of a research work since the layers of the onion distinctly gives a more detailed description of the stages of a research process (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). The onion provides an effective progression through which a research methodology can be designed; and as clearly noted by Bryman (2012), its practicality and value lies in its adaptability for virtually all kinds of research methodology and more quintessential in a variety of contexts. Below is an

illustration of Saunders' research diagram which was analysed and related to the context of this research project:

Figure 2: Saunders' Research Onion (Saunders et al., 2009).

In congruence with the onion illustration, Saunders *et al.*, (2009) posits that application of the research onion begins with the outer layer and progresses to the inner layer. He argues that a research process is like an act of peeling off an onion layer by layer; and for the inner layer to be made manifest, the outer layer must be undone first. He further explains that when the onion is analysed from the outer layer, each layer of the onion describes a more detailed stage of the research process. Likewise, to successfully achieve a research goal the precise and factual steps must be taken accordingly, such that a researcher gets to one step first before proceeding to another.

Within the context of this study, using the research onion framework is to proceed from the outer layer (research philosophy) to the inner layer of the research onion (data collection). The research philosophy lays the groundwork for the research process and defines the method

adopted. Suffice to say that research philosophy sets up the idea of the research approach as well as the research strategy until the last step, representing the stage at which the data collection methodology is identified. Thus, there is no gainsaying the importance of the research onion to this study, as it provides a series of stages under which the different methods of data collection can be understood, with illustrated steps by which the methodological processes are described.

3.3.1 Positivism

Positivism paradigm is a research model under objectivism epistemology, described as a methodological philosophy in quantitative inquiry whereby researchers apply the methods of natural sciences to realise the study of social sciences (Ryami, 2015). Virtually all empirical studies are positivist in approach and according to Pham (2018), positivist long and rich historical tradition is traced to that of the physical and natural sciences. Its philosophical stance is characterised by the testing of hypothesis developed from existing theory through the measurement of observable social realities (as it applies to the social sciences).

The positivist position holds that the social world exists objectively and externally and that knowledge is valid only if it is based on observations of the external reality (Kanna, 2018). Positivism depicts that theoretical models can be developed that are generalisable and serve as universal laws, which can be effectively applied to explain cause and effect relationships, and utilized in predicting outcomes. In this respect, understanding of the phenomena in reality must be measured and supported by evidence; and in the process of investigating the phenomena, independent-dependent variables relationship will be discovered by causal inferences as the results of experimental designs (Johnson, 2014).

Typically, positivism is founded on the values of reason, truth and high quality standard of validity and reliability. Likewise, its emphasis is purely on facts gathered through direct

observation and experience and measured empirically using quantitative methods of surveys, experiments and statistical analysis (Idowu, 2016). The expectation is that social sciences must (as possible as it can be) seek to free themselves of value-judgments and of moral, political, and religion ideas that might fault their research (Hammersley, 2013).

Positivism therefore draws up research questions and conjectural statements (i.e. hypotheses) that can be evaluated and analysed with findings from empirical surveys or experiments. The philosophical stance is justified on the bases that science single-handedly sets the perimeters for human knowledge; and for this reason, positivism maintains the belief that science will in the end manage to solve all human problems (Pham, 2018).

Relating the positivist stance to the context of this study “the role of women leadership among SMEs in Nigeria” would mean that what truly happens in the Nigerian business or economic sector (in terms of gender and entrepreneur leadership) can only be discovered through categorisation and scientific measurement of the behaviour of people and social systems and that philological interpretation is truly a representative of the reality. This is probably why the application of the Positivism philosophy in studying social phenomenon upholds the standard that social scientific knowledge must always be subject to proof through empirical experimentation; thus, investigation should be based upon observations derived from sense-perceptions. Their argument is that data gathered from sense perceptions is the only possible data to form a foundation for knowledge and thought (Pham, 2018).

However, one of the greatest drawbacks of positivism in general, but particularly with respect to this study as a social and management sciences research, is the insistence upon methodological absoluteness. Idowu (2015) affirms that from its earliest phase of conception, positivists have insistently sought to use its scientific methods to explain every conceivable aspect of social phenomenon, striving to observe a phenomenon in its totality and consequently produce an absolute theory of knowledge about that phenomenon. But the

challenge is that social sciences investigations (like in this context) are confronted with the complexities of human behaviour which are ever changing and more often than not problematical.

Hence, by declaring valid, only those things which conform to its vigorous standards of investigation, embracing the positivist paradigm alone invariably strips social phenomenon of their perceived nature. Marsh, *et al.*, (2011) aver that this accounts for the major reason why other discoveries in the social sciences began to place greater emphasis upon the life of the individual and upon subjective experiences as vital factors in the constituency of societies. So with this shift in emphasis, the 'Interpretivist' approach evolved to gain far greater importance within the social sciences.

3.3.2 Interpretivism

Interpretivism is described as a branch of epistemology that focuses on the assessment of the differences between humans as social actors. In comparison to positivists who often accept only one correct answer for research, interpretivism is much more inclusive since it accepts manifold viewpoints of different individuals from different groups (Thanh and Thanh, 2015). From its inception, interpretivism is deeply rooted in the emphasis that methods useful in understanding knowledge related to human and social sciences, cannot attain the same usefulness as with the physical and natural sciences. Hammersly (2013) argues that this is because human beings interpret their world and accordingly act based on such interpretation even though it is not vice versa.

On the foregoing note, interpretivists' stance positions the relativist ontology point of view in which a single phenomenon may have multiple interpretations, rather than a sole truth that can be determined by a process of measurement. Adding more substance to the foregoing, Thanh and Thanh, (2015) explain that interpretivism disagrees with the existence of universal

standards for research; instead the proponents rather argue that standards guiding research are products of a particular group or beliefs. On this note, interpretive scholars do not go about their studies seeking answers in an inflexible or rigid ways but seek reality from subjects, usually from people who own their experiences and are of a particular group or social system. By searching for research answers through people, the interpretive researcher applies those experiences to construct and interpret his understanding from collated data (Idowu, 2016). Willis (2017) however notes that interpretive research is more subjective than objective, since its goal is to value subjectivity while debunking the idea that objective research on human behaviour is certain or even possible. This is perhaps the reason why interpretivist are said to be ‘anti-foundationalists’, on the premise that there is no particular right or correct path to knowledge or any singular method that automatically culminates in intellectual progress. Hence, interpretivists are rather criticised for disregarding the use of methods that offer objective or precise information; instead, they observe the world through a sequence of individual eyes and select participants who have their own interpretations of reality to comprehend the worldview (McQueen, 2012).

Suffice to say that interpretivists focus on interpreted meaning and this encourages the use of various methods so as to reflect different aspects of the issue or phenomenon; and according to interpretivist approach, it is important for the researcher as a social actor to appreciate differences between people (Idowu, 2016). Consequently, interpretivists are more inclined to adopt qualitative research methods such as case studies and ethnography; and as emphasised by Willis (2007), qualitative approaches habitually give plush reports that are necessary for interpretivists to fully understand contexts, with great efforts to avoid associated bias in studying people with their own interpretations.

Nevertheless, the diverse opinions in assessing and interpreting phenomena accord interpretivist researchers the advantage of not only describing objects, human or event; but to

also understand them deeply in a social context. Moreover, researchers can conduct their investigations in natural setting by applying key methodologies as grounded theory, case study or life history to gain the insider's insights of research's objects and gain more authentic information (Tuli, 2010). Furthermore, the key interpretivist method of interactive interview enables researchers to investigate deeply and incite insights to things that quantitative inquiry on its own may miss out on.

Regardless of its inclusiveness, the interpretivists seek to advance the deeper understanding and knowledge of phenomena within the complexity of the context rather than generalise obtained results to other people and other contexts. Thanh and Thanh (2015) describe this as a major weakness because of the lacuna in verifying validity and usefulness of research outcomes by means of scientific procedures. In concomitance with the emphasis of being subjective rather than objective, interpretivist research outcomes are unarguably affected by the researcher's own interpretation, belief system, thought process and manner of thinking or cultural preference leading to bias. Hence, the interpretivist paradigm by itself is devoid of flawlessness and grandeur research exploits.

3.3.3 Pragmatism

Pragmatism is a paradigm that declares to close the theoretical and empirical lacuna between the scientific method and structuralist orientation of older approaches (i.e. positivists and post-positivists) as well as the naturalistic methods (interpretivist) and the carefree orientation of newer approaches (Creswell, 2013). The paradigm is considered to be relatively new in comparison to other research philosophies; however, the pragmatism paradigm has evolved as a strong contending philosophical standpoint that researchers like us have come to value as an appropriate alternative (Creswell, 2013).

As a philosophical movement, pragmatism originated from the United States of America in the late 19th century. Creswell and Clark (2011) clearly emphasise that the philosophical movement of pragmatism arose as a result of the central accord of some group of scholars who unanimously rejected the traditional assumptions about the nature of reality, knowledge, and inquiry. They utterly rejected the notion that social science inquiry can gain insight of the reality solely by using a single scientific method. Hence, pragmatism is often associated with multiple-methods (otherwise known as the mixed research methods) where the emphasis is on the consequences of research and on the research questions instead of focusing on the methods.

Being a liberal research paradigm, pragmatism therefore proposes that researchers should use the philosophical and/or methodological approach that works best for the particular research problem that is being investigated, because no single method is best in absolute terms. Pragmatist approach is termed a deconstructive paradigm that circumvents the contentious issues of truth and reality and focuses instead on what works as the truth regarding the research questions under investigation (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). In that sense, pragmatism rejects a position between the two opposing viewpoints. Suffice to say that pragmatism paradigm rejects the choice associated with the paradigm wars.

Pragmatism therefore operates between the positivist research paradigm and the interpretivist research paradigm, such that it effectively combines the quantitative and qualitative mix-method of inquiry. According to Thompson (2018), Pragmatists researchers doubt the preposition that reality can ever be determined once and for all. They view reality as a normative concept and maintain that reality is what works. Therefore, they argue that the truth or knowledge claims cannot be totally alienated from contingent beliefs, habits, and experiences.

Truth from the perspective of pragmatist scholars is whatever proves itself good or what has withstood the test of individual use over time. Pragmatists generally agree that all knowledge in this world is socially constructed, but some versions of those social constructions match individuals' experiences more than others. Thus, the foremost sustenance of pragmatist paradigm is that knowledge and reality are based on beliefs and habits which are socially constructed (Yefimov 2014). Pragmatist scholars have offered their specific opinion in contestation that there is an objective reality that exists apart from human experience. They argue that this reality is dependent on the environment and can only be encountered through human experience (Morgan 2014).

Consequently, pragmatists have concluded (in retrospect to careful consideration of the effort and involvement) that the broader philosophical arguments or paradigm war can never be solved; because meaning is inseparable from human experience and human needs, all of which is dependent upon the environment. Hence, as a methodological approach to problem solving, pragmatism requires detection of a socially situated problem and adequate action to address the problem through the systematic combination of quantitative and qualitative data gathering and analyses (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019).

3.3.4 Realism

Like pragmatism, realism paradigm has evolved to become an increasingly useful universal view for some social scientists, but most significantly transforming the intellectuality of management research (Khanna, 2018). Realism in its real essence, gained certain features from both positivist and interpretivist paradigms. As a research paradigm, realism is simply an ontological stance, which holds that reality exists independently beyond what the researcher perceives it to be; presupposing that there is an external reality outside the researchers mind. This external reality is made up of abstract stuffs that are intuitive of

people's or group minds, but exist autonomously of any one person, although it is created by us.

Reality in this instance is said to be all that is 'out there' including forces, objects, entities, structures, situations, to mention but a few. Originally, the realism paradigm more or less argued against idealism which posits that objects of our experience and attributes as human beings are deemed not to possess any existence of reality outside of our mind. A person's perceptions are regarded as an opening to make clarity of that blurry/unclear external reality (Thompson, 2018; Khanna, 2018). In other words, realism holds that real structures exist independent of human consciousness, with our knowledge of reality socially created and therefore a result of social conditioning (Saunders, *et al.*, 2009).

It is also noteworthy that they are categories of researchers who are referred to as direct realists and on the other hand, those regarded as critical realists. The direct-realist inquiry (otherwise called naive empirical scientific realism) is the realism paradigm contending that 'what one sees is what the person gets', such that realists portray the world through personal human senses. This invariably implies that whatever is experienced by means of our senses accurately depicts what the world really is. Critical realism on the other hand argues that regardless of the experienced sensations and images of the real world by researchers, these sensations and images of the real world can be deceptive and most likely do not portray the real world (Thompson, 2018).

Nevertheless, realism in social and management sciences research is searching towards an understanding of the common reality of a social system in which many people operate inter-dependently. In other words, Realists researchers have confidence that there is a real world out there to discover; though the apprehension of the real external world is under probability. The foregoing notions hinge on the Realists acknowledgment of the differences between the

real world and their actual view of it; hence, realists attempt to construct various views of this reality based on those that are relative in time and place (Riege, 2013).

3.3.5 Chosen Research Paradigm Rationale

With regards to the research questions and objectives of this study, the pragmatic philosophy is observed to be the most suitable paradigm that would facilitate the successful fruition of a research of this nature. Pragmatism operates between the positivist and interpretivist research philosophies; and as a research philosophy, pragmatism core focus is on practical identification of solutions to address issues on ground by appropriately applying good mixtures of theories and frameworks (Guha and Chalty, 2015).

Pragmatic research philosophy focuses on the use of both qualitative and quantitative research methods. In the research parlance, a mix or blend of both quantitative and qualitative data in a study is termed the 'Mixed research method'. This method is typically an approach to a survey based on the collection and integration of both quantitative and qualitative data, in concomitance with the application of assorted designs that possibly embroil certain philosophical suppositions and theoretical frameworks.

Pragmatism research philosophy is best suited for this research as the middle point between interpretivism and positivism; also because the blend of both quantitative and qualitative research methods complements the strengths and makeup for the weaknesses of each method to serve a more useful purpose. The first three objectives are exploratory but more descriptive, as they aim to review leadership models for sustainable SMEs in Nigeria while examining the factors that contributes towards women leadership in Nigeria SMEs and their contributions towards sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

Considering that pragmatist research philosophy deals with facts which accept that there can be single or multiple realities that are open to empirical inquiry, it enabled more objectivity

for this study. Likewise, in social sciences, pragmatism holds that the choice of research philosophy is mostly determined by the research problem. Hence, as a problem-oriented philosophy that takes the view that the best research methods are those that help to most effectively answer the research question. This therefore enabled a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods used to evaluate different aspects of the research problem.

These objectives will be pursued using quantitative methods. However, the last three objectives are descriptive but more exploratory and they aim to examine the challenges facing women leadership and SMEs in Nigeria, evaluate the relationship between women leadership and sustainable SMEs in Nigeria and propose adoptable leadership model for women leadership that can drive a sustainable SME in Nigeria. Both quantitative and qualitative method will be employed to evaluate these objectives.

3.4 RESEARCH APPROACH

A research approach is referred to as a plan and procedure for research, specifying the steps to be observed from broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection, analysis and interpretation (Grover, 2015). The purpose of science and research is to discover truth which is said to be elusive but often attainable (Sanford, 2020). Hence, the two basic approach of truth discovery is the inductive and deductive approach. The evolving combination of qualitative and quantitative methods of inquiry has influenced many scientists to begin their research with an inductive study (which centres on developing a theory) and then integrating the inductive reasoning with the deductive approach to confirm or invalidate the conclusion drawn from the general to the specific (Streefkerk, 2019).

The overall decision hinges on choosing an approach that can be utilized the most to see the research to fruition. Groves (2015) avows that getting to the decision of which research approach to use, is guided by philosophical assumptions a given approach conveys to the

study; as well as the procedures of inquiry (i.e. the research designs); the elect approach it necessitates and specific research methods of data collection, analysis, and interpretation as guided by the design. Therefore, the criteria for choosing a research approach (like in this instance) take into cognizance the nature of the research problem being addressed and the research questions to be answered, as well as the purpose of the research which brings to the fore different concerns and arrangements of presenting results, invariably determining the selection of certain approach.

3.4.1 Inductive Approach

Inductive research approach also called inductive reasoning is an approach to research that predominantly uses detailed elucidations of raw data to derive concepts, themes, theories or a model through interpretations made from raw data by the researcher (Thomas, 2016). Johnson and Christensen (2017) further explain that inductive research approach allows the researcher to induce general conclusions from individual instances or observations; which implies that an inductive approach is the point at which the researcher begins with as few preconceptions as possible, allowing theory to emerge from the data, with the ultimate goal focused on exploring new phenomena or investigating previously researched phenomena from a different perspective.

Adding more clarifications to the foregoing notion of inductive approach, Thomas (2016) asserts that the primary purpose of the inductive approach is to allow research findings to emerge from the frequent, prevailing or weighty themes inherent in raw data devoid of restraints imposed by structured methodologies. Hence, inductive approach is categorized as a type of research approach that flows from the specific point of view, to the general interpretations. In other words, the central concern of inductive reasoning is the generation of new theory emerging from observed phenomenon.

Inductive approach is quintessential for analysing wide-ranging raw data to make a concise summary. Besides, it is widely held that research arguments based on experience or observations are best expressed inductively, because inductive analysis clearly establishes the nexus between variables and uphold how the connection gratify the research objectives (Gabriel, 2013). On the foregoing note, Eranny (2016) simply summed up inductive approach as a logical research process used to draw up conclusions, which presents a researcher with a starting point to enable the researcher narrow down tentative assumptions and reach an informed conclusion.

Accordingly, inductive approach is generally paired with qualitative research and the approach basically makes use of research questions to narrow the research scope. Inductive approach in an inquiry therefore requires a researcher to begin with a completely open mind without any preconceived ideas regarding what will be discovered (Thomas, 2016). Perhaps this is why the inductive approach is unanimously held as the archetypal approach intended for the generation of new theory emerging from undiluted data.

3.4.2 Deductive Approach

Deductive research approach or deductive reasoning is a method of inquiry concerned with putting forth a tentative or conjectural statements (hypotheses) based on an already existing theory, and then designing a research strategy to either confirm or refute the conjectured statements (i.e. test of hypotheses). Gabriel (2013) avows that deductive approach implies handling an inquiry from the particular or specific point of view, to the general point of view. This would imply that deductive approach begins with the general and ends with the specific, with a top-bottom strategy that flows from a theory down to hypotheses, and then builds on data that supports or contradict the theory. Hence, deductive approach usually begins with a hypothesis and its emphasis is generally on causality relationship among variables.

Causality herein refers to the idea that a given phenomenon (usually the independent variable be it an event, idea, behaviour or belief) will result in the occurrence of another (that is the dependent variable). In other words, causality is about cause and effect relationship of which researchers operating in the social scientist field would employ deductive approach to explore variables relationships. The application of deductive approach is typically in concomitance with qualitative research method that informs participants' observation and in-depth interview kind of data (Eranny, 2016).

As its research approach, this study employed both inductive and deductive line of attack, which engendered the effective combination of both qualitative and quantitative research methods. Both methods were adopted to serve the research purpose of examining the role of women leadership among small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria, so as to proffer a plausible model for sustainability. Therefore, the combination of both deductive and inductive approach facilitated the mixed method of quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis. Suffice to say that the inductive tactic enabled the researcher to utilize qualitative method of inquiry, built on open-ended interview discussions to gain in-depth information addressing the research questions in concrete details. On the other hand, the use of deductive tactic (which is best appropriate for quantitative data collation vis-à-vis questionnaire instruments) enabled the researcher to objectively explore the cause and effect relationship between women entrepreneur leadership and the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria.

3.5 RESEARCH DESIGN

Taking into consideration the research questions and objectives of this study, the study adopted the descriptive survey research design and sequential mixed method research design (Guha and Chalty, 2015). Descriptive survey research design according to Asika (2018)

avails a researcher the freedom to select and study a group of people, items or events considered to be representative of the census or total population. Sequential mixed method (QUAN-QUAL), is a research design whereby quantitative findings are explained and interpreted with the use of qualitative methods.

This mixed method is adopted because the results obtained from quantitative research may thread toward biased expressions as the items on the questionnaire are self-structured by the researcher and guided by existing literature. Also, since there is no extant consensus on a leadership model for SME sustainability in Nigeria, empirical data vis-à-vis quantitative method as deemed quintessential. However, applying quantitative method alone will not give whole access to the personal and emotional view of the participants about factors that impacts on SME sustainability vis-à-vis their high mortality susceptibility. Effectively, qualitative method (using semi-structured interview) was added to augment quantitative data and facilitate in-depth access of relevant information from participants.

3.5.1 Research Method: Quantitative

Quantitative research is a method of enquiry that deals with numbers and uses specific statistical techniques to explain data, make predictions, test causal relationships, and generalize results to wider populations (Idowu, 2016). Apuke (2017) describes quantitative research methods as the process of explaining an issue or phenomenon by means of gathering data in numerical form and analyzing them with the aid of mathematical methods, in particular statistics. In other words, quantitative research is the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data with great emphasis on procedures and statistical measures of validity.

Quantitative research method is deductive in nature and adopts such strategies of inquiry as experiments and surveys, and collect data on predetermined instruments that yield statistical

data. Bryman (2004) clearly notes that because quantitative research is deductive, researchers deal directly with operationalisation, prediction, and testing of conjectural postulations made to obtain valid information. Erynna (2016) explained that the quantitative method and its associated deductive reasoning adopts an objective approach and stresses more on breadth (quantity) rather than depth (profundity) of data and is aimed at generalisation.

One of the most utilized instruments of quantitative research method is the questionnaire, which is a way of collecting information about a range of phenomena (Guha and Chalty, 2015). Thus, in quantitative research, variables (both the independent and dependent variables) are very essential because variables are the phenomena that are classified and quantified. Harney (2016) however notes that collection of quantitative data often times requires the use of operational definitions that translate abstract concepts into observable and quantifiable measures.

The foregoing assertion places much significance on the issue of coding and encoding of meaning in questionnaire items for extraction of data that can be measured. Therefore with the application of quantitative method, such research designs as descriptive survey, correlational and experimental designs, as well as causal-comparative or ex-post-facto design can be used to formerly test hypotheses and make predictions using statistical tools (Apuke, 2017). Likewise, data obtained can be generalized to broad population based on the sampling method adopted (Grover, 2015).

3.5.2 Research Method: Qualitative

Qualitative research method by contrast is referred to as the direct opposite of quantitative research method. This method avoids numbers; therefore, it is non-numerical and deals with the interpretation of social realities. Idowu (2016) corroborates that the most important features of qualitative research is its express commitment to observing social phenomena

such as events, actions, norms, and values from the perspective of the people being studied. The goal of qualitative research according to Creswell (2013) is to rely as much as possible on the participants' views of the situation being studied.

Creswell (2013) further explains that qualitative research method focuses on the construction of subjective understandings by individuals and the interpretations of experiences to form coherent meanings. These meanings are the heart and core value for the qualitative research in terms of promoting unique narratives on situations from the individuals experiencing them. This justifies the qualitative method axiom that “He who wears the shoe knows where it pinches most”.

Shone (2015) avers that qualitative researchers focus on generalized, open-ended questions to harvest in-depth information, based on the subjective construction of meanings for the subject under investigation. These constructed meanings as succinctly put by Creswell (2013) are typically generated by focus group discussions as well as interview interactions with other individuals. This approach obviously involves the researchers' preparedness to empathise with participants being studied; thus, it is commonly associated with inductive reasoning as qualitative research also hinges on the capacity of the researcher to penetrate the frames of meaning with which they operate.

The qualitative methodology lays emphasis on depth rather than breadth and the end is not aimed at generalisation. Expanding on the foregoing Creswell (2009) avers that qualitative methodology deals with how people understand their experiences. Qualitative methodology therefore aims to explore meaning and is very fitting for the investigation of issues which, for ethical, practical or epistemological reasons, are difficult to measure. Moreover, qualitative research are often found to be descriptive and termed a soft research, in contrast to the rigorous approach which is often associated with quantitative studies (Idowu, 2016).

3.5.3 Research Method: Mixed

Mixed research methods is an enquiry approach in which the investigator or researcher collects and analyses data, integrates the findings and draws inferences using both qualitative and quantitative methods in a single study (Doyle, Brady and Byrne, 2009).

Reasons abound as the justification for combining quantitative and qualitative mixed-research methods. Opinions (Greene, *et al.*, 1989; Bryman, 2006; Doyle *et al.*, 2009; Mertens and Biber, 2012;) are unanimous that the main rationales for undertaking a mixed methods are to facilitate Triangulation, completeness, benefit of offsetting weaknesses, objectivity in answering different questions, ability to illustrate data vividly and appropriately develop and test hypotheses.

Triangulation is a surveyors' measurement tool borrowed as a concept by social scientists, to argue for its use in data validation process, particularly in assessing the veracity (accuracy and reliability) of social science research results. Mertens and Biber (2012) aver that a major benefit of mixed research methods is the benefit of triangulation, as this allows for greater validity and reliability in a study by seeking corroboration between quantitative and qualitative data. Likewise, using a combination of quantitative and qualitative research methods engenders research completeness, by creating a more complete and comprehensive picture of the phenomenon or phenomena under study.

Opinions are rather undivided that the use of mixed research methods enables a researcher to build on the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative methods, thereby offsetting loopholes. In other words, it allows for the limitations of each approach to be neutralised while strong suit are harnessed to build a stronger and more accurate inferences (Bryman, 2006). Mertens and Biber (2012) were emphatic in pointing out that mixed research methods facilitates answering of different questions more objectively. This is because the research questions that cannot be answered by quantitative or qualitative methods single-handedly, is

handled better with a combination of both methods. Thus, mixed methods engender the benefit of gamut tools to meet the aims and objectives of a study, and this is particularly useful when unusual discoveries emerge.

Needless to say that each method backup the other since findings from a quantitative survey (like questionnaire) can be qualitatively followed up and explained by conducting interviews or focus group discussions, with a sample of the study population, so as to gain better understanding of the findings obtained (Doyle *et al.*, 2009). It is even more beneficial to mix both methods because using a qualitative research method to illustrate quantitative findings can help paint a better picture of the phenomenon under investigation. Furthermore, a qualitative aspect of a study can be effectively utilised to develop hypotheses which would be tested in a follow-up quantitative phase (Creswell, 2013).

3.6 REQUIREMENTS OF DATA

In the process of carrying out an inquiry, researchers mainly rely on two categories of data viz: primary data which they generate themselves and secondary data which refers to existing data already provided by other researchers or institutions/firms for knowledge development and further studies. Nonetheless, a researcher could singularly make use of either (primary or secondary) of the categories of data or combine both categories just like it was combined during the course of this research. This research therefore employed both primary and secondary data type, a combination of which conclusively informed which leadership model is adoptable for women leadership to drive sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

Primary data: Primary data simply refers to data that collected from first-hand-experience, that is, data collected directly from the field. Perhaps, it is its originality that gained primary data the definition of ‘rawness’ since it is data that has not been published up until the time of

collection; but then it is deemed more reliable, authentic and objective (Kabir, 2016). Suffice to say that when research data is said to be primary, it implies that it has not been changed or tempered with by any being; for this reason, its validity scales higher than secondary data. Expanding more on the foregoing, Driscoll (2017) argues that researchers no doubt carry out their investigation without secondary data. However, a researcher can hardly make-do without primary data; premised on the experience that research conducted only with secondary data is least reliable and may have biases since secondary data has already been manipulated by human beings.

Nevertheless, primary data sources are more often limited and in certain cases, it becomes difficult to source data primarily. Kabir (2016) attributed the limitation to scarcity of population and/or recalcitrant attitude of participants. Sources of primary data are of qualitative and quantitative nature; ranging from experiments, questionnaire, observations and diaries to interviews, focus group discussions, to mention but a few. Experiments take place in natural setting and the researcher has to keep control over the influence of any extraneous variable on the results. Moreover, Experimentations are more suitable for natural and physical sciences studies such as: medicine, industrial physics studies, psychological studies, nutrition studies and other scientific enquiries (Ajayi, 2018).

A questionnaire is a survey tool most commonly used in the social and management sciences. Questionnaires comprises of a list of open-ended or close-ended questions with the answers provided by the respondents. Questionnaires can be conducted via telephone, mail and even live in a public or private area. In a similar vein, observations are done in natural or artificial setting such that participants can either be made aware that they are being observed or not. Interviews and focus group discussion are more direct and impactful tools of data collection compared to the questionnaire, because participants are channelled to give an in-depth opinion of phenomena being investigated (Shone, 2015; Ajayi, 2018).

Secondary data: Secondary data are data that have been collected by someone else for another primary purpose, but furthers an investigation by enabling the researcher to learn more of what is already known and what remains to be learned about a topic in a specified area of interest (Nicholson and Bennett, 2008). Nonetheless, Johnston (2014) succinctly notes that the utilization of this existing secondary data provides a feasible option for researchers who may be inhibited by time and resources constraints. He further argues that being secondary data takes away nothing from their usefulness and credibility, because secondary data are also empirical sourced and involves the same basic research principles/values as data sourced primarily.

Nicholson and Bennett (2018) argues that secondary data is essential, since it is impossible to conduct a new survey that can adequately capture past change and/or developments. For instance, literature review is built on secondary data which is collected by someone else for some other purpose, but being utilized by the researcher for another purpose; thus more depth is covered because much of the background work needed has already been carried out. Avail to say that secondary data is beneficial in research because it is unmanageable to conduct a new survey that can adequately capture past change/developments devoid of secondary data. Sources of secondary data include: records, books, data archives, published journals, internet articles, etc.

3.6.1 Sampling Method

Sampling methods refer to techniques for sampling which accords researchers the opportunity to select a subset of a population (sample) to gather data from and infer information about the entire population based on results of the subset, without having to investigate every individual that make-up the entire population (Elder, 2019; Taherdoost, 2017). Diherty (2019) avows that the selection of a sample size in the first instance is because it is not feasible in most studies that a researcher would be able to collect data from the entire

population; thereby culminating in a need to select a sample through the application of sampling technique(s) to reduce the number of cases.

Picking a subset of participants to investigate from the entire cases or population of a study is generally referred to as sampling which can be effectively utilised to draw inferences about a population or to make generalization in relation to existing theory, depending on the choice of sampling technique. Taherdoost (2017) however notes that prior to picking a sample and deciding on a given sampling technique, the population of the study must be determined from thereon the researcher can proceed with the sampling.

Accordingly, the population for this study is the SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. This location was chosen because Lagos State is the commercial capital of Nigeria and it is mainly where most businesses and entrepreneurial ventures in the country take place. There is a significant growth of SMEs in the state. According to the NBS (2013), there are about 11663 SMEs in Lagos State alone (Adebiyi, Banjo & Regin, 2017) and since the purpose of this study is to identify the major impediments to SME sustainability, targeting this population is expedient.

Therefore, both the quantitative and qualitative exercises were conducted using Lagos State, Nigeria. The study carried out a three-stage research with the first two stages being quantitative and the last one being qualitative, the sample size for the two quantitative stages will be the same while that of the qualitative stage will be different. In the quantitative stage, sampling size was calculated using the Raosoft sample calculator with confidence level of 95% and 5% margin of error. According to this calculator, the sample size for the quantitative stage is 372 as illustrated in the figure hereunder:

Raosoft®

What margin of error can you accept? <small>5% is a common choice</small>	<input type="text" value="5"/> %
What confidence level do you need? <small>Typical choices are 90%, 95%, or 99%</small>	<input type="text" value="95"/> %
What is the population size? <small>If you don't know, use 20000</small>	<input type="text" value="11663"/>
What is the response distribution? <small>Leave this as 50%</small>	<input type="text" value="50"/> %
Your recommended sample size is	372

Figure 3: Sample Size Calculator Used

Basically, there are two grouped categories of sampling methods known as the probability sampling methods and the nonprobability sampling methods. While probability sampling methods are employed where the researcher wants to make inferences about the population by ensuring that every item in the population has an equal chance of being selected; nonprobability sampling methods tend to focus on small samples and are intended to examine a real life phenomenon, rather than make statistical inferences in relation to the wider population (Etikan and Bala, 2017; Elder, 2019).

For the purpose of this study, the non-probability convenience sampling method was adopted. Convenience sampling is a type of nonprobability sampling in which participants are investigated as the sample because they are readily and easily available; thereby making them convenient sources of data for researchers (Taherdoost, 2017). Thus with nonprobability convenience sampling method, subjective approach is used to decide which elements should be included in the sample.

Adopting the nonprobability convenience sampling method enabled this study to overcome the accessibility and availability limitations associated with gathering data from a large and

heterogeneous population such as Nigeria, with 36 States (including the Federal Capital Territory Abuja) and 774 Local Government Areas. Thus, the nonprobability convenience sampling method is more suitable given the circumstances; and very beneficial for the researcher to easily gather data from SMEs in Lagos State instead of travelling across the entire country. To this end, the non-probability convenience sampling was employed to study the approximated 11663 SMEs in Lagos State (Abeh, 2017).

However, in the qualitative stage, there was no enforcement of specific rules when forming the sample size, as it all depends on the amount of time allocated, objective of the study as well as the resource available. Convenience sampling was used to select 17 participants for the interview. Face-to-face semi-structured focus group discussion was conducted with the use of open-ended questions.

3.6.2 Data Collection: Primary And Secondary

Data collection is the process of gathering and measuring information on variables of interest, in an established systematic fashion that enables one to answer stated research questions, test hypotheses, and evaluate outcomes (Kabir, 2016). The goal for all data collection is to capture quality evidence that then translates to rich data analysis and allows the building of a convincing and credible answer to questions that have been posed. Regardless of the field of study or preference for defining data (whether quantitative or qualitative), accurate data collection is essential to maintaining the integrity of research.

Data collection is one of the most important stages in conducting a research, to which Datta (2018) clearly emphasise that, the selection of appropriate data collection instruments (existing, modified, or newly developed) and clearly delineated instructions for their correct use reduce the likelihood of errors occurring in research. Hence the argument that researchers can have the best research design in the world but if the right choices are not made in

collecting the required data, the research will not successfully come to fruition. To this end, this study combined the primary and secondary sources of data collection to build a formidable study.

As there are two stages in the primary data collection in this study, namely, qualitative and quantitative stages. The quantitative stage employed the use of self-structured questionnaire so as to be able to reach a large number of participants. The method is employed as it is cost effective and it helps to simplify the disclosure of sensitive matters, it also affords the participants flexibility as they are able to complete at their own time. The structured questionnaires were designed using Likert 5-point rating scale of Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D), Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD), Agree (A) and Strongly Agree (SA); with each option rated on a scale of 1-5 respectively in English Language. The questionnaires were administered with the use of the survey website www.surveymonkey.com and sent through email to the owners and managers of SMEs in Lagos State. As seen in the sample size calculated above (Figure 3), 372 questionnaires were sent out with 231 respondents resulting in a response rate of 62%.

Also, the qualitative aspect of this study made use of semi-structured interview method, with open-ended questions that enabled the researcher to investigate and obtain more insightful and/or in-depth information from participants. This method is important as it not only helps to obtain detailed information from individuals about personal opinions, but particularly gave them the freewill to better explore and explain their perceptions or experiences.

Secondary data included other external data obtained from academic journals, industry publication, government publication, articles and books. The external secondary data were collected from reliable sources such as: Association of Business School Journals, Science

Direct and so on. Therefore, secondary data were collected with techniques that enable the researcher to extract the useful information from the data sources and literature.

3.7 DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

The primary purpose of analysing data is to obtain usable and useful information to achieve set research objectives (Wang, 2014). Effectively, this study is built on the pragmatic standpoint which embraces the mixed research method. Thus, quantitative and qualitative methodological analyses are combined to examine collated data. It is important to note that the application of quantitative analysis (using questionnaires) enabled the testing of the study theoretical foundation through the testing of hypotheses. Complementarily, qualitative method of analysis enabled testing of the open-ended interview questions to address the research questions. To this end, the quantitative data from this study were analysed using SPSS (statistical package for social science) while the qualitative data from the interview were examined through thematic analysis using NVIVO software.

3.7.1 Quantitative Data Analysis Technique

Quantitative data for this study comprised of data got from the research questionnaire, and to analyse the data gathered from quantitative survey, the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) was used. The quantitative data obtained from the survey were presented using charts and frequency distribution tables with their corresponding percentages. The ordinal regression analysis test was adopted to test causality relationship in line with the hypotheses formulated for the study. The aim was to test the inter-variable correlation as well as describe the strength and direction of relationship between variables.

Hence, in accordance to the correlational analysis that examined the relationship between variables, a regression analysis was added to substantiate the significance of the relationship

between the variables and to find out the independent variable that is more likely to display a highest significant level of impact in the value of the dependent variable. Consequently, the following are steps carried out in the analysis of the quantitative data collected.

- i. Descriptive analysis: Descriptive statistics are a set of techniques used to summarize and describe the characteristics of a dataset. These statistics provide a concise overview of the data, helping to identify patterns, trends, and key features. This is required so as to assess common features in the data collected. Example of descriptive analysis; mean, median, standard deviation, variance.
- ii. Reliability test: In SPSS, you can conduct reliability testing using the "Reliability Analysis" procedure. This procedure calculates various measures of internal consistency reliability, such as Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which assesses how well a set of items measures a single construct and to ensure that the data collected is reliable and that all items in the questionnaire can assess the research variables without bias.
- iii. Regression analysis: Regression analysis in SPSS allows for the examination of the relationship between the independent variables (predictors) and a dependent variable (outcome). In the case, the ordinal regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between the factors and sustainability of SMEs.
- iv. Hypothesis as well as statistical tests, and
- v. Interpretation of results from the tests carried out.

3.7.2 Qualitative Data Analysis Technique

Qualitative data for this study were gathered using semi-structured interview based on open-ended questions. The semi-structured interview was added to close the loopholes of questionnaire quantitative data through the provision of a more detail personal experiences

and opinions from the participants. Through convenience sampling, 17 participants were chosen from the population upon whom face-to-face semi-structured interview were administered with the use of open-ended questions. Accordingly, the six stages involved in the qualitative data analysis are as follows;

- i. Familiarisation with data, whereby the verbal data obtained will be transcribed.
- ii. Generating initial codes, whereby codes are generated for ideas to look interesting.
- iii. Searching for themes, themes will be generated from the list of codes generated.
- iv. Reviewing themes, themes will be reviewed and refined.
- v. Defining and naming themes, the themes will be defined and processed for analysis.
- vi. Producing reports, final analysis of the data.

3.8 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Researchers are professionals and are required to keep to the right behaviour in conducting and publicising their research findings; thereby necessitating that the exercise of all research activities and research processes should follow a sound and moral manner, founded on laid down ethical principles (Akaranga and Makau, 2016). There are quite a number of valid reasons why ethical norms in research is very crucial such as: prohibitions against fabrication, falsification or misrepresentation of research data aimed at promoting truth and avoiding errors. There are also ethical standards that promote the values vital for collaborative work such as: authorship, copyright, and data sharing policies to guide against plagiarism, foster trust, accountability, mutual respect, and fairness. Perhaps most emphasised is the respect of the rights of the participants in terms of their compliance or cooperation, privacy and safety (Wang, 2014; Akaranga and Makau, 2016; Etikan and Bala, 2017).

In accordance with the laid down ethical principles of conducting and transcribing research in the social and management sciences, required measures in this study were taken in ensuring that the researcher observed due protocol in the execution of the research. Ethical authorization was got by applying to the ethical committee to seek their approval. The approval was sought through the project supervisor(s) who inspected the research topic and the methodology of the project; particularly as it concerns the content of the questionnaire and interview, including the outlined sampling procedure for generation of data.

Informed consent was sought for voluntariness in participation; likewise the clear and unambiguous disclosure of relevant information to ensure proper understanding of information before any sort of participation. Hence, for timely mitigation against lack of confidence and any form of misunderstanding, participants were appropriately guided on the aim and objectives of the research. Written papers succinctly describing the research aim and objectives were issued to some respondents via face-to-face contacts and through electronic mail for some other respondents. Participants were equally allowed a reasonable time interval to acquaint themselves with the necessary information provided, with opportunities given to them to seek further clarification about the questionnaire items as well as the research objectives and processes.

All the participants were aptly and vividly informed that they could withdraw from the research at any time without any consequences whatsoever to the individuals. The participants were affirmed and included only after verbal explanation and after they had voluntarily signed the written consent and information statements prior to the research. Participation by respondents was entirely voluntary, devoid of monetary compensation for participation, and the assurance that all information resulting from the study will be treated with strict confidentiality was strictly adhered to by the researcher. Thus, the avoidance of name inclusion in the questionnaire and for the interviews was a major priority, except for

those who chose to be recognized. Accordingly, the researcher avoided any form of indicting persuasive approach and/or power relations approach towards pressurizing or influencing participants in a bid to collect the written agreements.

3.9 CHALLENGES/LIMITATIONS IN DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Researchers are normally confronted with uncontrollable constraints that directly or indirectly influence the conduct of the research vis-à-vis the research design or methodology and might as well influence the research outcome. It is therefore required that those constraints (otherwise referred to as the limitations of research) be made known to aid the validity and reliability of the research. The limitations could be those resulting from the methodology and/or those resulting from issues with the researcher. Methodological limitations are issues with study population and sampling, errors in statistical measurements, lack of extant research studies relevant to the ensuing study, issues with data collection instruments/techniques. On the other hand, limitations issues from the researcher range from data inaccessibility, to time and financial constraints, cultural bias and other personal issues (Theodore, 2018).

Methodologically, this study was confronted with scope constraints since the researcher could not cover all the 36 federating states of Nigeria (including the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja) due to the researchers' constraints of time and financial dearth. The study was also encumbered by some of respondents not willing to cooperate with the researcher; perhaps due to lack of trust and/or fear of compromised anonymity.

The researcher persistently made resilient effort to convince officials and other participants on the study adherence to anonymity as well as the confidentiality and strict use of all data for research. To carve a niche for itself by meeting a realistic and practicable data needs, the research population was constricted to SMEs in Lagos State which is the country's centre of

commerce. Such and other measures including use of vernacular was utilized in explanation for few of the uninformed field respondents, so as to enable the researcher achieve a significant success in the course of the research.

3.10 CONCLUSION

This chapter gave a thorough account of the research philosophy, research design and approach, methodology and techniques of data collection employed to ensure the thesis was conducted and transcribed accordingly. The study embraced the pragmatic research paradigm, with a blend of qualitative and quantitative methods (mixed methods) based on an inductive and deductive analysis for the primary data viz: structured questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, used to complement other secondary sources. Non-Probability-Convenience sampling technique was adopted to attain a realistic research range. Meanwhile for the method of data analysis, the quantifiable data of the study were examined using descriptive and correlational statistics with the aid of SPSS (statistical package for social science); while the qualitative data from the interview were examined using content analysis.

CHAPTER 4

4.0 RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Previous studies suggested that the Nigerian SMEs within the last decade have been predominated by male leadership (Uchebulam, Akinyele and Ibidunni, 2015). This could be as a result of a number of societal factors within the African/ Nigerian cultural biases (Oyinade, Daramola and Lamidi, 2013). Also studies from (Ighomereho *et al.*, 2013), suggested that most SMEs in Nigerian struggled to thrive due to gender biases when getting funding and other form of capital required for effective running of businesses.

The findings from this current study looked to explore the impact of female leadership on SMEs and which leadership model is most suitable for female leaders. As earlier discussed in the methodology, a mixed method is employed to carry out the study and the findings will be presented in two sections (quantitative and qualitative).

4.2 QUANTITATIVE DATA PRESENTATION

The qualitative analysis was carried out by first assessing the proportion in the number of respondents who are males and females. It was also critical to assess the difference in ages of respondents and the impact these groups have on overall sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. This chapter also looked at leadership styles, components, and leadership's impact on SMEs. As a result, the 5- point rating Likert Scale Questionnaire was used to measure these dimensions.

4.2.1 Respondent Demographics

A total number of 231 respondents' data was analysed using SPSS, to determine the percentage that were either males or females. Figure 4. revealed that female respondents make up 62% while male respondents make up 38% of the survey.

Figure 4: The difference in percentage of women and men involved in the quantitative survey.

Age * Gender Crosstabulation				
Count				
		Gender		Total
Age Group	Respondents age distribution (years)	Female	Male	
A	18-25	21	7	28
B	26-33	72	39	111
C	34-40	23	20	43
D	41-47	11	12	23
E	48 & above	17	9	26
Total		144	87	231
% within Age		62.30%	37.70%	100.00%

Table 1: Age groups distribution in relation to gender

4.2.2 Respondent's Experience

Along with educational qualifications, business experience was taken into account. As a result, Table 2 investigates respondents' experience in their chosen field as well as their level of education. It is worth noting that this study does not take into account respondents' level of formal education in the field of their enterprise, but rather their overall education, which could have been in a field other than their business.

A total of 115 respondents have less than 5 years of business experience, two have WASSCE/GCE/SSCE, 77 have ND/NCE, 30 have HND/BSc, two have MScs, and four have PhDs. 54 respondents have 6-10 years of enterprise experience, four of whom have WASSCE/GCE/SSCE, 25 have ND/NCE, 23 have HND/BSc, and one has MSc and one has PhD. 28 respondents have 10-15 years of business experience, with one having

WASSCE/GCE/SSCE, 17 having ND/NCE, 10 having HND/BSc, and none having MSc or PhD. 14 respondents have 16-20 years of business experience, with two holding WASSCE/GCE/SSCE, five holding ND/NCE, four holding HND/BSc, none holding MSc, and three holding PhD. Twenty respondents have 21 years of business experience or more, with none having WASSCE/GCE/SSCE, 11 having ND/NCE, 9 having HND/BSc, none having MSc, and none having PhD (Table 2). Over all, Table 2. revealed that almost 50% (115) of our respondents have below 5 years working experience with an SME and 57% (77 out of 115) of that population are ND/NCE holders.

Count						
Enterprise Experience	Qualifications considered					Total
	WASSCE/GCE/SSCE	ND/NCE	HND/BSc	MSc	PhD	
5 years and below	2	77	30	2	4	115
6-10 years	4	25	23	1	1	54
11-15 years	1	17	10	0	0	28
16 – 20 years	2	5	4	0	3	14
21 years and above	0	11	9	0	0	20
Total	9	135	76	3	8	231

Table 2: Enterprise Experience and Educational Qualification Crosstabulation

4.2.3. The Impediments To SMEs Sustainability In Nigeria

The different measures of impediments to SME sustainability are transformed and computed into different categories highlighted below.

1. Financial Hurdle

Descriptive analysis was carried out to assess the mean and standard deviation of the data in relation to financial hurdle.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Financial_hurdle_SMEs	231	0	4	3.24	.716
stifled by inadequate working capital	231	0	4	3.07	.815
SME financially incapable_employ_professionals	231	0	4	3.02	.823
Valid N (listwise)	231				

Table 3: Mean and Standard deviation of financial hurdle

According to Addison and Jenkins (2023), a standard deviation that is below 2 SD is low and it presents values that are normally distributed. In Table 3, the Standard deviation for the variable financial hurdle is a normal deviation and this is because the SD value is low.

2. Lack of infrastructural facilities

Descriptive analysis was carried out to assess the mean and standard deviation of the data in relation to infrastructural facilities.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Infras_facilities_impediment_to_SMEs	231	0	4	3.27	.844
indigenously made goods_uncompetitive_costs of production.	231	0	4	3.03	.874
Valid N (listwise)	231				

Table 4: Mean and Standard deviation of lack of infrastructural facilities

In Table 4, the Standard deviation for the variable infrastructural facilities is a normal deviation and this is because the SD value is low.

3. Poor Management

Descriptive analysis was carried out to assess the mean and standard deviation of the data in relation to poor management

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Poor_management_incompetence_under_utilization_resources	231	0	4	3.16	.803
evolutionary_stage_low IT communication skills .	231	0	4	2.95	.846
Valid N (listwise)	231				

Table 5: Mean and Standard deviation of poor management

In Table 5, the Standard deviation for the variable poor management is a normal deviation and this is because the SD value is low.

4. Gender Discrimination

Descriptive analysis was carried out to assess the mean and standard deviation of the data in relation to gender discrimination.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gender_discrimination	231	0	4	2.23	1.152
Women_not_afforded_same_opportunities_male	231	0	4	2.37	1.153
preference_for_male_operators_may_lack_techniques.	231	0	4	2.23	1.117
Valid N (listwise)	231				

Table 6: Mean and Standard deviation of gender discrimination

In Table 5, the Standard deviation for the variable gender discrimination is a normal deviation and this is because the SD value is low.

5. Leadership Issues

Descriptive analysis was carried out to assess the mean and standard deviation of the data in relation to leadership issues

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
leadership_problem.	231	0	4	2.74	.989
operators_lack_resilience	231	0	4	2.38	1.035
operators_expected_inventive_solutions_lack_entrepreneur_skills.	231	0	4	2.68	.818

Lack_entrepreneurial_s kills_impedes_adaptatio n	231	0	4	2.91	.821
Valid N (listwise)	231				

Table 7: Mean and Standard deviation of leadership problem

In Table 4, the Standard deviation for the variable infrastructural facilities is a normal deviation and this is because the SD value is low.

Our model fits the data as level of significance (*p-value*) is less than 0.05. This depicts that the variables listed above have effect on SMEs sustainability.

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	598.264			
Final	552.838	45.426	5	.000
Link function: Logit.				

Table 8: Model fitting test for the variables that influence SME sustainability

According to Table 9. R-square value was 0.191 which means that 19.1% of SME sustainability is impaired by the variables which are; financial hurdle, lack of infrastructure, poor management, gender discrimination and/or leadership issues.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.179
Nagelkerke	.191
McFadden	.072
Link function: Logit.	

Table 9: The percentage effect of the variables on SMEs sustainability

Using SPSS, ordinal regression analysis was used in the above distribution, to test for the significance and influence of financial hurdle, infrastructural facilities, poor management, gender discrimination, and leadership issues on SME sustainability. A variable is significant when the *p-value* is < 0.05 and insignificant when value is > 0.05 . Table 10 below shows the significant value for leadership issues to be 0.00 which depicts that leadership issues being a major impediment to SMEs sustainability is significant.

Parameter Estimates								
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = .00]	-.754	1.280	.347	1	.556	-3.263	1.755
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = .50]	-.035	1.053	.001	1	.973	-2.098	2.028
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 1.00]	.408	.965	.179	1	.673	-1.483	2.298
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 1.50]	1.165	.877	1.765	1	.184	-.554	2.884
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 2.00]	2.961	.836	12.536	1	.000	1.322	4.599

	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 2.50]	3.865	.847	20.840	1	.000	2.206	5.525
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 3.00]	6.888	.931	54.711	1	.000	5.063	8.714
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 3.50]	7.766	.956	65.926	1	.000	5.891	9.641
Location	Financial_hurdle	.195	.241	.655	1	.418	-.277	.667
	Infrastructural_facilities	.319	.235	1.849	1	.174	-.141	.779
	Poor_management	.355	.237	2.242	1	.134	-.110	.820
	Gender_discrimination	-.153	.155	.965	1	.326	-.457	.152
	leadership_problem	1.081	.275	15.481	1	.000	.543	1.620
Link function: Logit.								

Table 10: Regression analysis to test for significance

According to the findings of this current study, the issue of leadership is extremely important in terms of impediments to SME sustainability and this is because for every unit increase in the leadership problem, there is a predicted increase of 1.081 in the log odds of further impeding sustainable SMEs. This simply means that for every increase in leadership issues, the rate of sustainability of SMEs is reduced.

According to our respondents, and as shown in Table 10, financial hurdles are not a major impediment to SME sustainability because for every unit increase in the financial hurdles, there is a predicted 0.195 in the log odds of impediments for sustainable SMEs;

For every unit increase in infrastructural facilities, there is a predicted 0.319 in the log odds of impediments for sustainable SMEs. For every unit increase in poor management, there is a predicted 0.355 in the log odds of impediments for sustainable SMEs

For every unit increase in gender discrimination, there is a predicted -0.153 in the log odds of SME sustainability impediments.

4.2.4. The Effect of Women Leadership on SMEs Sustainability in Nigeria

The different measures of women leadership are transformed and computed into one variable as stated below.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
enterprises_perform_better_female_head	231	0	4	2.24	1.010
C24: When it comes to business growth and competitiveness, Nigeria women are result oriented as they are able to breakeven, thrive and grow SMEs to maturity.	231	0	4	2.95	.790
Women_attention_details_focused_tasks	231	0	4	2.83	.897
women_communicate_influence_desired_results	231	0	4	2.57	1.006
Women thought enables_competitive_existence.	231	0	4	2.84	.787
Women leaders resourceful_utilization_resources.	231	0	4	2.87	.788
women_responsibility_decisions_profitably.	231	0	4	2.98	.754
woman inspired encouraging_motivated	231	0	4	2.77	.878
resilience spirit female_managers	231	0	4	2.71	.850
Women_responsive_to_meet_customer_satisfaction.	231	0	4	2.82	.849
Women_strong_backing_stay_ahead_competition	231	0	4	2.84	.866
Valid N (listwise)	231				

Table 11: Mean and Standard deviation of the effect of women leadership on SMEs

Table 11 shows that the result is normal distribution , so we can proceed with the rest of the studies using the normality information above. Our model fits the data as level of significance (*p-value*) is less than 0.05. This depicts that women leadership has effect on SMEs sustainability.

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	327.665			
Final	298.781	28.885	1	.000
Link function: Logit.				

Table 12: Model fitting test for effect of women leaders on SME sustainability

As shown in Table 13 below, R-square value was 0.126 which depicts that 12.6% of change in SME sustainability is as a result of women leadership.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.118
Nagelkerke	.126
McFadden	.046
Link function: Logit.	

Table 13: The percentage effect of women leadership on SMEs sustainability

Using SPSS, ordinal regression analysis was used in the above distribution, to test for the significance and the level of influence women leadership can have on SME sustainability. A

variable is significant when the *p-value* is < 0.05 and insignificant when value is > 0.05 . The significant value for the effect of women leadership on SMEs sustainability is 0.00 which depicts that women leadership does affect SMEs sustainability.

Parameter Estimates								
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = .00]	-2.357	1.142	4.258	1	.039	-4.596	-.118
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = .50]	-1.635	.886	3.408	1	.065	-3.371	.101
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 1.00]	-1.193	.781	2.334	1	.127	-2.724	.337
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 1.50]	-.446	.669	.443	1	.506	-1.758	.866

	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 2.00]	1.280	.594	4.647	1	.031	.116	2.443
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 2.50]	2.128	.597	12.692	1	.000	.957	3.299
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 3.00]	5.028	.679	54.881	1	.000	3.698	6.359
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 3.50]	5.896	.706	69.730	1	.000	4.512	7.279
Location	Women_leadership	1.239	.222	31.275	1	.000	.805	1.674
Link function: Logit.								

Table 14: Regression analysis for test of significance

Female leadership has grown in popularity in recent years, and it is now more popular than it has ever been. As a result, it was critical in this study to assess our respondents' perspectives on how women can contribute to the future sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. According to the findings of this study, and as shown in Table 14, Female leadership are a perfectly significant positive predictor of SMEs sustainability. For every unit increase in female leadership, the log odds of having a more sustainable SMEs increase by 1.239.

4.2.5. Charismatic Leadership; An Effective Leadership Model For Sustainable SMEs In Nigeria

In Chapter 2 of this study, five major leadership models were described, namely; Coercive, charismatic, authentic, transactional and transformational style of leadership.

As a result, we tested these leadership models in the current studies to determine which style was used by our respondents. During our analysis, certain responses were transformed and computed to produce the mean/median of our dependent variable (SMEs sustainability) and the independent variables mentioned above.

Having computed our variables, we ran a test of normality, to be sure that our data is a normal distribution which also helps define which form of regression is best used.

Table 15. Shows that the result is normal, so we proceeded with the rest of the studies using the normality information below in Table 15. Our model fits the data as level of significance (*p-value*) is less than 0.05. The variables have effect on SMEs sustainability.

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	576.365			
Final	481.377	94.988	5	.000
Link function: Logit.				

Table 15: Model fitting test

As seen in Table 16, R-square value is 0.361 which depicts that 36% of change in SMEs sustainability is as a result of the previously highlighted models of leadership

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.337
Nagelkerke	.361
McFadden	.151
Link function: Logit.	

Table 16: The percentage effect of the variables on SMEs sustainability

Using SPSS, ordinal regression analysis was used in the above distribution, to test for the significance and the level of influence Coercive, charismatic, authentic, transactional and transformational style of leadership can have on SMEs sustainability. A variable is significant

when the *p-value* is < 0.05 and insignificant when value is > 0.05 . The significant value for charismatic leadership was 0.00

Parameter Estimates								
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = .00]	.092	1.133	.007	1	.935	-2.129	2.314
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = .50]	.842	.917	.843	1	.359	-.955	2.639
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 1.00]	1.341	.834	2.587	1	.108	-.293	2.975
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 1.50]	2.286	.766	8.896	1	.003	.784	3.788
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 2.00]	4.556	.797	32.663	1	.000	2.993	6.118
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 2.50]	5.635	.820	47.235	1	.000	4.028	7.242
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 3.00]	9.054	.935	93.810	1	.000	7.222	10.887
	[SME_SUSTAINABILITY = 3.50]	10.021	.967	107.485	1	.000	8.126	11.915

Location	Authentic_leadership	.424	.151	7.878	1	.005	.128	.720
	Coersive_leadership	.321	.194	2.749	1	.097	-.058	.701
	Charismatic_leadership	1.003	.235	18.180	1	.000	.542	1.464
	transformational_leadership	.499	.220	5.142	1	.023	.068	.931
	Transactional_leadership	.269	.232	1.348	1	.246	-.185	.724
Link function: Logit.								

Table 17: Effect of leadership styles on SMEs sustainability

As shown in Table 17, for every unit increase in Charismatic Leadership Style, the log odds of having a more sustainable SMEs increases by 1.003. According to our data, the significance value of Charismatic leadership is .000 (*p-value is* < 0.05), indicating that Charismatic leadership is a significant positive predictor of SMEs sustainability.

Also, the result of the current study suggest that transformational leadership style is a significant positive predictor of SMEs sustainability as the significant value is 0.023. For every one unit increase in transformational style of leadership, there is a predicted increase of 0.499 in the log odds of having a more sustainable SMEs. Furthermore, authentic leadership style is significant positive predictor of SMEs sustainability as the significant value is 0.005. For every one unit increase in authentic Style of leadership, there is a predicted increase of 0.424 in the log odds of having a more sustainable SMEs.

Coercive leadership is not a significant predictor of SMEs sustainability. The level of significance (0.097) is greater than the threshold of 0.05. Furthermore, transactional leadership style is also not a strong predictor of SMEs sustainability. The level of significance (0.246) is significantly greater than 0.05. Our respondents believe that with the Nigerian culture as equally important SMEs would struggle under both Coercive and transactional leadership.

From our current findings, charismatic model of leadership is the most effective form of leadership and has the ability to influence the sustainability of SMEs more than any other form. The Authentic and transformational models are also very effective in influencing SME sustainability. However, according to our survey, Coercive and transactional styles of leadership are not so effective.

4.3. QUALITATIVE DATA PRESENTATION

4.3.1. Introduction

As discussed in Chapter 2, several emerging economies are expected to transform from an industrial society to an entrepreneurial one in which entrepreneurial leadership and orientation are supposed to be the core elements contributing to the success of the many enterprise. As the practice of startups grows in popularity and breadth, some researchers have attempted to analyze factors influencing the business performance of SMEs.

Leadership is critical to making changes at multiple levels of the society including the environmental and policy levels, and will therefore provide solutions to the several issues SMEs are facing.

The purpose of this qualitative study is to assess the factors that affects women leadership in Nigeria with the aim of adopting a leadership model best suited for women leadership thereby enhancing sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria.

Key informant interviews were conducted with 17 participants of which 9 are women and 8 are men from November 2020 through December 2020. The sample represented a spectrum of leaders from across different businesses. Questions were designed to determine the leadership model mostly practised in SMEs, motivation, characteristics, successful leadership model for women leadership, and challenges, suitable leadership model for SME sustainability.

As discussed in the previous chapter, the use of NVIVO analysis software was adopted to analyse the data collected for the qualitative data collection. The transcripts from the interview were assessed and ensured to be clean and usable by initial proofreading and paraphrasing for proper coding and analysis. The interview was coded and classified into

themes which enabled the research to identify ideas and patterns, theories and themes in the transcripts of the interview. The word cloud below shows some of the generated themes by use of the NVIVO software.

Figure 5: Word cloud of what the participants discussed mostly.

Authentic leadership model, Situational leadership model, Charismatic leadership model, and Full-Range leadership model were the various leadership models explored in this current study, as discussed in Chapter 2. This study's framework consisted of independent variables, component variables, and dependent variables. This is depicted in Figure 4.3 as a structured flowchart.

4.3.3. Factors That Contributes To SMEs Sustainability

Figure 8: : Opinions of our respondents on what factors they believe could improve sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria

As part of this current study, we asked our respondents for their thoughts on the factors that could improve sustainability. Using a proportionality chart like the one shown in Figure 8, the majority of our respondents believe leadership is the most important, as stated by some of the respondents;

“I think we've mentioned all the leadership models. I also think the full range for anyone that wants to successfully run a business in this country is mostly appropriate”. (Respondent (R),

13)

“Nothing much, I'll only say I think if you want to go further in entrepreneurship, we all need these leadership traits in our Business one way or the other, either you are starting small or not, it's something everyone irrespective of gender should adapt to”. (R, 16)

Also, the respondents believed that financial aid is the next major impediment to SMEs sustainability as seen in Figure 8 above. Here is what some of them have to say;

“Money! They need money, support and empowerment ... it will go a long way in helping the society, but because of lack of funds, they are helpless” (R,1)

“In Nigeria, you need capital for business and those kind of opportunities are not so many here ... if I can get the loan, I can get a brand new car for my business”. (R, 2)

A smaller but equal proportion believe that visibility, public relations, equipment provision, and the formation of support groups are critical.

“I just want the government to help with equipment for support, in this business line, you can use your hand but it's much easier when you're using the computer”. (R, 5)

However, though encouragement and education appeared to be our respondents' least favourite factor, one of the respondents had this to say;

“I think more awareness and education. Some organizations are having SME camps and presentations and all. They are trying to build the Participant in business and all that. More of that will help in going forward”. (R,3)

4.3.4 Leadership Models As Preferred By Respondents

Participants in this qualitative study were interviewed to determine which leadership models they use in their own businesses. Opinions were solicited and classified according to gender as presented in Figure 4.5. According to the findings of this study, the most commonly used leadership models by our female respondents were charismatic leadership, situational leadership, transactional leadership, authentic leadership, and full range leadership, as shown in Figure 4.6. Male respondents, on the other hand, primarily used full range leadership,

authentic leadership, transactional leadership, and situational leadership styles, with no males using the charismatic leadership model, which was primarily used by female respondents in this study.

Figure 9: Male and female respondents' preferred leadership styles used in their businesses

4.3.5. Leadership Values

LEADERSHIP VALUES					
COMMUNICATION		RESOURCEFULNESS		RESILIENCE	
MALE	BOTH	MALE		FEMALE	BOTH
FEMALE		FEMALE		MALE	
CLARITY OF THOUGHT		PROFESSIONALISM		RESPONSIVENESS	
FEMALE	MALE	FEMALE	MALE	BOTH	MALE
BOTH		BOTH		FEMALE	

Figure 10: Participant's thought on the leadership values as displayed by both male and female leaders

For the sake of this study, a few values were mentioned; Communication, Resourcefulness, Resilience, Clarity of thought, Professionalism and Responsiveness. These are values expected of a good leader, some leaders can possess all, some a few. However, participants shared their opinion on values they have noticed in certain leaders based on their gender.

Figure 10 shows the thoughts of the participants as regards the leadership values assessed.

They believe that

- i. Men communicate more than women as leaders
- ii. Men are more resourceful than women
- iii. Women have shown more resilience in leadership
- iv. Women possess more clarity in thinking as leaders
- v. Women are way more professional than men as leaders

vi. Both gender are very responsive as leaders.

4.3.6. Leadership Styles That Encourages SMEs Sustainability

Participants were polled to determine which model they believe will encourage the long-term existence and sustainability of businesses in Lagos. So far in this current study, we have found that our respondents favor charismatic leadership as a preferred leadership model that promotes the growth of SMEs in Lagos, Nigeria. Figure 4.8 shows that a larger proportion of our respondents preferred the charismatic leadership model, with the authentic leadership model coming in second place. We have a smaller proportion who believe in situational leadership and the smallest who believe in the full range leadership model.

Figure 11: Leadership style that encourage SMEs sustainability

The above chart, explains the views of our participants. Based on the survey, majority of our participants strongly believe that the charismatic model of leadership has more influence on SME sustainability than any other model.

4.3.7 Leadership Model That Best Suit Women Leaders

Figure 12: Respondents' perceptions of the best leadership style for female entrepreneurs.

Based on Figure 12 above charismatic leadership not only suits women in Leadership, it has a strong influence on SMEs sustainability .

One of the respondents had this to say;

“Charismatic because once you know there is a way something must be done, it will definitely enhance a sustainable SMEs in the sense that, when you have a template for the operations in your enterprise, and if you derail from it, it will lead to inability to reach the goals of that SMEs. Anyone in that enterprise can easily do what they are supposed to do based on the set template”. (R, 11)

Another respondent had this to say;

“I will still pick charismatic. I've already said you should be a role model in whatever you do, let people look up to you and aspire to be like you”. (R17)

Also, R14 believes that Charismatic leadership works best for women as stated in the response below;

“For me, charismatic leadership works best for a woman, reason being that, if you're being authentic as a woman, your staff tend to see you like a bossy person that they can't approach ... So, I think the charismatic model works best for women leaders. It's like you're balancing the situational and authentic models. Women leaders that exhibit the authentic kind of leadership don't get to keep their staff for long with them, their staff tend to leave within few months of working with them, but if you are the charismatic type, it will be balanced because you know you have different types of people you are bringing to work with you, if you understand them on such grounds and you are able to match both authentic and situational leadership, it will make the business thrive fine”. (R14)

CHAPTER 5

5.0 DISCUSSION

As stated in Chapter 1, the study aims to examine how women leadership impact on SMEs and to suggest an adoptable leadership model for SME sustainability in Nigeria. Following the presentation of the result findings of this study in Chapter 4, this current chapter would look to explore different aspects of the results presented with possible concepts that is believed to have originated from the study data.

5.1 THE INFLUENCE OF AGE GROUP ON NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY GRADUATES' ENTREPRENEURIAL AMBITIONS.

Setting up businesses has been perceived to come with a level of maturity and expertise (Deszczyński and Beręsewicz 2021). Often times, the unprivileged Nigerians who may not be able to afford formal education, usually choose to learn a trade (Okolie *et al.*, 2021). Such apprenticeship normally takes 4 to 7 years to complete, and the time of graduation (or *freedom* as they call it) depends on a number of factors such as; level of expertise of the apprentice, discretion of the trade master, and availability of funds to set up personal business to mention a few (Asirvatham and Humphries-Kil, 2021). After completing the apprenticeship and all conditions met, the trade graduates would look to start their own business mostly around the age of 18-25.

As shown in Table 1, findings from this study suggest that there are more entrepreneurs within the 26-33 years of age as we received most (111) respondents within this age group (Table 1). This could be attributed to a number of socio-economic reasons. Studies from Okolie *et al.*, 2021 reported that many Nigerians complete their university education within

the ages of 24 to 30. After which they are enrolled into the National Youth Service Scheme which runs for a 12 calendar month. During this period the government attempts to support ambitious graduates to embark on SMEs in their chosen trades. This is a deliberate attempt to reduce the pressure on the labour market such that young graduates could embark on setting up a decent means of livelihood rather than looking for work elsewhere. This however have not been without its pit falls (Deszczyński and Beręsewicz 2021).

5.2 THE RATIO OF FEMALE TO MALE ENTREPRENEURS IN NIGERIA

Although previous studies (Okolie *et al.*, 2021) reported otherwise as discussed in the introduction of this chapter findings from this current studies suggested that there are more women entrepreneurs in Lagos Nigeria (Table 1). It is a common practise in the western part of Nigeria for women to run the family business, as they are able to balance work commitments with family life to create a more conducive work-life balance. This means women are able to run small scale businesses and still have the time to raise their children and also the time for domestic chores. It must be mentioned however that the scope of this study remains within the SMEs in Lagos Nigeria our case study.

Also studies have shown that women are agreeably better business owners as they are endowed with natural innate abilities to multitask and coordinate complex activities better than the men (Luthar *et al.*, 2017; Freischlag and Velazquez-Ramirez, 2021). Although Abu-Hammad *et al.*, (2020) agree with the concept of women being great leaders, the study suggested that this sort of disposition lies only with the Alpha females. That said, studies from Freischlag and Velazquez-Ramirez, (2021), reported that women have the tenacity and determination required to stay in business and see it thrive. This on the other hand, has not

been accepted by Abu-Hammad *et al.*, (2020) who argued that women easily give up on their dreams as they tend to be more emotional than men. The result of this quantitative survey is in agreement nonetheless with studies from Luthar *et al.*, (2017).

5.3 TECHNICAL KNOW-HOW A FUEL FOR BUSINESS SUSTAINABILITY.

There was a sharp decline in the number of respondents within the ages 34-40 ,41-47 and 48 above who took part in this survey as seen in Table 1. As earlier stated in this discussion, the endowment fund granted to graduates upon completion of the National Youth Service program would see them become business owners but with little or no business experience. Although it is easy to argue that the young graduates have the technical and education required to run successful businesses, they however are inexperienced and may struggle to understand business dynamics which comes with years of experience on the same business. In the context of this study, there is a tendency that upon the start of the businesses at the age of graduation, SME owners face technical or infrastructural constraints, economic hardship, unfavourable government policies and marketing issues that render the business unsustainable leading to the permanent shutdown.

In addition, the lack of technical know-how of the chosen trade could be a serious factor limiting the sustainability of the business. The short duration of the NYSC scheme, and the time taken to prepare the graduates for the chosen business may not be adequate for a comprehensive training and information gathering about the chosen business. This means that many graduates could have chosen a business on impulse and simply because it is their passion without a complete market survey or visibility studies which are completed based on facts and concrete marketing evidences. Based on the aforementioned, SMEs owners may

struggle to afford to employ the right skills set required to steer the business during the periods of turbulence. This may have explained some of the reasons for the decline in the number of respondents as their age increases as shown in the result of this study (Table 4.1).

5.4 IMPRACTICABLE OR NO SUSTAINABLE FORECASTS

For a sustainable running of an enterprise, entrepreneurs would be keen to ensure that they continue to commit to long term goals and sustainable practices. According to Epe Shari *et al.*, (2022), the ever changing government policies especially in growing economies like that in Nigeria, is a strong factor that affect sustainability of businesses. It is important that entrepreneurs are able cope with ever changing, government, market demands, inflations, and other factors that might affect sustainable practices. The decline observed in the number of respondents from ages 41 and above could be as a result of impracticable forecasts or poor market forecasts. Studies from Ozoegwu and Akpan, (2021) would see it from other perspectives as it places the blame of business sustainability on the poor economy which is a ripple effect of bad governance and corrupt practices. Although other studies Hadi and Baskaran, (2021) suggested that the problems facing SMEs in Nigeria should not only be seen from government perspective but also from social and psychological stand point where individual determination to succeed by business owners play important roles in business sustainability. It was stressed that most businesses experience challenging phases where profit is low or even marginal and as such would take determination and resilience of the owners to pull through. This has been thought to be lacking in some entrepreneurs.

5.5 THE IMPACT OF ENTERPRISE EXPERIENCE AND EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION ON NIGERIA SMES

When it comes to business sustainability, the importance of education cannot be overemphasized particularly for SMEs where more than just a specific skill set is required. Because most SMEs operate on a shoestring budget, the owner tends to do a lot more than you would expect in a large corporation. SME owners are frequently in charge of accounting, human resources, operations, transportation, continuous improvement, and other sensitive aspects of the business. As a result, SMEs' owners should be well-educated. According to our findings, 50% of our respondents only have an Ordinary National Diploma or a National Certificate in Education (Table 2). While both of these qualifications may be sufficient for basic awareness of some businesses and the skill set they bring, they do not appear to be sufficient for business owners whose positions require management expertise. (Nwagwu, 2020). Although the findings of this study do not imply that respondents with higher degrees have more years of enterprise experience, studies from Nwagwu (2020) emphasise the importance of business degrees as a qualification required for efficient management and business sustainability. This has somewhat impacted not just sustainability but the quality of services you get from the SMEs in Nigeria. Is it important, as stated by Darley (2021) that specific activities necessitate specific training. A number of scholars have examined the issue of sustainability in the SME sector holistically. Most importantly, it is critical to note that most businesses never progress past the developmental stages due to a lack of education and technical knowledge of the type of trade. Based on this premise, it is reasonable to infer that a lack of the necessary formal education may be a significant barrier to the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria.

5.6 JOB MIGRATION AND EMPLOYABILITY

For many young graduates in Nigeria, the difficulty in obtaining gainful employment revolves around work experience. As previously discussed in this session, the government's investment in young graduates allows them to start their own businesses with no prior business experience. Regardless, when they finally start and can boast of years of experience, their employability grows and they are able to compete for available jobs. According to the findings of this study, nearly half (115) of our respondents have less than 5 years of work experience with a SME (Table 2). As a result, the number of people who leave after gaining the necessary experience to work for other existing and well-established businesses can be used to assess the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. Conversely, the Nigerian labour market has thrived primarily on attracting not only experienced but also highly qualified candidates for advertised positions. According to studies by Darley (2021), due to a lack of job opportunities, most Nigerian employers would place a premium on graduates or individuals with excellent academic results as a means of reducing the number of applicants who make it to the interview stage. For example, regardless of job proficiency, a candidate with a second class lower would be less desirable than one with a second class upper. Having said that, due to the oversaturation of the labour market, candidates with NCEs and ONDs are sometimes overlooked when it comes to employability. The effect of this anomaly is that most persons with the lower degrees would therefore result into looking for fundings and then starting an SME (Nwagwu, 2020).

5.7 IMPEDIMENTS TO SME SUSTAINABILITY

Leadership has been identified as a serious issue of concern in many African countries, not only in terms of politics but also of business sustainability (Onakoya *et al.*, 2018). According to the findings of this current study, the issue of leadership is extremely important in terms of impediments to SME sustainability. For every unit increase in the “leadership problem” as seen Table 10, there is a predicted increase of 1.081 in the log odds of further impeding sustainable SMEs. According to our respondents, and as shown in Table 10, financial constraints are not a major impediment to SME sustainability; a lack of infrastructural facilities is not a major impediment to SME sustainability; poor management is not a major impediment to SME sustainability; and gender discrimination is not a major impediment to SME sustainability.

It should be noted, however, that our respondent's views are limited to Nigeria. Nigeria's leadership has faced numerous challenges since the country's independence in 1960 (Oredein and Eigbe, 2014). The reality, which is not far-fetched, is that there are a number of corrupt practises taking place in various sectors of government, which have a direct or indirect impact on businesses and sustainability (Karatepe and Magaji, 2008). This is also evident in the corruption perception index (Transparency International, 2021). According to the findings of researchers Eluwole *et al.*, (2022), while ethical leadership fosters employees' trust in the organisation and service recovery performance while reducing absenteeism, most Nigerian organisations have had their fair share of bad leadership built on favouritism, double standards, nepotism, financial abuse, and bullying. The findings above imply that trust in the organisation moderates the impact of ethical leadership on absenteeism, social loafing behaviour, and service recovery performance. The findings highlight the importance of

ethical leadership in fostering trust in organisational and service recovery performance and reducing absenteeism.

Furthermore, as reported by Oredein and Eigbe (2014), a leader must be able to negotiate in order to resolve inevitable conflicts, which is a skill required in any organisation. It should be stated undoubtedly that conflicts are unavoidable in any organisation. This is especially true in an organisation, such as a business with a structure that allows two or more different units or groups to share functional boundaries in order to achieve its goals. Negotiation is a problem-solving process in which two parties try to reach an agreement on issues or courses of action in which they have some level of interest, goals, values, or beliefs in common. One of Nigeria's leadership issues, according to the report, is a lack of fair negotiation skills. This would almost certainly have an impact on the long-term viability of SMEs.

As reported by Ufua *et al.*, (2020) advocates of effective leadership practise place a premium on the leader's behavioural efforts, which are required to boost followers' confidence in their commitment to achieving set leadership goals. This leaves leaders with the task of developing a positive behavioural disposition that can serve as a tacit learning platform for followers in organisations. It also highlights the fact that the practise of organisational leadership appears to have progressed beyond simple transactional practises such as motivation and rewards. These include extended positive acts such as pro-social behaviours, continuous self-development that can inform compliance in addressing complex issues, and exceeding expectations across an organization's operational structure. To be more specific, leaders must set a good example and be able to comport themselves in such a way that their actions can be emulated by their followers. Certain leaders, as seen in most Nigerian societies, have little or no regard for time, expecting their followers to arrive at meetings earlier while they arrive later.

5.8 LEADERSHIP AS A FACTOR TO IMPROVING SUSTAINABILITY

As part of this current study, using a proportionality chart like the one shown in Table 10, the majority of our respondents believe leadership is the most important, followed by financial aid. A smaller but equal proportion believe that visibility, public relations, equipment provision, and the formation of support groups are critical. Our respondents' least favourite factors were encouragement and education.

One of the most important aspects of management is leadership (Wehrich, *et al.*, 2008). This is due to the fact that leadership is a major factor that greatly contributes to the overall well-being of organisations and nations. Through the effective leadership of Jack Welch and Lee Iacocca, organisations such as General Electric and Chrysler were brought back from the brink of bankruptcy to become two of the world's most profitable businesses (Robbins and Coulter, 2007). Our survey respondents were clear in their assessment of the importance they place on leadership. It should be noted, however, that the available data does not currently assess the extent to which leadership impacts any business, but rather perspectives on what is considered important. As a result, there were clearly opposing viewpoints. From a political standpoint, our respondents' views on leadership could be seen. Nigeria's leadership, as well as the leadership of some African nations. More directly, political leadership influences the types of marketing policies that are enacted, as well as the impact that these policies have on SMEs. For example, the ban on imported goods into Nigeria in 2012 meant that there would be a scarcity of not only certain finished products, but also raw materials, which were critical for the long-term viability of some SMEs.

5.9 LEADERSHIP MODELS FOR SUSTAINABLE SMES IN NIGERIA

The result of this study suggest that most of our women respondents preferred charismatic leadership styles. This is not farfetched when considered what charismatic leadership model is. According to the researchers Ernst *et al.*, (2021), charismatic leadership is a "values-based, symbolic, and emotion-laden leader signaling." Charismatic leadership is related to leader effectiveness, task performance and attitudes of followers, and firm performance.

More importantly, charisma is not an immutable trait one is born with; it can be trained and developed. Keeping this in mind, the preference expressed by our female respondents can be attributed to most women's natural aptitude to be mentors, role models and nurturers. This is consistent with studies (Taylor *et al.*, 2022). According to Chhaochharia *et al.*, (2022), some businesses are dominated by women and thus avoided by men, and vice versa. The current study's limitation stems from the fact that the type of SME operated by the respondents was not determined. This implies that the types of businesses operated by our female respondents are likely to be female-dominated, and as such, only a specific leadership model may be applicable. Females predominate in some professions or SMEs, such as nursing, nursing assistants, fashion design, make-up artists, hair styling, and grocery retailing (Taylor *et al.*, 2022). The findings of this qualitative study can be viewed through the eyes of our respondents who work in one of those female-dominated businesses and may account for the reason majority chose charismatic leadership as the preferred leadership model Figure 9.

It came as no surprise that the majority of our male respondents preferred full-range leadership models (Figure 9). However, a sizable proportion also concluded that authentic leadership models are their preferred option. To gain an insight to full range leadership and why we think our male respondent preferred this model, Bass and Riggio, 2006 described the full-range leadership model

as that which entails directing or influencing followers toward a specific result, goal, or objective via reward or discipline. Without any gender bias or prejudice, the findings of this study could only be seen from the lens of reports from the respondents which relies majorly on their perception. That being said, the directive or influential actions seen in full range leadership models are generally viewed positively, particularly in relation to transformational leadership, and the ideal leadership profile is said to include someone who exhibits higher frequencies of transformational leadership behaviours. Report by Westerlaken *et al.*, (2013) suggested that full range leadership is positively related to follower commitment, loyalty, satisfaction, and leader effectiveness. Theorists have also however identified a dark side of full range leadership, that involves charismatic leaders using dominance, aggression, exploitation, threats, and punishment in order to manipulate followers for their own personal gain (Westerlaken *et al.*, 2013).

5.10 FACTORS THAT CONTRIBUTES TOWARDS WOMEN LEADERSHIP IN NIGERIA SMES

It has been thought that there seem to be a leadership style that support the proliferation of women SME owners. Over the last few decades, there has been a debate about whether women manage or lead differently than men. There are three points of view on this issue. The first is the "women do lead differently" hypothesis, which holds that women are born with or develop traits that differ sharply from male leadership characteristics (Deji and Makinde 2006). According to the opposing argument, there are few or no gender differences in leadership styles. The third point of view on this topic dismissed the debate over leadership styles as insignificant. What matters from this vantage point is the end result. It doesn't matter how you lead as long as your leadership style is effective (Okafor *et al.*, 2011).

Similarly, Bellou, (2011) contends that male stereotypes of independence, assertiveness, competence, competitiveness, lower emotional and analytic minds are compatible with leadership demands. Female stereotypes that reflect dependence, weakness, emotionality, nurturance, and talkativeness, on the other hand, are inconsistent with the functions of a leader. However, in order to increase their effectiveness as leaders and dispel the myth that women are a weaker sex, some women may adopt an autocratic leadership style.

As much as there may have been a number of misconceptions about African women and leadership, it has been assumed that women leaders demonstrate more empathy than men, making them more effective at influencing and motivating individuals (Gibson *et al.*, 2017). Also, in a sample of US firms by Adams and Ferreira (2009), it was observed that female directors have better attendance records than male directors, male directors have fewer attendance problems the more gender-diverse the board is, and women are more likely to join monitoring committees. Despite the fact that this hypothesis has been debated for over a decade, researchers Adams and Ferreira (2009) suggested that the leadership models used and the outcome have more to do with temperaments and human personalities than gender. According to Ikegbu and Odey (2018), both alpha males and females have similar leadership traits that make them great leaders. This concept reinterprets the ideology of human personality traits as opposed to gender biases or stereotypes. Within the last decade, the Nigerian mindset toward female leadership has been heavily influenced by the West. Existing stereotypes have been shaped and are constantly being modified by the civilisational influence brought by western culture. The cultural shift seeks to dispel the notion that women are only well-suited to domestic tasks. However, as more women strive to break down ethnic and social barriers, the number of successful female entrepreneurs grows over time. For instance and in accord with the findings of this chapter, Adam and Funk (2011) reported that female directors are more benevolent and universally concerned than male directors, but less power oriented. More positively,

the authors argue that women leaders are better risk takers than men SME owners, who are more logical by nature, limiting their business ventures. Researchers Ikegbu and Odey (2018) argued strongly that, while there appear to be more female SME owners in Nigeria, their exploits remain limited because they usually do not make it past few thousands annual turnover due to the nature of the businesses they run. It is believed that they are more involved in some petty trading and business that is kept at a subsistence level (Nosike and Oguzor, 2011).

AlHajj *et al.*, (2013) stated that women have always been compassionate and empathic toward their co-workers and subordinates. Although this has frequently been perceived as a flaw rather than a strength in most African societies, it is critical to understand that one of the keys to successful business management in modern times is good human resource management. Most businesses with high staff turnover have been observed to have poor people management. People are more likely to stay in jobs where the leadership is compassionate and empathic. This could only be seen from a different angle, as studies by Deji and Makinde (2007) suggested that there is insufficient evidence to conclude that most female leaders are empathic and companionate. However, the narrative becomes more interesting when women are viewed through the lens of their roles in the home as opposed to when they have a business to run. At this point, most leaders are more concerned with maximising the business's potential than with the emotional rationale that their gender may suggest (Okafor *et al.*, 2011).

5.11 IMPACT OF WOMEN LEADERSHIP ON SME SUSTAINABILITY IN NIGERIA

Female leadership has grown in popularity in recent years, and it is now more popular than it has ever been. As a result, it was critical in this study to assess our respondents' perspectives on how women can contribute to the future sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. According to the findings of

this study, and as shown in Table 14, Female leadership are a perfectly significant positive predictor of SME sustainability. For every unit increase in female leadership, the log odds of having a more sustainable SME increase by 1.239.

According to a study by Colovic (2022), women have some advantages over men in business. We discussed the ratio of women to men SME owners in Nigeria earlier in this chapter, and our research indicates that there are more women entrepreneurs in Lagos, Nigeria than men. Keeping this in mind, the opinions of random respondents were gathered for this quantitative study. Thus, we believe our findings are valid because they are consistent with ideas from Handaragama and Kusakabe (2021) in a study in Sri Lanka where women's participation in business associations in small scale tourism enterprises was evaluated. They reported that although women's participation in business associations is limited to low-level positions, while significant leadership positions in business associations are dominated by men, preventing women from reaping many of the potential benefits. Women entrepreneurs join business associations with a strong desire to overcome obstacles, gaining access to business resources such as financial, information, and connections. They also join a variety of business associations in search of tenacity to address the challenges they face as female entrepreneurs. Colvic (2022)'s conclusion about women having an advantage over men in business cannot be overstated. It can be argued that societal resistance can lead to an exaggerated level of resilience, which Handaragama and Kusakabe (2021) found in the majority of Sri Lankan women entrepreneurs. It is also believed that this is not limited to a single location. Over time, the male gender's dominance has almost ensured that women are more determined than ever before to be heard and remain a force to be reckoned with.

Similarly, Azeem *et al.*, 2021 proposed that interactions between women can often lead to greater innovation and firm performance. The study investigated the logic behind business transactions involving women to women and the impact this can have on a firm's productivity. It was suggested

that as more women become SME owners, interactions between women may become more effective, indicating a more sustainable SME. Other researchers believe that the obvious disposition of women being able to manage relatively small businesses makes it difficult to base sustainability decisions solely on emotional prowess, which is based on the assumption that women are marginalised and thus become more resilient. Furthermore, before concluding that women leadership could be the ideal model standard for a sustainable SME in Nigeria, it is critical to understand the nature of individual businesses. This study relies on our respondents' opinions on what they believe is best suited for SMEs in Nigeria as evidence for future research.

5.12 CHARISMATIC LEADERSHIP; AN EFFECTIVE LEADERSHIP MODEL FOR SUSTAINABLE SMES IN NIGERIA

As shown in Table 17, for every unit increase in Charismatic Leadership Style, the log odds of having a more sustainable SME increases by 1.003. According to our data, the significance of Charismatic leadership is .000 (*p-value is* < 0.05), indicating that Charismatic leadership is a significant positive predictor of SME sustainability. Our respondents' understanding of Charismatic was seen and expressed in the context of our current study. This is due to a strong belief that charismatic leadership refers to the amount of leader influence over followers and the type of leader-follower relationship, as demonstrated by leader behaviours toward their followers (Zhang and Wei, 2021). This is thought to be especially important in Nigeria, where natives value individual leaders over offices or positions. The majority of Nigerian culture has traditionally thrived on respecting a leader in charge and would provide all possible support if the leader was still their choice for a variety of sentimental reasons. It then implies that the leader has some level of control and influence over the people. The sentimental acceptance fosters an enabling environment

for the leader to establish a good leader-follower relationship that is considered sustainable. This finding is consistent with Zhang and Wei's (2021) findings in a study of product life cycle, environmental performance, and financial performance, which concluded that the product life cycle is a contextual factor in the effects of charismatic leadership on environmental performance to support the product stewardship strategy; SMEs' charismatic leadership helps stakeholders share visions for promoting environmental performance and sustainable development.

The result of the current study suggest that transformational leadership style is a significant positive predictor of SME sustainability. For every one unit increase in transformational style of leadership, there is a predicted increase of 0.499 in the log odds of having a more sustainable SME (Table 17). Owing to the idea that transformational leaders motivate their followers through group identification and they influence the extent to which followers view their work as more consistent with their personal values, a number of Nigeria's SME owners adopt this leadership model. For example, some of our respondents believe that their pride is derived from the quality of their work, which is more of a motivator. Although our current study favours more charismatic leadership, it is important to note that some of our respondents believe transformational leadership is the best model for the long-term viability of Nigerian SMEs for the reasons stated above. Researchers Abbas and Ali (2021) reported similar findings after providing evidence that adopting transformational leadership leads to project success.

Authentic leadership style is significant positive predictor of SME sustainability. For every one unit increase in authentic Style of leadership, there is a predicted increase of 0.424 in the log odds of having a more sustainable SME. The responses from our respondent suggest that there are a number of SME owners that believe in authentic leadership styles as they have been able to express their true feelings and opinions in front of their team members, laying the groundwork for observational learning and, as a result, facilitating team voice. Furthermore, authentic leaders remain open to

differing viewpoints, including both innovative ideas and personal concerns; present their authentic selves rather than masking their true feelings; and adhere to their own moral standards. This is thought to support the proliferation of sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

From our current findings, charismatic model of leadership is the most effective form of leadership and has the ability to influence the sustainability of SMEs more than any other form. The coercive and transformational models are also very effective in influencing SME sustainability. However, according to our survey, Coercive and transactional styles of leadership are not so effective.

5.13 ADOPTABLE LEADERSHIP MODEL FOR WOMEN, THAT CAN DRIVE A SUSTAINABLE SME IN NIGERIA

According to the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), businesses in Nigeria die before their fifth anniversary in 2008. Yusuf (2014) enumerated that one of the reasons for this high failure rate is inappropriate leadership style and a failure to use market research to confirm demand and assess the suitability of proposed offerings, as well as to maintain a high level of customer patronage.

The responses of our respondents during this qualitative study on what leadership model they believe can drive a sustainable SME in Nigeria did not come as a complete surprise as seen in Figure 4.9. This is primarily due to the fact that our respondent earlier in this chapter advocated for the charismatic leadership model, which they currently employ. Previously in this study, there was a split between male respondents who preferred full range and authentic models over charismatic and situational models, which were preferred by female respondents. Nonetheless, the general perception of our respondents is that charismatic leadership in the contest of the Nigerian people,

culture, government policies, and commerce is the best for the sustenance of SMEs in the country. Our result is seen however to be inconsistent with finding of Emuwa and Fields, (2017) where their hierarchical regression analysis, showed a positive relationship between authentic leadership behaviours and the outcome variables of employees' organisational commitment and perceived leader effectiveness among Nigerian employees. According to the moderation result, the leader's contingent reward behaviours reduce the effects of the internal moral perspective dimension of authentic leadership. Contingency rewards become less important to followers as authentic leaders interact with them and followers exhibit high levels of moral and ethical behaviour. However, from the perspective of charismatic leadership, organisational commitment and leadership effectiveness are desirable organisational outcomes across cultures. From a practical standpoint, the current study's findings show that several charismatic dimensions are associated with organisational commitment and leadership effectiveness among Nigerian employees. This broadens the appeal of charismatic leadership to African countries. It, in particular, provides additional insight into a contemporary leadership model that has the potential to positively impact leadership development in Nigeria. While the interactive effects of contingent reward were limited, they do suggest that some behavioural combinations should be considered in order to effectively meet situational needs.

According to our respondents' reports, while not all have currently adopted the charismatic model, the majority believe it has the potential to improve the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. It should be noted, however, that when determining the most sustainable leadership model, the current study did not take into account women entrepreneurs' performance and productivity as a result of adopting charismatic leadership. According to Yusuf (2014), understanding the effects of leadership on performance is also important because leadership is viewed as one of the key driving forces for improving a firm's performance. Effective leadership is viewed as a powerful source of

management development and long-term competitive advantage for organisational performance improvement.

CHAPTER 6

6.0 GENERAL CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The sustainability of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in West Africa, particularly Nigeria, has long been a source of concern. Businesses have had a short life expectancy. Many studies have investigated the main cause of this problem as a lack of infrastructure, funding, manpower, required expertise and experience, government policy, cultural biases and ethnic differences, a lack of basic amenities, and gender related biases. While all of the preceding has been investigated, the understanding of the appropriate leadership style or model remains elusive. While some recent studies have identified leadership as a major issue in Nigeria, existing studies have primarily focused on how political leadership affects the Nigerian economy and its impact on the sustainability of Nigerian industries. As a result, it remains unclear which leadership model is best suited to the Nigerian economy, and, more importantly, which model promotes the growth and sustainability of SMEs.

However, this current study contributes to existing literature by identifying leadership and leadership style as the two most pressing issues at this time. Currently, studies have investigated various leadership styles, such as Transactional, Transformational, Coercive, Charismatic, and Full range leadership styles, but none has highlighted or suggested which one is thought to be the most effective and would support the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. Concurrently, while female leadership is accepted in some cultures, it is still rejected in others around the world. After the millennium, civilisation means that more countries, religions, and cultures are warming up to the idea of female leadership, and that more female leaders are being appointed to positions of

significant authority. Their performance, on the other hand, has been scrutinised, and a wide range of studies have been conducted to investigate the differences in female performance over male counterparts.

The current study investigated the efficacy of female leadership in relation to the leadership model or style that is thought to be best suited for them. Not only that, but it also investigated what leadership style favours females and, most importantly, what offers the possibility of a sustainable SMEs in Nigeria. As a result, the current study was designed to look into the role of female leadership in the sustainability of SMEs and, as a result, to make recommendations for the long-term operation of SMEs.

6.2 SUMMARY: CONCEPTUAL MODEL

The study was focused on exploring the relationship between women's leadership and sustainable SMEs in Nigeria. Various models of leadership was assessed to develop a framework that could enhance the sustainability of SMEs which were the dependent variable of this study. In this context, sustainable SMEs were characterised by factors such as effectiveness, efficiency, quality, timeliness and finance as well as workplace environment which were the independent variable of this study. However, for these variables to contribute to sustainable SMEs, leadership must be effective and it has to engender the essential component variables of professionalism, resourcefulness, resilience and clarity of thought for rational decision-making that is consistent with the vision of the company.

6.3 SUMMARY: LITERATURE GAP

The importance of SMEs in socio-economic transformation cannot be overemphasized as they have been acknowledged as crucial drivers of economic growth as well as agent of industrial development. While many studies have explored leadership challenges within SMEs in Nigeria and

assess various leadership styles for sustainable SMEs, there has been relatively limited attention given to how women leadership could enhance SMEs sustainability. Gender issues continues to be a contentious issues especially concerning economic and social marginalisation. Despite Nigeria's large population and significant educational, economic and social achievements, women continue to be underrepresented in leadership roles including SMEs. Therefore, to address the identified literature gaps and carve a niche for itself, this study carried out a comprehensive examination of the role of women leadership SMEs in Nigeria while developing a model aimed at enhancing the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria.

6.4 SUMMARY: METHODOLOGY

The research methodology adopted for this study combined both quantitative and qualitative approaches, ensuring a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the research topic. Quantitative data was made up of data from tailored research questionnaire. A non probability convenience sampling method was adopted with 231 viable responses analysed with the use of SPSS. Qualitative data was made up of responses from semi-structured interviews providing more detailed and person experiences and opinions. A convenience sampling method was adopted with 17 responses analysed with use of NVIVO software.

6.5 SUMMARY: FINDINGS

To address a major overarching gap in knowledge of leadership and the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria, recommendations on what leadership style is considered viable for SME sustainability were developed. This was accomplished by posing five major objectives over the course of a progressive qualitative and quantitative study: (i) to review leadership model thought to support the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. (ii) to examine factors that contributes towards women leadership

in SMEs in Nigeria. (iii) to investigate the contributions of women leadership towards sustainable SMEs in Nigeria. (iv) to evaluate the relationship between women leadership and sustainable SMEs in Nigeria. (v) to propose an adoptable leadership model for women leadership that can drive a sustainable SMEs in Nigeria.

6.5.1 Leadership models for sustainable SMEs.

The findings from the study suggested that most women respondents preferred charismatic leadership styles due to the characteristics of charismatic leadership. Charismatic leadership, being values-based, symbolic, and emotion-laden, often resonates with individuals who are drawn to inspirational and visionary leadership styles. Though a number of our male respondents preferred the full-range leadership models, however, some of them concluded that authentic leader models is their preferred option. Situational leadership model appeared to be the least preferred model as most of our respondents do not want to be reactive in their approach.

6.5.2 Factors that contributes to women leadership in SMEs

The findings from this study shows that some believe that women lead differently because they possess inherent or developed traits that distinguish their leadership style from that of men. They believe that woman leaders demonstrate more empathy than men, making them more effective in motivating others. Female leaders are more benevolent and concerned but less power oriented. Gender roles and societal expectations may influence perceptions of women's leadership, effective leadership in the business world is ultimately driven by the imperative to maximize organizational potential and achieve results. Women leaders navigate these complexities by leveraging their diverse experiences and skills while prioritizing the strategic objectives of their business.

6.5.3 Contributions of Women Leadership to sustainable SME in Nigeria

Women's leadership in SMEs fosters sustainability by promoting diversity, innovation, community engagement, ethical conduct, and long-term strategic thinking. By leveraging these strengths, women-led SMEs can contribute to positive social, environmental, and economic outcomes, driving sustainable development and prosperity in their communities.

6.5.4 Women's leadership has positive relationship with SME sustainability

Women entrepreneurs join business associations because they have a strong desire to overcome obstacles and gain access to business resources such as financial, information, and connections. They also join a variety of business associations in search of the tenacity to face the challenges that female entrepreneurs face. According to the current study, female leadership is a highly significant positive predictor of SME sustainability.

6.5.5 Charismatic Leadership: An Effective Leadership Model for Long-Term SME Sustainability in Nigeria.

In the Nigerian context, the amount of leader influence over followers and the type of leader-follower relationship as demonstrated by leader behaviours toward their followers are critical. This is thought to be particularly important in Nigeria, where people are valued more than offices or positions. The majority of Nigerian culture has traditionally thrived on respecting a leader in charge for a variety of sentimental reasons and would provide all possible support if the leader was still their choice. According to our current findings, the charismatic leadership model is the most effective and has the most influence on the long-term viability of SMEs in Nigeria.

6.6 CONCLUSIONS

Overall, the findings of all studies supported the stated objectives and demonstrated that women's leadership would aid in the proliferation of SMEs in Nigeria as well as lead to sustainable SMEs.

Leadership was viewed as a key factor not only from a political standpoint, but also for its impact on sustainability. As a result, various leadership styles such as Transactional Transformational, Coercive, Charismatic, and Full Range leadership styles were considered. Over the other leadership styles, charismatic leadership was found to support the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. The study's recommendation is that female charismatic leadership would help the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria.

6.7 RECOMMENDATION OR FUTURE WORK

This research highlights that additional studies are required:

1. To gain a better understanding of the impact of leadership on SMEs. It would be extremely beneficial to present data on the extent to which leadership affects SMEs. The current study is concerned with respondents' opinions or points of view. As a result, there were clearly opposing points of view.
2. To gain a better understanding of the concept of female leadership and how it differs from that of the male, situations in which female leadership has clearly outperformed that of the male in the same industry or business should be evaluated over time.
3. To conduct a comparative study of various leadership styles and assess their effects on the sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria. The current study only included in-depth accounts from study respondents. A more in-depth investigation from various business owners who have explored specific leadership style would be more beneficial.

6.8 LIMITATION OF RESEARCH

Every academic study must identify the weaknesses and/or limitations of the study which indicates any inherent reservation, probable weaknesses in a study, and an understanding of where the results of the study will not be applicable. One of the major limitations was that the reluctance of some uninformed respondents, who were unwilling to cooperate, which affected the researcher from securing formidable data for the study. Some of the respondents were indifferent in providing relevant data, because such needed data were usually considered to be “classified business information”.

On the issue of scope limitation, the focus of the study was constricted to SMEs in Lagos State Nigeria for a definite and realistic research range, considering that there are about 41.5 million small and medium-sized businesses spread across the 36 states. Hence, a major restriction of this study was that data obtained may not be a whole representative of the entire private sector organisations and the general business environment in Nigeria or other developing nations.

Be that as it may, the researcher made good attempt to reduce the abovementioned constraints to the barest minimum. Hence the researcher persistently made resilient effort to convince participants on the confidentiality and strict use of all data for research. Such and other measures including use of Nigeria common vocabulary (vernacular) was applied in explanation for few of the uninformed field respondents, so as to enable the researcher to achieve a significant success in the course of the research. On the part of paucity of funds, the researcher solicited for fund from sponsors, friends and men of good will. To avert time constraints, the researcher adopted good time management techniques. The researcher paid more attention to the data generated in order to avoid minor and major mistakes in the course of data analysis.

Another major challenge experienced was availability of data. At the start of this research work, the initial plan was to work with more participant in order to collect more data, however, there was the Covid-19 pandemic and national lockdown at the time which restricted movement and made it difficult to travel. Consequently, the research had to travel under stringent condition in order to collect the data for the purpose of this analysis.

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8.0 APPENDIX

8.1 PARTICIPANTS' INFORMATION SHEET FOR THE INTERVIEW

Research title: CHARISMATIC FEMALE LEADERSHIP: AN ADOPTABLE LEADERSHIP MODEL FOR SUSTAINABLE SMES IN NIGERIA

Inclusion criteria: The study seeks to explore the factors that influence the sustainability of SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. Participation requires that you are a small and medium scale business owner and that your business is based in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Exclusion criteria: A business owner that is not small and medium scale, likewise a small and medium scale owner that is not based in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Study Aims: This research aims to examine the how women leadership impact on SMEs in Nigeria and to proffer an adoptable model for women leadership in SME. This study will form a part of the requirement for my Doctorate in Business administration programme in the school.

What will I actually have to do? Participation in this study would involve you being interviewed. This interview would be audio-recorded. Your decision to participate is completely voluntary. By completing and signing the attached consent form it is implied that you consent to take part in the study. You may however decide to withdraw from the study at any time and there will be no penalty

What advantages are there? Your opinion, perception as well as experience about factors that influence the sustainability of SMEs will be obtained and used to proffer an adoptable model for women leaders for upcoming businesses. This gives you the opportunity to help others who intends to start an SME.

Confidentiality: The information you give me in the interview will not be connected to your name or other identifying details. No one will have access to the interview recording or written notes except me and my supervisor. Your recording and notes will be kept in a locked and secure cabinet for a maximum period of five years, after which time it will be destroyed. During the focus group discussion you have the right to decline to answer any questions I ask and you have the right to leave the focus group discussion itself. Please note that occasionally group discussions about personal experiences can cause upset or distress.

Thank you for your consideration in participating in this study.

Any questions or concerns: If you would like any further information about the research, please contact:

Name: Temidayo Fayemi

Personal details withheld.

Email: [REDACTED]

Post: University of the West of Scotland, London Campus, Import building, 2 Clove Crescent, London. E14 2BE

8.2 SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Section A: Respondent Demographics

Instruction: please tick (√) against any option you consider appropriate.

- A01 Respondents Gender. Male Female
- A02 Respondents Age: 18-24 years 26-32years 34-40years 41-47years 48 & above
- A03 Marital Status: Single Married Divorced Widowed Prefer not to say
- A04 Educational Qualification: WASSCE/GCE/SSCE ND/NCE HND/BSc Masters Doctorate Professorship
- A05 Enterprise Experience: Below 5 years 6-10 years 10-15 years 16 – 20 years 21 years and above

Section B: Substantive Issues

Instruction: Please kindly tick (√) against any option of the items in the questionnaire which you consider most appropriate. Where; SD = Strongly Disagree, D= Disagree, N = Neither Agree nor Disagree, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree.

Hypothesis One: Leadership models significantly influence SMEs continuous competitive existence and sustainable SMEs in Nigerian.

S/N	Description	SD	D	N	A	SA
B06	SME owner-managers lack the necessary understanding of how leadership styles can be used to improve firm performance and organizational sustainability					
B07	Among all the factors associated with the poor performance of Nigerian SMEs, leadership approach is seen as the most critical factor that impacts the long-term sustainability of the firms.					
B08	Leadership approaches influence different SMEs phenomena in Nigeria such as enterprise performance, enterprise growth, and sustainability.					
B09	The influence of leaders on their followers towards growth and sustainability is more pronounced in SME firms because they are characteristically small-sized.					
B10	Coercive style of leadership adopted by SME leaders in Nigeria often undermines employee engagement and contributes to high mortality rate of SMEs.					
B11	Charismatic leadership interventions produce positive organizational outcomes which are attributable to an increase in desirable enterprise commitment among leaders and followers.					
B12	Authentic leadership approach influences innovative entrepreneurship which enhances enterprise performance, growth and sustainability.					
B13	Authentic leadership approach improves innovativeness in organizations mainly on individual-level behaviour and less within the group-level behaviour for sustainability.					
B14	SME sustainability can be improved when leaders are transformational to inspire their subordinates towards stronger commitment to the organization rather than pursuing narrow personal interests.					
B15	Some managers are only transformational in extreme situations than they are in normal situations to maintain continuous SMEs competitive existence.					
B16	With transactional leadership approach the organization benefits from high employees' productivity while the achievements of the employees will translate to better rewards and higher career positions for them.					

B17	Transactional leadership approach has varying levels of positive influence on specific sustainability measures such as employee turnover rate, productivity, customer service efficiency, and profit margin percentage.					
B18	Leadership styles depend to a large extent on the operating environment of the SMEs and the contingencies at hand.					
B19	There is no one best way of leadership or management as leadership models/methods used in one circumstance seldom work the same way in others for the volatile SME sector.					
B20	Possibility of 'best ways' for SMEs sustainability is attainable if SME operators-managers-directors contingently adapt a good combination of leadership practices that best soothes the situation at hand.					
B21	There is need to understand the implications of leadership approaches on the sustainability of SMEs from cultural and organizational perspectives in Nigeria					

Hypothesis Two: There is a significant relationship between women leadership and sustainable SMEs in Nigerian

C22	Most enterprises I have come across performed better with a female at the head of affairs.					
C23	Many are in business not for the passion but just to meet their daily needs and do not possess the willpower of driving their ventures beyond the subsistent level.					
C24	When it comes to business growth and competitiveness, Nigeria women are result oriented as they are able to breakeven, thrive and grow SMEs to maturity.					
C25	Women pay attention to details and more focused on tasks in line with the goals and vision of the company.					
C26	The women I have worked for/with communicate better and are able to influence others desired results at any point in the enterprise operations.					
C27	Women's clarity of thought in entrepreneurial activities enables them to think outside the box for continuous competitive existence.					
C28	Women entrepreneur leaders are very resourceful in delivering the best possible products and services through the best utilization of available resources.					
C29	I have worked with women leaders who prudently take responsibility for company finance and make good calculated decisions that allow the business to operate profitably.					
C30	My team leader is/was a woman who really inspired the workforce by encouraging them to feel valued and motivated to work hard and believe in the company.					
C31	The continuous competitive existence of our company is fostered by the resilience and entrepreneur spirit of our female manager to always push for a comeback.					
C32	Women management teams are very responsive and apt in the production and delivering of quality goods/services to meet customer's satisfaction.					
C33	Women provide strong leadership backing to always stay ahead of competition and maintain their enterprise sustainability.					

Hypothesis Three: The challenges facing women leadership and SMEs in Nigeria significantly affect sustainable SMEs in Nigeria

D34	Financial hurdle is a major formidable factor inhibiting the sustainability and continuous competitive existence of SMEs in Nigeria.					
D35	Existing SMEs are generally stifled by inadequate working capital, while new entrants or start-ups find it practically impossible to access funds from Nigerian banks.					
D36	SME operators are financially incapable to employ and retain the required skilled professionals to grow and sustain their businesses.					
D37	Infrastructural facilities are an impediment to SMEs sustainability in Nigeria as they operate with epileptic power supply, unreliable telecommunication facilities, abysmal state of road networks, etc.					
D38	SMEs indigenously made goods/services are increasingly turning out to be very uncompetitive due to the cost of obtaining/maintaining substitute power supply					

	and other costs of production.					
D39	Poor management has resulted in high level of incompetence, inefficiency, wastage and under-utilization of resources available to SMEs in Nigeria.					
D40	Most of the SMEs are stuck at the evolutionary stage with low IT and communication skills constraining their process improvement and overall competitiveness.					
D41	The crux of the varied challenges inhibiting sustainable SMEs in Nigeria is a leadership problem.					
D42	Gender discrimination in leadership/management positions is noticeable in my enterprise					
D43	Women entrepreneurs are not afforded the same opportunities as their male counterparts.					
D44	SMEs in Nigeria are not sustained because there is a preference for male operators who may lack good exposure to leadership/management training, practices and do not keep abreast with modern day techniques.					
D45	SME operators lack the resilience and commitment for driving the business beyond the subsistent level and to fight for the recovery of a dwindling venture.					
D46	SMEs leaders/operators are expected to be inventive in creating sustainable SMEs business solutions but remain moribund due to lack of entrepreneur skills.					
D47	Lack of entrepreneurial skills therefore impedes SMEs adaptation to changing market conditions which require continues infusion of innovative ideas into the business.					

8.3 SEMI-STRUCTURE INTERVIEW

Section A: Respondent Demographics

Respondents Gender: Male Female

Respondents Age: 18-24 years 26-32years 34-40years 41-47years 48 & above

Marital Status: Single Married Divorced Widowed Prefer not to say

Qualification: WASSCE/GCE/SSCE ND/NCE HND/BSc Masters Doctorate Professorship

Experience: Below 5 years 6-10 years 10-15 years 16 – 20 years 21 years and above

Section B

How would you describe the Leadership models in your enterprise?

- Authentic leadership model (*This model describes a leader's ability to act on the right societal values to influence followers, and the followers' ability to follow and act according to the leader's traits*)
- Situational leadership model (*This also means the contingency model which is based on the principle that behaviour is determined and influenced by the situation*)
- Charismatic leadership model (*This model describes deeper level of personality-induced influence that has the ability to stimulate employees towards set organisational goals via the leader's personality*)
- Full Range leadership model (*This model is the combination of three elements: transformational leadership, transactional leadership and laissez-faire leadership which are seen to encapsulate most of the contemporary leadership behaviours*)

Can you give further explanation with example of any experience you have had with your previous and present manager in the display of the leadership model you have mentioned earlier?

In your opinion, do you think the model you have mentioned is particular to women leadership and has to a reasonable extent considered the following characteristics:

- Professionalism
- Clarity of thoughts
- Resilience
- Communication
- Responsiveness
- Resourcefulness

Can you say your other colleagues share the similar opinion as yours?

Do you have a preferred leadership model that in your opinion will positively encourage a sustainable SME?

Section B

In your opinion, do you think women leadership characteristics discussed in the first part of this interview will contribute to a sustainable SME in relation to?

- Effectiveness (Business Growth)
- Efficiency (Productivity)
- Timeliness and Quality
- Profitability
- Workplace environment

Will you say that your colleagues share similar opinion as yours?

Which leadership model would you suggest that best suits a woman leadership and will encourage a sustainable SME?

To round off this interview session, do you have any relevant information you think can further expand the key areas we have discussed?

Again, thank you for choosing to participate in this interview.